

Analysis of integrated planning models in logistics

Mohamed Ben Ahmed

A dissertation submitted to Molde University College -
Specialized University in Logistics
for the degree of Philosophiae Doctor

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Mohamed Ben Ahmed
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Mathematicians are like Frenchmen: whatever you say to them they translate into their own language and forthwith it is something entirely different.

Johann Wolfgang von Goethe

Preface

This thesis is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of *Philosophiae Doctor* (PhD) in Logistics at Molde University College, Molde Norway.

The work started in April 2018 and ended in July 2022, during which I have been employed as a Research Fellow at Molde University College and later at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology. The position was partly funded by the Research Council of Norway under the AXIOM project [grant number: 263031]. Additional support was provided by Molde University College in exchange for carrying out teaching duties.

The research presented here was conducted at Molde University College, under the supervision of professor Lars Magnus Hvattum and professor Arild Hoff. In addition, through an invitation from professor Agostinho Agra, the following research visit included work on the thesis: From January 10th to February 20th 2020, I visited the University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal, where I was assigned to office space in the facilities of the Department of Mathematics.

The main subject of the thesis is to study integrated mathematical models for particular logistic problems, namely the inventory routing problem, the production routing problem, and the airline scheduling problem. This includes developing new solution techniques and investigating how knowledge about the problems' specific characteristics can be utilized to improve the proposed techniques. The thesis is a collection of four papers presented in topical order of writing. The papers are preceded by an introductory chapter that relates them to each other and provides background information and motivation for the work.

The work has been evaluated by a committee consisting of professor Claudia Archetti from ESSEC Business School, Paris, France, professor Jesper Larsen from the Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark, and associate professor Johan Oppen from Molde University College, Molde Norway.

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I also thank the computer support center (IT-senteret) for giving me access to dearly needed computational power during my work at Molde University College. My thanks go to the library staff and the administrative team, whose assistance helped me to conduct my research activities efficiently. Furthermore, I thank all additional friends, colleagues, and fellow PhD students that I have had the pleasure to encounter during my studies, both in Molde, as well as in Trondheim.

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Mohamed Ben Ahmed
Molde, March 2023

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Chapter 1
Introduction

Chapter 1

Introduction

Logistics is a word that you often see on the side of trucks. Nevertheless, it has a more significant meaning. The Oxford Dictionary definition of *logistics* is first, “the activity of moving equipment, supplies and people for military operations”¹. Poor logistics helped defeat Napoleon, and later Hitler, on the road to Moscow and Stalingrad: both over-stretched their supply lines. The same problem occurred for Rommel in North Africa when his tanks lacked enough fuel to fight Montgomery effectively at El Alamein. Quite apart from military applications, logistics expand into a broad field of studies that involves economic considerations. In general, logistics are concerned with managing the flow of objects (specifically goods, information, money, and people) through time and space to create an added value [32]. For most organizations, it is possible to draw up a familiar list of key elements representing the major logistics activities. These will include transport, warehousing, inventory, packaging, and information. This list can be expanded once again to reveal more detailed aspects of the different elements. Some typical elements and activities are given in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: The key elements of logistics.

It is interesting to identify many dependencies between these elements; for example, transportation and inventory activities can be examined within the context of the broader supply chain. The conventional practice used by professionals and scientists was based on handling these elements independently, deteriorating the system’s overall performance and thereby generating additional costs. However, the recent logistic planning trends are oriented toward adopting integrated management policies where the entire logistic system is considered, not just an individual element or subsystem in isolation. This would, by some accounts, do more to boost profits and to achieve the best overall performance [63]. This vision of integration was accompanied by more focus on using sophisticated decision support tools from operations research (OR). The tasks that OR examines are complex and involve many activities. They include allocating facilities, designing delivery routes, scheduling crews, and managing inventory levels to quote the most studied logistic problems.

In the following, three classes of integrated logistic planning problems are outlined, namely the *inventory routing problem* (IRP), the *production routing problem* (PRP), and the *airline scheduling problem* (ASP). The focus of this brief introduction is first to describe the studied classes of problems and then to present a few relevant examples from the literature. The presented examples are not intended to provide a comprehensive overview of the existing literature on the topics but only to underline their complexity. Related problems’ extensions are mentioned and described when this is deemed important. Then follows

¹The Oxford Dictionary definition of logistics

a section commenting on the shared characteristics between the three classes of problems. After this short introductory text, the contributions of this thesis are given, first in an overview and then described in detail through four scientific papers. Therein, we also underpin a few promising research directions.

1.1 The inventory routing problem

Bell et al. [12] provided perhaps the earliest work considering the operational interplay between two separate problems of a distribution chain; namely distribution and inventory management problems in the industrial gas industry. This endeavor impelled a novel steady research stream on *inventory routing problems* (IRP). The IRP can be fairly presented as the integration of three interwoven decisions: inventory management, vehicle routing, and delivery scheduling. More specifically, a supplier must decide (i) when to serve a given customer, (ii) how much to deliver to this customer when it is served, and (iii) how to combine customers into vehicle routes. The objective is to minimize the total transportation and inventory holding costs. Figure 1.2 shows the involved decisions in the IRP.

Figure 1.2: Representation of a two-period inventory routing problem.

Following the seminal work of Bell et al. [12] the powerful idea of combining distribution and inventory management problems into a single framework was continually being refined and adapted to other industries, as well as to new fields of application. The adaptation of know-how from the areas of OR and computer science bolstered a rich scientific literature on the IRP. For survey articles, the reader is referred to Andersson et al. [5] and Coelho, Cordeau, and Laporte [27].

Besides, the adoption by several companies of the Vendor Managed Inventory (VMI) technique in supply chain management has partially driven the research in this area [7]. A motley of IRP variants and extensions have been described over the past 30 years, the vast bulk of which is encountered in real-life applications. We distinguish therefore between two broad classes of the IRP: “basic versions”, which are generic, and “rich versions”, which are more elaborate. The basic versions are described in Table 1.1. They are sorted according to seven aspects, namely, time horizon, structure, routing, inventory policy, inventory decisions, fleet composition, and fleet size.

Rich versions are multi-constrained problems with diverse patterns and operating rules that are often encountered in real-life applications. The most characteristic feature considers a different objective function. For instance, one could instead minimize routes’ total travel time [44], or could also optimize the number of operating vehicles in the solution [50]. Time windows may be incorporated depending on the application at hand [43, 46]. The fleet composition can be heterogeneous rather than homogeneous [3, 66]. Maritime applications of the IRP provided significant impetus for including these variations. Additional settings involve multiple depots with the possibility of open tours that have different origin and destination depots, or multi-day tours that span over several days [17, 56, 69]. Other labor restrictions may apply, which limits the route’s duration and enforce working time regulations [26, 53]. The problem can be

Table 1.1: Structural Variants of the IRP.

Decision	Aspect	Possible options		
Time	Horizon	Finite	Infinite	
Distribution	Structure	One-to-one	One-to-many	Many-to-many
	Routing	Direct	Multiple	Continuous
Inventory	Policy	Maximum level (ML)	Order-up-to level (OU)	
	Supply	Lost sales	Back-order	Nonnegative
Fleet	Composition	Homogeneous	Heterogeneous	
	Size	Single	Multiple	Unconstrained

Adapted from Andersson et al. [5].

extended by allowing split deliveries, i.e., serving a single customer by more than one vehicle, may add an extra degree of flexibility to the underlying problem [64, 68]. IRP variants with pickup and deliveries are also in the foreground, chiefly in recent years. In such a setting, items will be both picked up and delivered to customers, and precedence requirements may thus be applicable [6, 8]. Further extensions account for multiple products models which entail in turn collateral storage and transportation constraints [28, 52].

Another defining feature of rich IRPs is uncertainty. It can be in evidence through a variety of ways, such as uncertain demand quantities, uncertain customer availability, uncertain travel, and service times. By contrast to basic IRPs, which are deterministic, rich problems could be deterministic, stochastic, or dynamic. The stochastic inventory routing problem (SIRP) arises when a probabilistic distribution depicts the uncertain parameter. Information about uncertainty in dynamic inventory routing problem (DIRP) is gradually revealed over time, thereby repeated decisions have to be taken at different stages within the planning horizon, and earlier decisions affect later ones. The papers by Baita et al. [11] and Roldán, Basagoiti, and Coelho [57] contain a wealth of information on stochastic and dynamic IRP models. As a final note to this section, it is worth mentioning that the integration of routing and inventory decisions bears in practice a long-term, possibly infinite problem that is innately stochastic. Because of the intricacy of the problem, most of the contributions documented so far tended to reduce into a more basic form.

1.2 The production routing problem

The *production routing problem* (PRP) extends the basic IRP by considering lot-sizing decisions. Hence a manufacturer must decide (i) when and how much to produce a given product, (ii) when to serve a given customer, (iii) how much quantity of product to deliver to this customer when it is served, and (iv) how to combine customers into vehicle routes. The objective is to minimize the sum of setup costs, unit production costs transportation, and inventory holding costs. Figure 1.3 depicts an illustration of the PRP.

The PRP was formally introduced by Chandra [22], depicting the case where a single production facility produces and distributes goods to spatially distributed customers to meet their non-stationary demand. Following this seminal paper, a long, successful, and still-expanding body of literature about PRP and an innumerable number of its extensions have been enriching logistic studies. For a more comprehensive review, we refer the interested readers to Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [2], Díaz-Madroño, Peidro, and Mula [35], and Hrabec, Hvattum, and Hoff [42]. Studies on the PRP also differ into basic and rich variants. The basic versions are described in Table 1.2. They are sorted according to eight aspects, namely, number of plants, number of products, production capacity, inventory policy, inventory capacity, fleet composition, and fleet size, and vehicle capacity.

More advanced configurations of the PRP include customer delivery time windows where each customer must be serviced within a predefined time interval, and the vehicle must remain at the customer's location during service. Akin studies are found in Brahimi and Aouam [18] and Miranda et al. [51]. Another extension of the PRP is concerned with pick-up and delivery features, such as the ones studied by Fang, Du, and Qiu [37] and Golsefidi and Jokar [40]. Under this setting, a product can be picked up from several origins and delivered to other distinct destinations. Such an assumption complicates the PRP considerably because of the precedence constraints that derive from it. Lateral transshipments between customers have also been considered in the PRP framework by Avci and Yildiz [10]. The authors claimed that lateral transshipments reduced system costs and improved service quality.

Industrial applications of the PRP are driving the OR community to address new variants of the problem. For example, product shelf life is limited in many real-life PRP settings, and delivered quantities

Figure 1.3: Representation of a two-period production routing problem.

Table 1.2: Structural Variants of the PRP.

Decision	Aspect	Possible options		
Production	N. plants	Single	Multiple	
	N. products	Single	Multiple	
	Capacity	Limited	Unconstrained	
Inventory	Policy	Maximum level (ML)	Order-up-to level (OU) ML/OU	
	Capacity	Finite	Infinite	
Distribution	Fleet composition	Homogeneous	Heterogeneous	
	Fleet size	Single	Multiple	Unconstrained
	Capacity	Finite	Infinite	

Adapted from Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [2].

must be very small and take place on consecutive days. These ideas were formally put forward by Dayarian and Desaulniers [31] who modeled a PRP with perishable products. Other authors have included short life-span product management within the PRP as in Li et al. [45], Ghasemkhani et al. [39]. The studies on the production routing problem with reverse logistics (PRP-RL) drew inspiration from reusing products and materials. Under this setting, the production process is located on the reverse side of the supply chain, and the collection process precedes it [23, 24, 41]. Another variation of the PRP is concerned with reducing carbon emissions, sometimes referred to as the pollution-production routing problem [30, 55].

Some authors have recognized the multi-echelon structure that may exist within industrial applications of the PRP. For instance, Schenekemberg et al. [58] introduced a two-echelon production routing problem (2E-PRP) that emerged in the petrochemical industry. The structure defines a two-echelon supply chain with three layers (ethanol suppliers - refineries - gas stations), where vehicles pick up raw material from a supplier and deliver final products to gas stations. Production decisions are taken in between, and only direct shipments are allowed in the first echelon of the supply chain.

Finally, the PRP's customer demands can be unknown when a decision should be made. The resulting problem is called the stochastic production routing problem (SPRP). An early attempt to formulate the SPRP was presented by Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] where customers' demand is known only in a probabilistic sense. However, very few contributions [4, 41, 61] built upon this endeavor and attempted to formulate the SPRP. Perhaps, the research progress is impeded by the complexity of the problem. This leaves the question of whether recent development in computing machines and customized optimization solvers could thrust new solutions techniques ahead.

1.3 The airline scheduling problem

The *airline scheduling problem* (ASP) comprises the decisions required to make a flight schedule functional. A flight schedule in this regard is a timetable of predefined legs, while a leg is a flight from a specific origin to a destination at a given departure time. These decisions come under three broad subproblems [54]. First is the fleet assignment, which consists in deciding which type of plane should operate each scheduled leg while using the available aircraft and maximizing revenue. Second is the aircraft maintenance routing, which devises individual aircraft routes while ensuring that each aircraft is periodically scheduled for maintenance. Next, obtained routes are used in the crew pairing subproblem, which generates the sequence of legs the crew has to fly while respecting labor rules and minimizing crew costs. All of these must be solved a few months before the operation. Figure 1.4 shows the hierarchy of various phases of airline planning, including the airline scheduling problem.

Figure 1.4: The hierarchy of airline planning process.

As the decisions described above are interwoven, combining them at the decision-making stage is essential. This, however, creates a complex problem with a large number of variables in the model. Owing to its complexity, it is almost impossible to formulate and solve the complete ASP as a mathematical model. The problem is decomposed into sub-problems with less complexity, which are solved sequentially. One of the significant drawbacks of this approach is that an individual subproblem's solution might be suboptimal, eventually leading to incompatible, infeasible implementations [54]. The existing literature on the topic is hence classified into contributions dealing either with fleet assignment decisions [60], aircraft maintenance routing decisions [65], or crew scheduling decisions [34]. Thus far, few studies have attempted integrating two or more ASP components, as detailed in Eltoukhy, Chan, and Chung [36]. Very few of them managed to integrate the three planning components. For example, Cacchiani and Salazar-González [20] proposed a mixed-integer linear programming formulation for the ASP, which was later extended by Cacchiani and Salazar-González [19] by incorporating flight retiming options. Shao, Sherali, and Haouari [59] proposed an alternative formulation of the problem which includes more operational considerations, such as itinerary-based demands and other mandated aircraft and crew requirements. However, the common feature in all these contributions is that a massive computational effort is required to devise feasible solutions.

Traditionally, deterministic methods have been employed to solve the ASP, which neglect the possible uncertainty of the data. Nevertheless, in practice, flight schedules and operations are subject to numerous

uncertainties that are likely to disturb normal operations and cause flight delays. Aircraft mechanical problems, severe weather, crew sickness, airport curfews, and security are among the commonly encountered sources of uncertainties. Two lines of research have been pursued to overcome this negligence of uncertainty by explicitly modeling it. This gave rise to two ASP-derived problems: the stochastic ASP and the robust ASP. In the stochastic ASP, an uncertainty set is defined, which probabilistically describes the possible data realizations. The problem seeks a flight schedule performing best on average; the objective is to minimize the expected cost on all possible scenarios of the considered uncertainty set. An extension of the stochastic ASP is the stochastic ASP with recourse. In this approach, the aim is to compute a first-stage solution to the original problem, and an additional recourse strategy considers, in a second stage, the corrections to perform to a flight schedule for each possible scenario. Ma et al. [47] provide comprehensive documentation about the existing stochastic models for the ASP. The robust ASP models are nevertheless more conservative than the stochastic ones, as they focus on the worst-case scenario rather than the average case. The optimal solution corresponds to the one performing best under the worst possible scenario of the given uncertainty set. For a comprehensive literature on robust optimization models for the ASP, we refer to Clausen et al. [25] and Ma et al. [47]. Note that, in the literature, robustness in airline scheduling is used to describe two distinct concepts. First is the ability of a schedule to remain feasible and cost-effective in case of a disruption, which is called *stability*. Second is the ability of a schedule to adapt to changes, if necessary, which is called *flexibility*. This latter concept is highly relevant in the context of airline recovery operations.

1.4 Common characteristics between the studied problems

Although IRP, PRP, and ASP models represent three different kinds of logistics problems, and disparate solutions techniques have been proposed to solve them, they still share many mutual characteristics. We describe in what follows the most obvious similarities between the three studied problems.

- Hierarchical structure: A vertical dependency exists between the problem's decision variables, where some decision variables depict the values taken by other variables. For example, fixing the routing variables in the IRP context induces fixed values for the visit variables. Similarly, when the aircraft routing or the crew pairing decisions are selected, they determine the fleeting decisions in the ASP. However, the same reasoning is not valid in the opposite direction. This propriety might favor the application of relax-and-fix heuristics, as well as other MIP heuristics like RINS [29] and local branching [38].
- Block structure: The problem naturally decomposes into sub-problems, provided we take care of the interconnections between the problem's decisions. For example, in the case of the IRP, if the decisions about when to deliver to customers are made, the original problem decomposes by time periods into distinct routing sub-problems, which may facilitate its solution. Similarly, in the ASP, the fleet assignment variables prevent deciding which aircraft or crew will serve a given flight leg. If the values of these variables are determined, the problem decomposes by fleet types. These two cases have structural properties that can be advantageously exploited to design tailored solution methods. Archetti and Speranza [9] mentions that *cluster first-route second* approaches, which exploit this particular structure, were successful in solving routing problems. The same holds for using branch-and-price and benders decomposition approaches when solving airline planning problems.
- Planning horizon: The three problems assume a fixed planning horizon T , and the planning interval is separated into several time periods ($t = 1, \dots, T$). The decisions span over the entire horizon, and a decision made for one period impacts outcomes in the others. This aspect comes with a tremendous computational expense and at the cost of generating end-of-horizon effects. Models usually fail to account for the future impact of decisions made in the final period; only the immediate consequences of these decisions are considered.
- Non-stationary demand: The problems' demand rates vary over the entire planning horizon (unless otherwise assumed for simplification purposes). Although such an aspect makes the studied problems more realistic, it affects the quality of the developed solution methods. In particular, a variable demand induces different strategies/decisions to be implemented from one time period to another since no clear patterns can be identified over the entire planning horizon. For example, the allocation of nodes to vehicles (or fleet) and, consequently, the design of routes may differ between two

consecutive days. The same applies to replenishment and production strategies (e.g., quantity, frequency). Thus, it becomes less obvious to design computing techniques that capture these changing particularities while ensuring solution feasibility. Still, a tremendous computational effort is needed to devise optimal decisions.

- Limited & capacitated resources: The available resources are limited in terms of number and capacity. In airline scheduling, there is typically a finite number of crews and aircraft, each with a maximum passenger-carrying capacity. Similarly, the fleet size is finite in the IRP and the PRP, and vehicle, inventory, and production capacity restrictions may apply.

These similarities may influence the performance of the developed solution techniques. If such an influence is explored, it might advise about the best performing modeling methods and solution techniques to be adopted for such problems.

1.5 Summary of scientific contributions

Here follows a brief summary of the scientific contributions of the four papers in this thesis.

In Paper 1 [16], we investigate the consequences of explicitly maximizing profits rather than minimizing costs in an IRP setting. Four IRP models are implemented to take into account different market conditions: classic cost minimization, profit maximization with lost sales, profit maximization under monopoly, and profit maximization with variable production costs. The two latter variants include nonlinear expressions, which are linearized using a piece-wise linear transformation. Second, we examine the effect of varying the planning horizon's length on the quality of the decisions derived by solving an IRP model. In this regard, we develop a deterministic simulator that calculates the long-term effects of making IRP decisions over short planning horizons. In doing so, we diverge from the typical literature on the IRP, which tends to focus on increasing the problem size in terms of the number of nodes, while ignoring the consequences of considering an increased planning horizon. Computational experiments show that the length of the planning horizon can significantly affect decision-making performance. By considering planning horizons for up to eight periods, we show that end-of-horizon effects could be mitigated. However, in some cases, it is unclear how many periods are required to achieve stable performance. The obtained results also demonstrate the viability of considering profit maximization within an IRP setting, particularly when the company can adjust its production volumes.

In Paper 2 [62], we propose a new set of real-world-like benchmark instances for the IRP, intended to complement the existing ones. The generated instances exhibit new features that should allow for a better assessment of the performance of the existing methodology and perhaps stimulate further thinking about new solution methods for the IRP. A total of 270 new instances are generated. Each instance is characterized by varied problem parameters. We conduct extensive computational experiments using two high-quality solution methods to derive lower and upper bounds for each instance and to study the impact of the instances' features on the methods' performance. Our analysis shows that the instances have the desired level of diversity and complexity and suggests the need to adapt the existing methodology accordingly since the considered solution methods do not perform well on the set of new benchmark instances.

Paper 3 [15] presents an experimental study of matheuristic performance for the PRP considering different mathematical formulations. For the sake of this study, we develop a novel matheuristic consisting of three phases: an initialization phase, a completion phase and an improvement phase. The experimental study assesses the impact of various design alternatives and choices of matheuristics for the PRP. More specifically, we investigate the computational effects stemming from the choice of mathematical formulations, using valid inequalities, and alternating the starting solutions within a matheuristic framework. We perform extensive computational tests on benchmark PRP instances and use consistent performance measures to compare the performance of the matheuristic under the proposed configurations. The results give us a better view of the models that work better for a matheuristic in practice. In particular, they show that the contribution of a mathematical formulation to the matheuristic convergence is instance-specific and mainly attributable to the number of customers and the length of the planning horizon considered. It is also clear that integrating valid inequalities is highly beneficial, regardless of the considered mathematical formulation. Additionally, a matheuristic with a strong initial solution (in terms of optimality gap) is not necessarily superior to one with a weaker initial solution. Several reasons might explain this behavior, and they relate to the data instances' inherent features, the definition of the search neighborhood, and the particular features of solvers, all of which are details often not fully known to the practitioner.

Finally, Paper 4 [14] investigates the robust airline scheduling problem. We develop a mathematical formulation that adopts a node-arc flow network representation, thus yielding a polynomial number of variables and constraints. The proposed model accommodates several realistic considerations such as itinerary-based demands and various crew work rules. We induce robustness in the formulation by promoting schedules where crew follow aircraft and by reallocating the buffer times to minimize tight connections. A matheuristic solution framework, that combines a decomposition approach and a proximity search, is developed and implemented. The decomposition approach enables building a feasible solution to the problem, and the proximity search attempts to improve it iteratively. Both procedures require solving mathematical programming models in a heuristic framework which allows for easy implementation. Importantly, this solution method can be applied to general complex optimization problems where important decisions are optimized at the highest level. The computational experiments show that the method significantly improves flight schedules' robustness at the expense of a negligible drop in revenue.

1.6 Future research directions

Although some immediate scientific value is to be found in the four papers presented in this thesis, another result of the work is the possibility of highlighting some potential directions for future research.

In the context of the IRP, more work is still needed to apprehend additional aspects of real-world problems. This can be achieved through extending the new benchmark instances for the IRP to other rich variants by including additional attributes like multiple depots, multiple products, time windows, or a heterogeneous fleet of vehicles. These instances can also be converted to the case of the PRP by considering production attributes. Moreover, a dynamic library with different sets of benchmark instances for both the IRP and the PRP is a matter of necessity. It should contain the latest benchmark results and summarize the progress made by the researchers.

The new benchmark instances described in Paper 2 might stimulate further research avenues. One such avenue is to test multi-commodity flow formulations since these formulations scale well for instances with a large number of vehicles and periods [49]. A different one would investigate the use of branch-and-price algorithms, which appear to be more effective when vehicle routes contain a few numbers of customer visits [33]. A third promising research avenue is the design of novel metaheuristics and matheuristics algorithms. Algorithms that allow for partitioning the nodes into clusters by location or consumption rate might provide an impetus for obtaining good results, as suggested by Cao and Glover [21].

There is a lack of research on the optimal design of matheuristics solution methods for integrated planning problems. The existing knowledge on the behavior and the performance of matheuristic components when solving integrated problems is insufficient, albeit some attempts were proposed in Paper 3 in the context of the PRP. This late endeavor is worth to be pursued for other problems and might infer knowledge about how to design generic matheuristics that can gracefully transition between different planning problems. In addition, a potential future work includes the development of an automatic configuration tool, which replaces the manual exploration and tuning process of matheuristic components with an automated, reproducible one. The advantages of this technique are yet to be fully uncovered, although a few benefits were pointed out in Maniezzo, Boschetti, and Stützle [48].

For the ASP, we share the concerns expressed in the literature that the assumptions made on the revenue management function are too simplistic to express the real-life practices in revenue management systems [67]. Typically, an airline revenue function resembles the one described in the expected marginal seat revenue (EMSR) model by Belobaba [13], which allocates bookings limits for each fare class. The model starts with the higher fare class, and given the expected demand for that class, the exact number of seats is protected for future passenger requests. Then it continues with the next lower class until the authorized capacity of the aircraft is reached. Incorporating these calculations within the ASP might help to overcome the existing inaccuracies. However, the model's resulting objective function is non-linear but can be transformed using piece-wise linear approximations.

1.7 Summary of papers

This section lists the four papers that constitute the central part of the thesis. Since other contributors co-authored the four papers, the contribution of each co-writer is stated. As stated for each paper, versions of all four papers can be found from other sources, either as published journal papers or in working paper series. Also given a list of some of the conferences and workshops at which the material has been presented. Unless otherwise stated, these presentations were held by the PhD candidate.

Paper 1 was written in cooperation with my supervisor Lars Magnus Hvattum and former master students Onyemaechi Linda Okoronkwo and Edwin Chimezie Okoronkwo. Some of the materials in Paper 1 were researched as part of a Master’s Thesis in Logistics conducted at Molde University College by Onyemaechi Linda Okoronkwo and Edwin Chimezie Okoronkwo in 2019, while the initial research ideas are due to Lars Magnus Hvattum. A significant part of the implementation, refinements, computational experiments, and the initial writing was performed by the PhD candidate, although the final text was much-improved thanks to Lars Magnus Hvattum, the associate editor, and the two anonymous reviewers. The paper was published in *International Transactions in Operational Research*, volume 29, pages 2995–3030, 2021.

Presented at EURO (European Conference on Operational Research) 2019, Dublin, Ireland, July 2019. Presented at the annual PhD seminar at Molde University College, Molde, Norway, March 2020.

Paper 2 was written in cooperation with Jørgen Skålnes, Lars Magnus Hvattum, and Magnus Stålhane. The work that eventually led to Paper 2 started as early as the summer of 2020, and it rallied several participants from the AXIOM project. The material presented therein serves as a part of a thesis for both the candidate and Jørgen Skålnes, who is conducting a PhD degree at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU). The initial ideas for this work are due to Lars Magnus Hvattum and Magnus Stålhane, whose contributions expand to setting the concrete goals of the paper. The two PhD candidates jointly performed the algorithmic design, implementations, computational testings, and the initial writings, although additional analysis and refinements are due to Jørgen Skålnes. Paper 2 has been submitted to an international academic journal and is currently available as a working paper through the AXIOM project website .

This manuscript has not been yet presented at any conference or workshop.

Paper 3 was written together with Lars Magnus Hvattum and Agostinho Agra. The idea of evaluating the performance of a matheuristic for the production routing problem was due to professor Lars Magnus Hvattum. A consistent part of the work was done during my stay with professor Agostinho Agra at the Maths Department at the University of Aveiro, in Aveiro, Portugal, from January to February 2020. Most of the algorithmic design was completed by the candidate, as well as all implementations, computational testing, analyses, and writing. Agostinho Agra supplied useful ideas regarding several algorithmic elements. Significant improvements were made to the written work based on suggestions by the co-authors. Paper 3, as included in this thesis, was submitted for publication to an international academic journal and is currently available as a working paper through the AXIOM project website .

Part of the materials stated in this paper was presented at the the annual PhD seminar at Molde University College, Molde, Norway, April 2022.

Paper 4 is the final piece of this thesis, and was completed in cooperation with Maryia Hryhoryeva, Lars Magnus Hvattum, and Mohamed Haouari. Professor Mohamed Haouari suggested the *robust integrated airline fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing problem* as an interesting area for our research, set the goals for this paper, and supplied the research data required to carry out the experiments. The idea of using the proximity search algorithm was due to Professor Lars Magnus Hvattum. The PhD candidate developed the mathematical formulation of the problem, which the former master’s student Maryia Hryhoryeva later implemented as part of the fulfillment of her M.Sc. degree in Logistics at Molde University College. The candidate performed the matheuristic’s design and implementation, computational testing and analysis, and writing. The readability of this paper was enhanced in an early version by the co-authors and in a late version by the journal’s editor and the two anonymous reviewers. The paper was published in *Computers & Operations Research*, Volume 137, pages 105551, 2022.

Presented at the annual PhD seminar at Molde University College, Molde, Norway, April 2021. Presented at MESS2020+1 summer school on Metaheuristics, University of Catania, Catania, Italy, June 2021. Presented at EURO (European Conference on Operational Research) 2021, Athens, Greece, July 2021.

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Chapter 2

Long-term effects of short planning horizons for inventory routing problems

Chapter 2

Long-term effects of short planning horizons for inventory routing problems

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Mohamed Ben Ahmed Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway mohamed.ben.ahmed@himolde.no

Onyemaechi Linda Okoronkwo Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway

Edwin Chimezie Okoronkwo Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway

Lars Magnus Hvattum Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway Lars.M.Hvattum@himolde.no

Abstract

This paper presents a detailed study concerning the importance of the planning horizon when solving inventory routing problems (IRPs). We evaluate the quality of decisions obtained by solving a finite-horizon IRP. We also discuss the relevance of explicitly considering profit maximization models rather than the traditional cost minimization variant. As a means to this end, we describe four classes of the IRP corresponding to different types of markets. Two of them lead to non-linear models, which are linearized. Furthermore, we provide a deterministic simulator to evaluate the long term effects arising from using planning horizons of varying lengths when solving the IRP. A computational study is performed on cases generated from benchmark data instances. The results confirm that the long term performance of the IRP decisions is, in part, contingent on the length of the selected planning horizon. They also show that considering profit maximization instead of cost minimization leads to different decisions, generating considerably more revenue and profits, albeit not nearly as much as suggested by individual solutions to static IRPs with short planning horizons.

Keywords: Profit maximization, Path flow, Linearization, End effect, Simulation

2.1 Introduction

The inventory routing problem (IRP) integrates two fundamental logistic problems: inventory management and vehicle routing. Precisely, a supplier must decide *(i)* when to serve a given customer, *(ii)* how much to deliver to this customer when it is served, and *(iii)* how to combine customers into vehicle routes. Most often, the vehicles have limitations on the quantity of product they can transport, and the objective is to minimize the total transportation and inventory holding costs.

The IRP literature differentiates between instant, finite, and infinite planning horizons [4]. If at most one visit per customer is required, then it is deemed to be instant. The problem is termed finite if the length of the planning horizon $T < \infty$; otherwise, it is an infinite horizon problem. To reduce complexity, the IRP has often been modeled over finite planning horizons. However, this comes at the cost of generating end-of-horizon effects. A typical consequence is that customers' inventories are empty or near empty at the end of the last period. Since goods have a relatively high cost of shipping and holding, myopic decisions involve delivering fewer goods to customers in the final planning periods. If additional planning periods are modeled, this shortage would be corrected by more intensives deliveries, and the end effects would be transferred to the new final period. The distortions occur because models fail to account for the future impact of decisions made in the final period; only the immediate consequences of these decisions are considered. When more planning periods are considered, the end effects become less significant, but it becomes more intricate to compute solutions of the IRP.

Given these concerns, we investigate *(i)* the potential long term gain from explicitly maximizing profits rather than minimizing costs in an IRP setting, and *(ii)* the effect of varying the length of the planning horizon on the quality of the decisions obtained by solving a finite-horizon IRP model. First, we consider four different models for the IRP, that are adapted from Zaitseva, Hvattum, and Urrutia [40]. All of the models described hereafter account for limits on the number stops a vehicle can make within a route. These characteristics can be used to represent real-life applications of the IRP, such as perishable goods delivery problems and time-critical delivery problems. The models are:

1. **A basic cost minimization model.**
2. **A profit maximization model with lost sales.** By modifying the basic cost minimization model to allow for lost sales, a profit maximization variant can be obtained. Here, the company may scale back the volume of its deliveries, in case it is more profitable to accept penalties for lost sales than to service the full demand at a high transportation cost.
3. **A profit maximization model under monopoly.** This model examines the case of a price-setting company. The company can adjust its prices, whereupon the customer demands follow accordingly.
4. **A profit maximization model with variable production costs.** The last model extends the profit maximization with lost sales variant by incorporating variable production costs. Production costs can increase or decrease following the company's production volume.

The profit maximization models are generalizations of the cost minimization model. Therefore, when considering a particular instance and a fixed planning horizon, the profit obtained by profit maximization models are necessarily at least as good as the profit obtained by the optimal decisions from the cost minimization model. Zaitseva, Hvattum, and Urrutia [40] showed that the increase in profits could be substantial. However, just as end-of-horizon effects can influence the value of decisions in a given model, they can also distort the comparison between two different models. To properly assess the actual difference between cost minimization models and profit maximization models and the actual impact of varying the length of the planning horizon used when solving IRPs, we propose using simulation. In this simulation, decisions about scheduling, routing, and potentially pricing and production rates are determined by solving a sequence of IRPs. While simulation is an accepted tool for evaluating such policies in the face of uncertainty, this work shows that policies based on solving problems with finite planning horizons exhibit similar behavior even when no stochasticity is present. In summary, this paper makes the following contributions:

- We use a deterministic simulator to calculate the long-term effects of making decisions by solving IRPs with short planning horizons.
- We present path flow formulations of four distinct classes of the IRP, including profit maximization variants with non-linear expressions that are linearized.
- We perform an extensive computational study using benchmark test instances. The experiment is designed to examine the impact of three factors: the length of the planning horizon, the maximum route length allowed, and the market structure.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2.2 contains a review of relevant literature. In Section 2.3, we formally present the problem at hand and provide a detailed description of the proposed models. Next, in Section 2.4 we describe the deterministic simulator. This is followed by the results of extensive computational experiments in Section 4.5. Concluding remarks follow in Section 4.6.

2.2 Literature review

For recent surveys of research on IRPs, see the work by Andersson et al. [4] and Coelho, Cordeau, and Laporte [14]. In the following, we focus on contributions related to the planning horizon of IRPs (Section 2.2.1) and on profit maximization in IRPs (Section 2.2.2).

2.2.1 IRPs with long planning horizons

A substantial body of IRP literature is concerned with the deficiency of short planning horizons. Several notable contributions ventured to solve IRP for long planning horizons. Dror, Ball, and Golden [16] proposed a way to take into consideration what happens after the short-term planning period. The authors computed the stock-out probability, the average cost to deliver, and the anticipated cost of a stock-out for each customer and each day in the planning horizon. By dint of these metrics, they determined the optimal replenishment day, which yields a minimum expected total cost. If this day falls within the short-term planning period, the customer will be visited. Otherwise, an anticipated delivery is scheduled, and a future benefit is included within the objective. These computed values reflect the long term effects of short term decisions.

Bard et al. [9] formulated an extension of the ideas by Dror, Ball, and Golden [16] to address an IRP with satellite facilities. A satellite facility is a location apart from the depot where vehicles can be loaded. They proposed a rolling horizon framework, in which shipment schedules are determined over a two-week moving period. Only customers scheduled for the first week are routed. The two-week planning horizon is then shifted by a week, and the process is repeated. The routing decisions are fixed by employing three heuristics (randomized Clarke-Wright, GRASP, modified sweep). An analysis similar to Dror, Ball, and Golden [16] was performed to determine an optimal replenishment day for each customer. A handful of contributions adapted and enhanced these solution strategies and attempted to mitigate the effect of short term decisions, including Anily and Federgruen [5], Trudeau and Dror [38], and Jaillet et al. [23].

Archetti, Desaulniers, and Speranza [8] presented a new variant of the IRP in which the ratio between the total costs and the total delivered quantity, is minimized. This ratio represents the unitary distribution cost, and the problem was labeled the IRP with a logistic ratio. The authors' motivation for using this objective function is to avoid low inventory levels at the end of the planning horizon and capture the IRP's long-term impact. Using a branch-price-and-cut based-algorithm, the authors could optimally solve instances with up to 5 vehicles and 15 customers over three periods. Recently, Archetti, Coelho, and Speranza [7] proposed an exact iterative algorithm to solve larger instances with more customers and a longer planning horizon.

We encounter a more advanced treatment of long-term decisions in the cyclic IRP. It is a long-term decision problem where the distribution policy and vehicle routes, once computed for a baseline period, will remain the same in the following periods. Raa and Aghezzaf [34] brought forth a cyclic planning approach, in which a vehicle travels in every period of the cyclic planning horizon the same route to serve customers. Replenishment frequencies that minimize total costs are heuristically derived. With these patterns at hand, a steady-state distribution plan is constructed, which can be repeatedly reproduced no matter how long the planning horizon is. Later, Lefever, Aghezzaf, and Hadj-Hamou [27] reformulated the problem as a convex optimization problem and proposed a modified branch-and-bound procedure for its solution. Raa and Aghezzaf [33] extended the former approaches by integrating a fleet sizing problem. Vansteenwegen and Mateo [39] examined a particular case of the cyclic IRP where a single vehicle is at disposal and employed an iterated local search to solve it. Chitsaz, Divsalar, and Vansteenwegen [12] studied the multiple vehicles variant of the problem and solved it using a decomposition algorithm. Ekici, Özener, and Kuyzu [17], Zenker, Emde, and Boysen [41], Raa and Dullaert [35], and Dai, Gao, and Giri [15] provide further examples for solving the IRP over a perpetual time horizon. Cyclic IRP plans can mitigate the end-of-horizon effects since they allow for equal ending inventory levels at each planning period. However, a cyclic IRP is not necessarily appropriate when some parameters of the problem, such as customer demands, vary over time.

A completely different solution strategy for tackling long term IRPs is concerned with using rolling horizon heuristics (RHH). This approach operates by splitting up the planning horizon into shorter and more manageable periods. Rakke et al. [36] used a rolling horizon matheuristics when studying a maritime IRP. A later effort to incorporate rolling horizon matheuristics was performed by Agra et al. [1]. The authors developed a mathematical programming formulation for the problem and a heuristic algorithm, which uses a rolling horizon decomposition, local branching, and a feasibility pump procedure. The relevance of RHH is high for maritime IRPs since these naturally involve long planning horizons. However, a handful of studies have used RHH when solving basic IRPs [13].

Many of the contributions documented above tend to reduce the long term IRP into a more basic form. In doing so, they neglect the long-term impact of such decisions, and are in principle, still dealing with short planning horizons.

2.2.2 IRPs with profit maximization

A key characteristic of the class of IRPs with profit maximization is that the set of customers to be served and the demands to be satisfied are not necessarily known in advance. Therefore, a decision-maker must identify the customers to serve and determine their fill rates to maximize the profit. Revenue is usually associated with each customer to quantify their attractiveness. In other settings, a penalty cost for lost sales is attributed to each customer.

Several variations of this problem have been addressed in the literature. They respond to challenges faced by a logistic provider. In what follows, we provide a classification perspective that may help identify the relevance of IRPs with profit maximization models.

- **Lost sales.** For a supplier with limited resources (e.g., production, fleet), it may be impossible to meet customer demands. Only a proportion of demands can be fulfilled, while the remaining part is treated as lost sales and not backlogged. These shortages are discouraged by a penalty term specific to each customer. The objective is to choose a distribution policy that maximizes the profits (revenues minus costs). Chien, Balakrishnan, and Wong [11] proposed a day-to-day version of the problem where inventory holding costs are null. The solution approach breaks down the problem into two subproblems: an inventory allocation subproblem and a combined customer assignment and vehicle routing subproblem, both of which were solved to optimality. Numerous contributions have drawn inspiration from the seminal work of Chien, Balakrishnan, and Wong [11] and successfully incorporated lost sales within profit maximization models, e.g., Goyal and Gunasekaran [19], Al-Ameri, Shah, and Papageorgiou [2], Kleywegt, Nori, and Savelsbergh [24, 25], and Liu and Lee [28].
- **Customer selection.** In some applications, the supplier must select a subset of customers from those available in the market. For each selected customer, the supplier gets a revenue, while no penalty is incurred from those not selected. The objective is to maximize the sum of revenues minus operations costs. These variants are often encountered in the IRP's maritime applications, where a shipping company has a mix of contracted cargoes (spot) and optional cargoes. Hemmati et al. [22] described a profit maximization IRP that arises in tramp shipping. In that problem, revenue is collected from mandatory cargoes as well as optional cargoes. A two-phase heuristic was proposed to compute routes and schedules for the shipping company. Akin models with profit maximization are found in Grønhaug et al. [21], Stålhane et al. [37], Papageorgiou et al. [31], and Andersson, Christiansen, and Desaulniers [3].
- **Maximum collection.** The counterpart of delivery to customers is the collection from customers, where goods are picked-up from selective points to the depot based on profitability. The objective is to select pick-up points and quantities that maximize total profits. Montagné, Gamache, and Gendreau [29] introduced an application of this problem for waste collection. The developed approach relies on linear programming to build delivery schedules, while service routes are computed heuristically.
- **Variable production rates.** Some IRPs involve decisions regarding the production rate at the supplier. Solutions to these planning problems specify how much to produce, how much to sell, and how to combine deliveries within vehicle routes to maximize profits. The problem is not to be confounded with the production routing problem (PRP), which incorporates as well as lot-sizing decisions. Papageorgiou et al. [32] described a maritime variant of this problem, where a single product can be loaded from a set of production ports and discharged in specified consumption ports. An arc-flow based formulation was proposed to model the problem, while a branch-and-cut algorithm was developed to solve it. Similar problems were also considered by Grønhaug and Christiansen [20] and Papageorgiou et al. [30, 32].

2.3 Mathematical formulations for multiple classes of the IRP

In the following, we describe mathematical formulations for four classes of the IRP. The considered models are adapted from Zaitseva, Hvattum, and Urrutia [40] and correspond to specific market structures within the IRP.

While the models may seem incompatible, they can all be used for the same application, which involves a price-setting company whose unit production cost varies with the production rate, and that can choose not to meet the available demand at the cost of a penalty and lost sales. If prices and production quantities

are decided a priori, and it is assumed that all demands must be met, decisions can be made using a cost minimization model. If only prices and production quantities are decided a priori, a profit maximization model with lost sales can be used to make decisions. If only deciding the production rates a priori, a model for profit maximization under monopoly can be used. Finally, if only deciding prices a priori, a model for profit maximization with variable production costs can be used. These four models are now described in turn. For either model, its performance can be evaluated under the assumption that the decisions can be converted into a final profit over the long term.

2.3.1 Problem definition, terminology, and notation

The inventory routing problem considered in this paper is formally defined as follows. Let $G = (V, A)$ be an undirected graph where $V = \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$ is the vertex set, and $A = \{(i, j) : i, j \in V, i \leq j\}$ is the arc set, all defined over a finite and discrete time horizon H . Vertex 0 represents the depot whereas the set $V' = \{1, \dots, n\}$ corresponds to n customers. Let $T = \{1, \dots, H\}$ be a set of time periods. A fleet of m identical vehicles of capacity Q are stationed at the depot. At each time period $t \in T$, a quantity r_{0t} is produced by the supplier and r_{it} units are demanded by customer $i \in V'$. Production costs are represented by the unit cost function $f(r_{0t})$. A starting inventory level I_i^0 and a maximum inventory level U_i are given for each $i \in V$. The inventory levels cannot be negative. That is, stock-out is not allowed. A holding cost is charged both at the supplier and at the customers. The unit inventory cost at $i \in V$ is denoted by h_i .

The problem is to determine, at each time period $t \in T$ and for each customer $i \in V'$, a shipped quantity, and a traveled route, providing that:

1. Each customer $i \in V'$ is visited at most once.
2. Each vehicle performs at most one tour, delivering at most Q units, visiting at most L customers, and starting and ending at the depot 0.
3. Inventory levels at both the supplier and customers are nonnegative and must not exceed a maximum holding capacity.

For modeling purposes, we use a path-flow formulation where $K = \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ is the set of routes that satisfy the problem requirements. These routes are enumerated a priori and fed into the formulation. We first generate tours by representing them as random combinations (X_0, \dots, X_k) of $(0, \dots, n)$, where each tour contains at most L customers. Then, a travelling salesman problem (TSP) is solved for each tour to obtain the optimal sequencing of nodes. A symmetric cost matrix c_{ij} is defined on A . The cost of a route $k \in K$, denoted by c_k , is computed using the arc costs c_{ij} . Strictly speaking, given a route k that successively visits vertices i_0, i_1, \dots, i_p , $0 < p \leq L$, its associated cost is given by:

$$c_k = \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} c_{i_j i_{j+1}}.$$

Let a_{ik} be a binary coefficient equal to 1 if and only if customer $i \in V'$ belongs to route k . Define y_{kt} , a binary variable equal to 1 if and only if a route k is used in the optimal solution in period $t \in T$, and 0 otherwise. Continuous variables x_{ikt} represent the quantity of product delivered to each customer $i \in V'$ at time $t \in T$ by means of route $k \in K$. The inventory levels at the end of period t at the supplier and customers are described by I_{0t} and I_{it} , respectively.

2.3.2 Cost minimization

In this formulation, transportation and inventory holding costs, are minimized. We deliberately omit production costs since they are assumed to be fixed. Accordingly, the cost minimization variant can be stated as follows:

$$\min \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T} c_k y_{kt} + \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{t \in T} h_i I_{it}, \quad (2.1.1)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{k \in K} y_{kt} \leq m, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.1.2)$$

$$x_{ikt} \leq Q a_{ik} y_{kt}, \quad i \in V', k \in K, t \in T, \quad (2.1.3)$$

$$x_{ikt} \leq U_i - I_{i,t-1}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, k \in K, \quad (2.1.4)$$

$$\sum_{i \in V} x_{ikt} \leq Q y_{kt}, \quad t \in T, k \in K, \quad (2.1.5)$$

$$I_{it} = I_{i,t-1} + x_{ikt} - r_{it}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, k \in K, \quad (2.1.6)$$

$$I_{0,t} = I_{0,t-1} + r_{0t} - \sum_{i \in V'} x_{ikt}, \quad t \in T, k \in K, \quad (2.1.7)$$

$$I_{i0} = I_i^0, \quad i \in V, \quad (2.1.8)$$

$$0 \leq I_{0,t-1} + r_{0t} \leq U_0, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.1.9)$$

$$I_{it} \geq 0, \quad i \in V, t \in T, \quad (2.1.10)$$

$$(x) \text{ positive}, \quad (2.1.11)$$

$$(y) \text{ binary}. \quad (2.1.12)$$

The objective function (2.1.1) is to minimize the sum of all costs incurred by transportation, inventory holding at customers, and inventory holding at the supplier. Constraints (2.1.2) restrict the maximum number of routes in a solution to the number of available vehicles while constraints (2.1.3) ensure that a customer is visited at most once during each period, $t \in T$. Constraints (2.1.4) establish that if a customer is visited, the quantity delivered is such that the maximum inventory level is not exceeded. The vehicle capacity constraints are provided by constraints (2.1.5). Furthermore, inventory balance for customer nodes, defined at the end of each period, is ensured in constraints (2.1.6). Inventory levels at the supplier are represented by (2.1.7). The initial conditions for the inventory levels are given by constraints (2.1.8), and the inventory bounds are enforced by constraints (2.1.9)-(2.1.10). Finally, constraints (2.1.11)-(2.1.12) set the domains for the decision variables. Given integer values of x satisfying constraints (2.1.6)-(2.1.7), constraints (2.1.6)-(2.1.7) necessarily induce the I -variables to be integer-valued.

2.3.3 Profit maximization with lost sales

The seller can earn a sales revenue of p_0 per unit of product consumed by customer $i \in V'$ in period $t \in T$, which is the unit price for that customer. Let b_i a penalty for each unit of unsatisfied demand, while $f(r_{0,t})$ a function that approximates the unit production cost. We also introduce a new decision variable w_{it} that represents the proportional amount of product consumed by customer $i \in V'$ at period $t \in T$. Accordingly, the profit maximization IRP with lost sales becomes:

$$\max \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} p_0 w_{it} - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T} c_k y_{kt} - \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} h_i I_{it} - \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} b_i (r_{it} - w_{it}) - \sum_{t \in T} f(r_{0,t}) r_{0,t}, \quad (2.2.1)$$

subject to

$$(2.1.2) - (2.1.5), \quad (2.1.7) - (2.1.10),$$

$$I_{it} = I_{i,t-1} + \sum_{k \in K} x_{ikt} - w_{it}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (2.2.2)$$

$$0 \leq w_{it} \leq r_{it}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (2.2.3)$$

$$(x, w) \text{ positive}, \quad (2.2.4)$$

$$(y) \text{ binary}. \quad (2.2.5)$$

The objective function (1.1) maximizes the earned net profit, which is equal to the total revenues minus transportation, inventory holding, and production costs as well as a penalty term that is induced by unsatisfied demands. Constraints (2.2.2) are inventory conservation constraints at customer $i \in V$, linking the inventory of period t with that of period $t - 1$, plus any deliveries minus the consumption w_{it} . Constraints (2.2.3) guarantee for each customer $i \in V$ that the consumed quantity of products in period t

does not exceed the preset demand r_{it} . The routing constraints and inventory conservation constraints at supplier are identical to (2.1.2)-(2.1.5) and (2.1.7)-(2.1.10). Finally, constraints (2.2.4)-(2.2.5) define the integrality conditions of variables.

2.3.4 Profit maximization under monopoly

We introduce the pricing variable p_i , representing the revenue per unit consumed at customer $i \in V'$. There is a maximum price p_{max} , and the demand, $r_{it} = g(p_i)$, is a decreasing function of the price.

Proposition 2.3.1. *A demand curve in a monopolistic market can be a linear downward-sloping curve. To sell more, the seller must decrease the price; when reducing the sales, the prices can increase [26, Chapter 13]. Accordingly, it can be approximated by a function of the type $g(p_i) = u_1 p_i + u_2$, $i \in V$, where $u_1, u_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, and u_2 have strictly negative values.*

Using these definitions, we can formulate the monopolistic variant of the IRP as follows.

$$\max \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} p_i w_{it} - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T} c_k y_{kt} - \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{t \in T} h_i I_{it} - \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} b_i (g(p_i) - w_{it}) - \sum_{t \in T} f(r_{0,t}) r_{0,t}, \quad (2.3.1)$$

subject to

$$(2.1.2) - (2.1.5), \quad (2.1.7) - (2.1.10), \quad (2.2.2),$$

$$0 \leq w_{it} \leq g(p_i), \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (2.3.2)$$

$$0 \leq p_i \leq p_{max}, \quad i \in V', \quad (2.3.3)$$

$$(x, w, p) \text{ positive}, \quad (2.3.4)$$

$$(y) \text{ binary}. \quad (2.3.5)$$

The objective function (2.1) is to maximize the total earned profits. Constraints (2.2) ensure that the consumed amount of product by each customer $i \in V'$ does not exceed the demand, $r_{it} = g(p_i)$. Constraints (2.3) ensure the restriction on the maximum allowed price, while (2.4)-(2.5) define the integrality conditions for the variables. The remaining set of constraints are reproduced from the previous model.

Remark 2.3.2. The objective function (2.1) contains a non-linear term $\sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} p_i w_{it}$, which is the product of two variables (w) and (p). We emphasize that this term is non-separable.

Proposition 2.3.3. *We can derive an equivalent mixed-integer linear programming model for the IRP under monopoly by applying an approximating piecewise linear function, upon the transformation of the non-separable function.*

The linearization process, as well as the resulting linear model, are described in Appendix A.

2.3.5 Profit maximization with variable productions costs

We introduce the variable $R_{0,t}$ representing the production rate in time period $t \in T$, and the total production cost $f(R_{0,t})$ as a function of the production rate.

Proposition 2.3.4. *The average total cost is equal to the sum of the average fixed cost and average variable cost. It has a U-shape because these two components vary in opposite directions when production increases (see Krugman and Wells [26], Chapter 11). Thus, the average total cost function can be approximated by a function of the type $f(R_{0,t}) = u'_1 R_{0,t} + \frac{u'_3}{R_{0,t}} + u'_2$, $t \in T$, where u'_1, u'_2 , and $u'_3 \in \mathbb{R}^+ \setminus \{0\}$.*

The profit maximization variant with variable production costs describes as follows:

$$\max \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} p_0 w_{it} - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T} c_k y_{kt} - \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{t \in T} h_i I_{it} - \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} b_i (r_{it} - w_{it}) - \sum_{t \in T} f(R_{0,t}) R_{0,t}, \quad (2.4.1)$$

subject to

$$(2.1.2) - (2.1.6), \quad (2.1.8), \quad (2.2.2) - (2.2.3),$$

$$I_{0,t} = I_{0,t-1} + R_{0,t} - \sum_{i \in V'} x_{ikt}, \quad t \in T, k \in K, \quad (2.4.2)$$

$$0 \leq I_{0,t-1} + R_{0,t} \leq U_0, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.4.3)$$

$$0 \leq R_{0,t} \leq r_{max}, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.4.4)$$

$$(x, w, R) \text{ positive}, \quad (2.4.5)$$

$$(y) \text{ binary}. \quad (2.4.6)$$

The objective function (3.1) maximizes the total revenue minus transportation, inventory holding, production costs, and the penalty term for lost sales. Constraints (2.4.2) define the inventory at the supplier, while Constraints (3.2) prohibit stock-outs at the supplier. Constraints (2.4.4) require that the total produced amount does not exceed the production capacity. Constraints (2.4.5)-(2.4.6) represent the logical restrictions. The remaining constraints are identical to those described in the monopoly variant of the IRP.

Remark 2.3.5. The objective function (3.1) includes a quadratic term $\sum_{t \in T} f(R_{0,t})R_{0,t}$ that is equivalent after factorization to $\sum_{t \in T} u'_1 R_{0,t}^2 + u'_2 R_{0,t} + u'_3$.

Proposition 2.3.6. *We can derive an equivalent linear model representation of the IRP with variable production costs by applying an approximating piecewise linear function.*

The linearization process, and the linear counterpart of this problem are described in Appendix B.

2.4 Deterministic simulator for the IRP

In this section, we address the issue of evaluating IRP decisions made using the optimization models over a longer time horizon, so that the consequences of end-of-horizon effects can be measured. For this purpose, we implement a deterministic simulator that embeds decisions made from the optimization model, which is updated with fixed time increments. Fagerholt et al. [18] formerly investigated the idea of combining simulation and optimization similarly in the context of strategic maritime planning. The simulator developed in this paper is built upon three phases: an optimization stage, an update procedure, and a time advance mechanism. Figure 5.1 illustrates the general steps of the simulation framework.

The procedure operates by initializing the system state, as well as the simulation clock. The system state contains all available information about customer demands, starting inventory levels, and pricing (i.e., input parameters of the mathematical model). The optimization stage relies on solving an IRP model whose planning horizon H and start date t are specified by the simulation clock. Whenever the optimization model is invoked, distribution, production, and pricing decisions, over H periods are determined, out of which the decisions for the first Δt periods are implemented. The system state is updated afterward to account for these changes, and performance metrics, such as incurred costs and profits, are recorded. Next, the simulation clock is advanced with a fixed time increment ($\Delta t \leq H$), the current time (t) is updated, and the procedure is reiterated. The simulation continues until reaching the end of the simulation horizon at S . Figure 2.2 describes the time advance mechanism between iterations. At each time instant (t), information about customers' demand is known for the next H periods.

2.5 Computational study

In this section, we present computational experiments that were carried out on data instances of the IRP adopted from Archetti et al. [6]. All runs were made on a PC equipped with an Intel Core i5-6300U CPU running at i7-8700, with 16GB of RAM. The mathematical models described in Section 2.3 and the simulation framework described in Section 2.4 were coded in AMPL language and compiled with CPLEX Optimization Studio 12.8 using its default setting.

2.5.1 Description of problem instances

The data set comprises nine generic instances, hereafter referred to as Ins_n_L , where n corresponds to the number of customers, $n \in \{5, 10, 15\}$, and L represents the maximum route length, $L \in \{2, 3, 4\}$.

Figure 2.1: Generic framework of the deterministic simulation.

Figure 2.2: Illustration of the time advance mechanism.

A fleet of $m = 3$ identical vehicles is used in each instance. Data related to the supplier, customers, and vehicles' capacities are kept as in Archetti et al. [6]. More specifically, the production quantity r_{it} consumed by a customer $i \in V'$ at time $t \in T$ is constant over time, and represented by an integer value in the interval $[10, 100]$. Inventory holding costs are selected in the interval $[0.1, 0.5]$. For each of the nine instances, the planning horizon is varied in the range $H = 1, \dots, 8$.

Parameter values for the four different models are set to correspond to the cost minimization case with standard parameter values from the benchmark instances. Hence, the production function f is given by $f(r) = 5 \times 10^{-4}r + \frac{3}{r} + 2$, where the production rate r can be either stationary or variable. The maximum production rate r_{max} was set equal to the sum of customers' demands. Similarly, the demand function g

is defined by $g(p) = -2.5p + 113$, where the price limit p_{max} is equal to 41. Given fixed demand values, the corresponding price can be calculated by the inverse function g^{-1} . The penalty term for unsatisfied demanded b_i is a proportion of the price and is set to $0.2p_i$. In the particular case of monopoly, penalty values were fixed a priori and were given values equal to those obtained in the other models.

Five grid points are used for the piece-wise linear transformation of the objective function in the monopoly case. Likewise, five grid points are selected to transform the non-linear terms in the IRP model with variable production costs. Further empirical studies can be carried out to determine the optimal number of grid points; however, this is beyond this paper’s scope. The simulation length (S) was set to 30 days, and jumps of $\Delta t = 1$ day in time are used to reproduce a real planning situation and provide maximum flexibility for re-planning. It implies that for each simulation, 30 calculations of IRP decisions are conducted. A time limit of 30 minutes is enforced in each step of the simulation, providing an overall time limit of approximately 15 hours per simulation run.

2.5.2 Performance of the cost minimization model

In this section, we discuss several experiments to test the long-term quality of policies produced by a cost minimization variant of the IRP. We examine the effect of varying the length of the planning horizon on the performance of IRP decisions. Figure 2.3 presents a summary of the results grouped by the number of customers. The horizontal axis represents the planning horizon, and the vertical axis represents recorded profits. A significant performance difference appears between one-period and eight-period tests. We see also that the profits obtained are, in general increasing with the length of the planning horizon. Thus, there is evidence that a potential gain can be achieved by selecting longer planning horizons.

Figure 2.3: Effect of varying the length of the planning horizon for the cost minimization case.

When planning horizons are short and the maximum route lengths low, the end of horizon effects can lead to simulations where the encountered IRPs do not have any feasible solutions. This happens

when $L = 2$ and $n = 15$, as well as for $L = 2$ and $n = 10$ with $H = 1$, and these results are omitted from Figure 2.3. For more detailed results, the reader can refer to Tables 2.6-2.8 in Appendix C.

2.5.3 Performance of the profit maximization model with lost sales

In Figure 2.4, we present the results of tests conducted for the profit maximization case with lost sales. Again, higher profits are obtained for tests with longer planning horizons. In all tests, we were able to derive feasible decisions for the IRP with profit maximization. In contrast to the cost minimization variant, allowing lost sales induces more flexibility in the IRP solutions, thereby avoiding stock-outs at customers at the cost of added complexity.

Figure 2.4: Effect of varying the length of the planning horizon for the case of profit maximization with lost sales.

Detailed experimental results are listed in Tables 2.9-2.11 in Appendix C. They show high inventory costs at the supplier, low transportation costs, and low inventory holding costs at customers for reduced planning horizons. These cost patterns indicate near-empty inventories at customers; meanwhile, inventories are full at the supplier. Also, high costs of lost sales are recorded for short planning horizons; however, these costs decrease when the IRP is solved with longer planning horizons. A natural explanation is that short term decision involves delivering less to customers. In the short run, it is more profitable to pay the penalty for unsatisfied customers rather than mobilizing resources.

2.5.4 Performance of the profit maximization model under monopoly

Figure 2.5 summarizes the results of experiments conducted for the case of a price-setting company. The corresponding mathematical model is harder to solve, and in 50% of the simulations, optimality cannot be proven within the 30-minute time limit for all the individual IRP instances encountered. Furthermore, the gap to the dual bound can be up to 62% on average for the hardest instances. Instances that yield

an average gap higher than 1% are highlighted by using a white fill color in Figure 2.5. These large optimality gaps affect the slope of the profit function, which behaves differently from the other models. Better results are sometimes recorded for shorter planning horizons, where better solutions can be found for the instances encountered. This effect is most apparent for the instances with $n = 15$ customers.

Figure 2.5: Effect of varying the length of the planning horizon for the monopoly case.

For a price-setting company, the customer demands can be decreased by increasing the unit price. This does happen in the test cases examined here, with the consequence that inventories at the supplier become almost full. Besides, the cost of lost sales can be higher when using the monopoly model. This occurs when the solution implies a price and a corresponding demand such that the demand cannot be completely satisfied. For instance, the cost of lost sales is higher when the planning horizon or the route length is short. In this case, the inventory levels at the supplier may become very high. The results show that substantial savings can be achieved when the planning horizon is longer. The savings are mainly due to a reduction in transportation costs. A more limited reduction is owed to a decrease in costs at the supplier. The detailed cost results are shown in Tables 2.12-2.14 in Appendix C.

2.5.5 Performance of the profit maximization model with variable production costs

For the final IRP-variant, with variable production costs, almost all IRPs encountered were solved to optimality, except in 11 of the simulations. For these simulations, the maximum recorded optimality gap was 1.56%. The single simulation with an average optimality gap above 1% is highlighted in Figure 2.6 using a white fill color. It appears that a stable performance is obtained once the length of the planning horizon reaches three periods.

Low inventory costs are incurred at the supplier. Since the production rates can be adjusted, the model forces the company to produce no more than necessary. In contrast, inventory costs at customers, respectively inventory levels, are high. If the planning horizon is longer, the optimal decisions involve increasing the production rate in early periods, leading to a lower unit production cost and, eventually,

further savings. A longer horizon offers more possibilities for the coordination of production and transportation. Detailed results are presented in Tables 2.15-2.17 in Appendix C.

Figure 2.6: Effect of varying the length of the planning horizon for the variable production costs case.

2.5.6 Comparing the different classes of the IRP

Given the results provided in the previous section, we assess the long-term gain of using profit maximization in the IRP, rather than deciding prices and production rates a priori while not allowing lost sales. We make the following comparisons:

- *Cost minimization vs. profit maximization with lost sales.* The profit maximization model with lost sales performs better than or equal to the cost minimization variant in only 47 out of 72 simulations. Allowing lost sales leaves room for flexibility in planning and induces substantial savings in transportation and inventory holding costs. These differences are considerable when route lengths are short, in which case allowing lost sales results in superior profits. When the route length is very restrictive, it is more important to select the customers to be served wisely. However, when the planning horizon is longer, the differences in quality between the two policies tend to be smaller. For $H = 6$, the cost minimization model leads to 0.45% higher profits than the lost sales model. From a purely theoretical perspective, the model with lost sales should perform at least as well as the cost minimization model: the only difference is increased flexibility through the possibility of losing sales. This strongly suggests that the lost sales model's performance depends on having an even longer planning horizon than tested in this research.
- *Cost minimization vs. monopoly.* When compared to the cost minimization variant, the monopoly variant records the overall best profit values. It outperforms the former in 91.6% of the simulations, while the average improvement in profit is 12.9%. The difference in quality reaches its peak with

medium length planning horizons (generally $H = 3$, or $H = 4$). However, the monopoly model is too complex to allow optimal solutions to be found within the allotted running time. This means that for test cases with longer planning horizons and more customers, the potential improvement from allowing prices to be optimized is likely underestimated.

- *Cost minimization vs. variable production costs.* The results demonstrate that the variable production costs policy consistently outperforms the cost minimization policy. Deciding about the production rate leads to lower unit production costs and lower inventory holding costs. Furthermore, the differences in quality appear to increase with the length of the planning horizon. Planning over longer planning horizons leads to better coordination of production and distribution. However, the variable production cost model produces solutions with almost empty inventories at the supplier, exemplifying an end-of-horizon effect that increases the risk of making bad decisions unless the planning horizon is sufficiently long.

Table 2.1: Performance comparison of profit maximization models with regard to a baseline cost minimization test case with $H = 3$

n	L	Baseline profit	(%) improvement with lost sales	(%) improvement with monopoly	(%) improvement with variable production costs
5	2	91,955	5.1	28.7	21.0
5	3	101,250	1.6	17.1	7.6
5	4	103,090	-1.1	14.8	8.1
10	2	187,839	5.6	16.2	18.8
10	3	202,463	-0.4	10.9	11.9
10	4	203,776	-0.7	11.8	10.9
15	2	*	*	*	*
15	3	336,502	0.0	17.2	9.0
15	4	340,586	0.0	17.9	9.0

* This setting led to infeasible IRP instances.

Another way to compare the performance of the different IRP policies is to compute their relative gap. Table 2.1 shows the performance ratio $(P^x - P^c)/P^c$, where P^x refers to the profit recorded by a profit maximization model, and P^c represent the profit obtained by the cost minimization model. All of them are computed for a baseline test case with $H = 3$. The table shows that substantial savings can be achieved by adopting different profit maximization policies for the IRP. We also observe that increasing the planning horizon has a more pronounced effect for instances with small number of customers than in instances with large number of customers.

Our findings can be juxtaposed with those obtained by Zaitseva, Hvattum, and Urrutia [40], where the authors conducted two experiments using a single planning instant to evaluate the quality of the different profit maximization policies. The two instances solved varied in terms of the length of the planning horizon, and the number of customers. Their results indicated that adopting a profit maximization policy for a price-setting company generates up to 283% in increased profits for a 5-customer instance, and up to 96% in increased profits for a 10-customer instance. Based on our simulations, these results are highly exaggerated, with more appropriate estimates being less than 15% and 8% profit increases, respectively. The discrepancy is due to the myopic nature of the IRP models: They merely consider the immediate gain, rather than anticipate the future effects taken into account through the simulations.

2.5.7 Investigating the impact of route limit constraints

In the results so far, it can be seen that increasing the maximum route length from three to four visits has a relatively small effect on the final profits. In this section, we examine how IRP decisions change when the route length limitations are lifted completely. We run new tests for instances with five customers with a full enumeration of routes. Tables 2.2-2.5 present results of tests conducted for the unconstrained versions of our IRP models.

2. Long-term effects of short planning horizons for inventory routing problems

Table 2.2: Summary of cost minimization results for eight tests with $n = 5$ and no limit on the maximum route length.

H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	TP
1	3.1	0.0	50,295	30,743	6,950	373	97,281
2	4.0	0.0	52,081	32,678	5,657	1,518	95,495
3	6.1	0.0	44,486	25,089	5,614	1,554	103,090
4	11.5	0.0	41,523	22,098	5,875	1,321	106,053
5	17.3	0.0	42,974	23,535	5,825	1,386	104,602
6	32.7	0.0	42,130	22,711	5,846	1,344	105,446
7	57.2	0.0	41,659	22,220	5,713	1497.67	105,917
8	73.4	0.0	41,002	21,556	5,933	1,284	106,574

Table 2.3: Summary of profit maximization with lost sales results for eight tests with $n = 5$ and no limit on the maximum route length.

H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
1	4.2	0.0	50,516	30,620	7,122	355	191	96,107
2	8.5	0.0	52,081	32,678	5,657	1,518	0	95,495
3	26.9	0.0	44,591	24,912	5,694	1,564	192	102,025
4	55.3	0.0	40,929	21,498	5,849	1,352	0	106,647
5	192.4	0.0	43,233	23,566	5,978	1,339	122	103,731
6	328.3	0.0	41,272	21,849	5,873	1,321	0	106,304
7	535.8	0.0	41,168	21,717	5728.2	1,494	0	106,408
8	1243.1	0.0	41,001	21,556	5,937	1,279	0	106,575

Table 2.4: Summary of profit maximization under monopoly results for eight tests with $n = 5$ and no limit on the maximum route length.

H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
1	4.8	0.00	54,568	39,724	2,582	33	0	117,634
2	14.8	0.00	52,751	37,676	2,171	513	162	118,738
3	53.7	0.00	51,889	37,243	1,602	645	170	118,982
4	235.5	0.00	49,567	34,775	1,518	828	217	120,456
5	1,733.7	0.00	49,804	35,002	1,521	944	109	120,545
6	8,503.2	0.00	48,080	32,900	1,582	1,059	310	121,289
7	42,790.3	0.32	49,206	34,075	1,541	1,140	222	120,552
8	54,286.4	0.99	49,541	34,345	1,640	1,139	187	120,286

Table 2.5: Summary of profit maximization with variable production costs results for eight tests with $n = 5$ and no limit on the maximum route length.

H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	PC	Lost sales	TP
1	2.8	0.0	47,218	36,248	364	48	10,468	90	99,909
2	3.8	0.0	35,992	24,605	248	423	10,393	323	109,971
3	7.609	0.0	36,116	24,795	223	511	10,576	12	111,403
4	9.7	0.0	35,016	23,442	284	657	10,633	0	112,560
5	19.5	0.0	35,216	23,599	336	648	10,630	4	112,338
6	56.8	0.0	33,825	22,222	278	693	10,632	0	113,751
7	108	0.0	34,049	22,253	321	805	10,615	55	113,252
8	294	0.0	34,442	22,565	324	848	10,705	0	113,134

Observe that 15 out of the 32 unconstrained tests record higher profits than tests where the maximum number of stops is enforced. An increase in the route size results in lower transportation costs and an increase in profits in consequence. We also observe that the gain earned by using a maximum route

size is relatively small in terms of the total profits. The average increase in profit is 0.09% for the basic cost minimization model, 0.15% for the profit maximization model with lost sales, 0.23% for the profit maximization model with monopoly, and 0.00% for the variable production costs model.

Interestingly, for 17 tests out of 32, it seems beneficial to enforce route limit constraint. The explanation may be simple. When only a few customers are assigned to a vehicle, they can be served with higher quantities. In the longer run, this translates into fewer visits, and subsequently, lower transportation costs.

2.6 Concluding remarks

The contribution of this paper is twofold. First, we investigated the consequences of explicitly maximizing profits rather than minimizing costs in an IRP setting. Four IRP models were implemented to take into account different market conditions: classic cost minimization, profit maximization with lost sales, profit maximization under monopoly, and profit maximization with variable production costs. The two latter variants include non-linear expressions, which are linearized using a piece-wise linear transformation. Second, we examined the effect of varying the planning horizon's length on the quality of the decisions derived by solving an IRP model. In this regard, we developed a deterministic simulator that calculates the long-term effects of making IRP decisions over short planning horizons. In doing so, we diverge from the typical literature on the IRP, which tends to focus on increasing the problem size in terms of the number of nodes, while ignoring the consequences of considering an increased planning horizon.

Extensive computational experiments show that the length of the planning horizon can significantly affect decision making performance. By considering planning horizons for up to eight periods, we showed that end-of-horizon effects could be mitigated. However, in some cases, it is unclear how many periods are required to achieve stable performance. The obtained results also demonstrate the viability of considering profit maximization within an IRP setting, particularly when the company can adjust its production volumes.

Several research avenues appear promising to enhance the proposed study. The consideration of larger test instances is one such avenue. A different one would take into account even longer planning horizons. A third promising research avenue is the utilization of heuristic mechanisms to derive IRP decisions. The exploration of this latter direction could provide a significant impetus to solve IRP models with long planning horizons.

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Appendix 2.A Linearization process of IRP model under monopoly.

To enhance the solvability of the proposed non-linear IRP under monopoly, we first apply a transformation technique to reduce the model to a separable form. Next, we use a piecewise linear approximation to derive an equivalent linear formulation. We start by recalling the nonseparable term in the objective (2.1) needed throughout:

Furthermore, we define the ensuing substitutions:

$$\alpha_{it} = \frac{1}{2}(p_i + w_{it}), \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\beta_{it} = \frac{1}{2}(p_i - w_{it}), \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\alpha_{it}, \beta_{it} \geq 0, \quad i \in V', t \in T. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Without loss of generality and for simplicity of description, we assume that the domains for (z) and (p) are used to define the auxiliary variables (α) and (β) . Strictly speaking, given $[0, p_{max}]$, respectively $[0, Q]$, the domain of (p) , respectively of (z) , then (α) and (β) are defined over $[l_\alpha, u_\alpha]$, respectively $[l_\beta, u_\beta]$, such that:

$$[l_\alpha, u_\alpha] = [0, \frac{1}{2}(p_{max} + Q)], \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$[l_\alpha, u_\alpha] = [0, \frac{1}{2}(p_{max} - Q)]. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

We notice the product $p_i z_{it}$ can be replaced by $\alpha_{it}^2 - \beta_{it}^2$, as long as the domains are preserved. Using the identities (A.5)-(A.6), we obtain:

$$\sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} p_i w_{it} = \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} (\alpha_{it}^2 - \beta_{it}^2). \quad (\text{A.10})$$

The expression (A.10) contains now non-linear functions α_{it}^2 and β_{it}^2 of single variables, and is separable.

The separable problem defined in (A.10) can be approximated into a linear form by replacing each nonlinear function with a piecewise linear approximation. For illustration, consider the function θ defined by $\theta(\mu) = \mu^2$. In general, the function θ can be approximated for any finite interval $[a, b]$ via the grid points μ_1, \dots, μ_n by the piecewise linear function $\hat{\theta}$

$$\hat{\theta}(\mu) = \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \theta(\mu_j), \quad \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j = 1; \lambda_j \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where at most two λ_j -variables are positive, and they must be adjacent. This condition can be modeled using binary variables s_j for $j = 1, \dots, n-1$ (where $s_j = 1$ if $\mu_j \leq \mu \leq \mu_{j+1}$ and $s_j = 0$ otherwise) and the constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 &\leq s_1, \\ \lambda_i &\leq s_{j-1} + s_j, \quad j = 1, \dots, n-1, \\ \lambda_n &\leq s_{n-1}, \\ \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} s_j &= 1, \\ s &\in [0, 1]. \end{aligned}$$

This set of variables and constraints represents a special ordered set of type 2 (SOS 2), and this representation is called the λ -form approximation [10]. In many modern MILP solvers, it is possible to declare special ordered sets explicitly.

Using these definitions, we introduce now the grid points $\hat{\alpha}_{itj}$ for $i \in V', t \in T$ and $j = 1, \dots, n_\alpha$, where $\hat{\alpha}_{i,1} = 0$ and $\hat{\alpha}_{it, n_\alpha} = \frac{1}{2}(p_{max} + Q)$. Hence, the term α_{it}^2 could be replaced for each $i \in V', t \in T$ by its linear approximation

$$\alpha_{it}^2 = \sum_{j=1}^{n_\alpha} \lambda_{itj}^\alpha \hat{\alpha}_{itj}^2, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\alpha_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_\alpha} \lambda_{itj}^\alpha \hat{\alpha}_{itj}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_\alpha} \lambda_{itj}^\alpha = 1, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$\lambda_{itj}^\alpha \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, n_\alpha, i \in V', t \in T. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Similarly, we can derive a linear representation of β_{it}^2 using the grid points $\hat{\beta}_{itj}$ for $i \in V', t \in T$, and $j = 1, \dots, n_\beta$, where $\hat{\beta}_{i,1} = 0$ and $\hat{\beta}_{it, n_\beta} = \frac{1}{2}(p_{max} - Q)$. Hence, the corresponding linear approximation is described by

$$\beta_{it}^2 = \sum_{j=1}^{n_\beta} \lambda_{itj}^\beta \hat{\beta}_{itj}^2, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\beta_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_\beta} \lambda_{itj}^\beta \hat{\beta}_{itj}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.17})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_\beta} \lambda_{itj}^\beta = 1, \quad i \in V', t \in T \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$\lambda_{itj}^\beta \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, n_\beta, i \in V', t \in T. \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Bazaraa, Sherali, and Shetty [10] maintain that the SOS constraints become redundant when minimizing a strictly convex function. Hence, the ones associated with the β -variables can be omitted, since we are maximizing the negation of a convex function ($\sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} (-\beta_{it}^2)$). Finally, by using the foregoing definitions, the IRP under monopoly can be restated in an equivalent compact linear form as follows.

$$\max \sum_{j=1}^{n_\alpha} \lambda_{itj}^\alpha \hat{\alpha}_{itj}^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{n_\beta} \lambda_{itj}^\beta \hat{\beta}_{itj}^2 - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T} c_k y_{kt} - \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{t \in T} h_i I_{it} - \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} b_i (g(p_i) - w_{it}) - \sum_{t \in T} f(r_{0,t}) r_{0,t} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

subject to

$$(2.1.2) - (2.1.5), \quad (2.1.7) - (2.1.10), \quad (2.2.2), \quad (2.2) - (2.5),$$

$$\alpha_{it} = \frac{1}{2}(p_i + w_{it}), \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$\beta_{it} = \frac{1}{2}(p_i - w_{it}), \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.22})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_\alpha} \lambda_{itj}^\alpha \hat{\alpha}_{itj} = \alpha_{it}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.23})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_\beta} \lambda_{itj}^\beta \hat{\beta}_{itj} = \beta_{it}, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.24})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_\alpha} \lambda_{itj}^\alpha = 1, \quad i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_\beta} \lambda_{itj}^\beta = 1, \quad i \in V', t \in T \quad (\text{A.26})$$

$$\lambda_{itj}^\alpha \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, n_\alpha, i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.27})$$

$$\lambda_{itj}^\beta \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, n_\beta, i \in V', t \in T, \quad (\text{A.28})$$

$$\text{At most, two adjacent } \lambda^\alpha \text{ are nonzero.} \quad (\text{A.29})$$

Appendix 2.B Linearization process of IRP model with variable production costs.

To enhance the solvability of the IRP model with variable production costs, we propose to apply a λ -form piecewise linear approximation to derive an equivalent linear model representation of this problem. Toward this end, first consider the objective function (3.1) which include the non linear term:

$$\sum_{t \in T} u'_1 R_{0,t}^2 + u'_2 R_{0,t} + u'_3.$$

Following Bazaraa, Sherali, and Shetty [10], we first consider the interval of interest $[0, r_{max}]$. We next define the grid points \hat{R}_{jt} for $j = 1, \dots, n, t \in T$, where $\hat{R}_{1t} = 0$ and $\hat{R}_{nt} = r_{max}$. Accordingly, the functions for which $R_{0,t}$ is an argument could be replaced by their linear approximations:

$$R_{0,t}^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{jt} \hat{R}_{jt}^2, \quad j = 1, \dots, n, t \in T, \quad (\text{B.30})$$

$$R_{0,t} = \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{jt} \hat{R}_{jt}, \quad j = 1, \dots, n, t \in T, \quad (\text{B.31})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{jt} = 1, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{B.32})$$

$$\lambda_{jt} \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, n, t \in T. \quad (\text{B.33})$$

This yields the following equivalent reformulation of the IRP problem with variable production costs:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T} p_0 c_{ikt} - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T} c_k y_{kt} - \sum_{i \in V} \sum_{t \in T} h_i I_{it} - \sum_{i \in V'} \sum_{t \in T} b_i (r_{it} - w_{it}) \\ & - \sum_{j=1}^n (u'_1 \lambda_{jt} \hat{R}_{jt}^2 + u'_2 \lambda_{jt} \hat{R}_{jt} + u'_3) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.34})$$

subject to

$$(2.1.2) - (2.1.6), \quad (2.1.8), \quad (2.2.2) - (2.2.3), \quad (2.4.2) - (2.4.6),$$

$$R_{0,t} = \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{jt} \hat{R}_{jt}, \quad j = 1, \dots, n, t \in T, \quad (\text{B.35})$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_{jt} = 1, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{B.36})$$

$$\lambda_{jt} \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, n, t \in T. \quad (\text{B.37})$$

The SOS 2 variables and constraints are deliberately omitted from this formulation since the adjacency restriction inherently holds (see Bazaraa, Sherali, and Shetty [10]).

Appendix 2.C Summary of computational results.

In Tables 2.6-2.8, we summarize the results obtained for the cost minimization model, where columns 1-2 give the parameters of the test. In particular, the first column displays the selected time horizon, and the second column shows the allowed length of vehicle routes. Columns 3-9 show the results. More specifically, column 3 provides the CPU time in seconds. Column 4 gives the average gap, $\sum_{\Delta t=1}^S \frac{Z^D - Z}{Z^D}$, where Z refers to the cost of the incumbent solution at each simulation instant Δt , and Z^D is the dual bound found within the time limit. Column 5 shows the total incurred costs TC , and column 9 the total profits TP . Finally, columns 6-8 provides a summary of transportation and inventory holding costs. We denote by VC , IHS , and IHC the transportation costs, the inventory holding costs at the supplier, and the inventory holding costs at customers.

Table 2.6: Summary of cost minimization results for 24 tests with $n = 5$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	TP
2	1	2.5	0.0	49,612	30,107	6,750	526	97,964
2	2	2.9	0.0	47,409	28,013	6,080	1,087	100,167
2	3	3.7	0.0	55,621	36,317	5,554	1,521	91,955
2	4	5.7	0.0	47,644	28,210	5,964	1,241	99,932
2	5	9.6	0.0	43,608	24,186	5,627	1,566	103,968
2	6	12.7	0.0	40,653	21,205	5,969	1,250	106,923
2	7	17.3	0.0	40,925	21,476	5,717	1,504	106,651
2	8	34.2	0.0	41,279	21,845	5,883	1,323	106,297
3	1	2.3	0.0	49,667	30,138	6,853	447	97,909
3	2	3.2	0.0	47,283	27,903	5,957	1,195	100,293
3	3	6.8	0.0	46,326	26,951	5,546	1,600	101,250
3	4	9.2	0.0	42,808	23,388	5,889	1,302	104,768
3	5	14.0	0.0	43,395	23,992	5,609	1,566	104,181
3	6	28.9	0.0	42,724	23,298	5,854	1,343	104,852
3	7	39.4	0.0	41,157	21,723	5,629	1,576	106,419
3	8	76.5	0.0	41,864	22,441	5,888	1,613	105,712
4	1	2.9	0.0	49,730	30,191	6,894	416	97,846
4	2	4.1	0.0	52,081	32,678	5,657	1,518	95,495
4	3	7.3	0.0	44,486	25,089	5,614	1,554	103,090
4	4	11.2	0.0	43,375	23,957	5,879	1,311	104,201
4	5	19.0	0.0	42,974	23,535	5,825	1,386	104,602
4	6	31.4	0.0	42,130	22,711	5,846	1,344	105,446
4	7	48.5	0.0	41,182	21,744	5,637	1,571	106,394
4	8	78.4	0.0	41,016	21,578	5,961	1,249	106,560

Table 2.7: Summary of cost minimization results for 24 tests with $n = 10$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	TP
2	1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	2	5.9	0.00	126,226	59,074	19,037	3,876	191,246
2	3	9.0	0.00	129,633	61,932	17,123	6,340	187,839
2	4	11.9	0.00	119,465	52,463	19,260	3,504	198,007
2	5	18.4	0.00	115,893	48,674	18,778	4,203	201,579
2	6	33.5	0.00	113,421	46,099	18,397	4,688	204,051
2	7	87.6	0.00	114,718	47,447	18,432	4,601	202,754
2	8	129.4	0.00	114,341	47,084	18,676	4,342	203,131
3	1	6.1	0.00	126,570	59,925	20,951	1,455	190,902
3	2	14.3	0.00	119,131	52,220	19,093	3,580	198,341
3	3	40.9	0.00	115,009	47,540	17,638	5,593	202,463
3	4	182.5	0.00	113,777	46,529	18,518	4,492	203,695
3	5	519.8	0.00	111,927	44,555	18,394	4,739	205,545
3	6	3,511.1	0.00	110,360	43,037	18,596	4,488	207,112
3	7	9,639.7	0.00	110,379	43,074	18,563	4,504	207,093
3	8	22,920.6	0.03	109,950	42,672	18,692	4,348	207,522
4	1	14.7	0.00	123,372	56,716	20,955	1,463	194,100
4	2	74.1	0.00	122,724	55,995	18,018	4,473	194,748
4	3	218.3	0.00	113,696	46,210	18,016	5,232	203,776
4	4	1,374.6	0.00	112,490	45,224	18,483	4,545	204,982
4	5	12,806.0	0.00	111,217	43,868	18,427	4,683	206,255
4	6	34,445.3	0.17	110,892	43,641	18,453	4,559	206,580
4	7	46,185.8	0.34	110,938	43,649	18,580	4,471	206,534
4	8	50,676.8	0.51	109,360	42,056	18,615	5,036	208,112

* This setting led to infeasible IRP instances.

Table 2.8: Summary of cost minimization results for 24 tests with $n = 15$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	TP
2	1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	2	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	3	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	4	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	5	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	6	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	7	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
2	8	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
3	1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
3	2	67.3	0.00	137,539	53,606	27,404	1,492	337,565
3	3	139.6	0.00	138,602	50,120	22,885	5,713	336,502
3	4	533.0	0.00	143,205	54,529	24,307	4,486	331,899
3	5	1,089.6	0.00	140,446	51,768	24,038	4,755	334,658
3	6	1,940.1	0.00	136,114	47,574	23,183	5,473	338,990
3	7	2,004.4	0.00	135,264	46,658	23,723	4,999	339,840
3	8	3,986.0	0.00	136,114	47,451	23,368	5,412	338,990
4	1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
4	2	238.9	0.00	142,561	39,311	27,202	1,337	332,543
4	3	566.5	0.00	13,316	46,129	22,686	6,003	340,586
4	4	5,370.9	0.00	13,316	45,387	23,703	4,953	341,178
4	5	12,277.6	0.01	132,856	44,226	23,540	5,206	342,248
4	6	23,589.0	0.11	129,946	41,375	23,419	5,268	345,158
4	7	40,719.8	0.20	131,142	42,537	23,507	5,214	343,962
4	8	51,496.8	0.55	131,136	42,676	22,920	5,656	343,968

* This setting led to infeasible IRP instances.

2. Long-term effects of short planning horizons for inventory routing problems

Tables 2.9-2.11 display the numerical results of the simulation study conducted for the case of profit maximization with lost sales. Columns 1-2 give the parameters of the test, and columns 3-10 show the results. An additional column is included to accommodate the cost of lost sales.

Table 2.9: Summary of profit maximization with lost sales results for 24 tests with $n = 5$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	2.6	0.0	50,129	21,901	7,377	1,185	1,528	96,461
2	2	3.9	0.0	45,097	25,694	6,113	1,062	0	102,479
2	3	8.0	0.0	50,924	31,613	5,460	1,622	0	96,652
2	4	21.5	0.0	48,507	29,074	5,942	1,262	0	99,069
2	5	37.6	0.0	43,463	23,901	5,762	1,489	82	103,705
2	6	59.5	0.0	41,131	21,693	5,926	1,283	0	106,445
2	7	140.1	0.0	41,078	21,646	5,662	1,541	0	106,498
2	8	438.6	0.0	40,815	21,362	5,962	1,262	0	106,761
3	1	2.5	0.0	48,898	29,175	6,955	446	94	98,210
3	2	6.7	0.0	47,242	27,857	5,979	1,178	0	100,334
3	3	21.3	0.0	44,076	24,470	5,791	1,459	128	102,862
3	4	47.7	0.0	42,936	23,498	5,929	1,274	7	104,604
3	5	163.8	0.0	42,503	22,944	5,758	1,468	104	104,553
3	6	215.4	0.0	42,724	23,298	5,854	1,343	0	104,852
3	7	387.9	0.0	40,982	21,539	5,648	1,566	0	106,594
3	8	1,132.1	0.0	41,850	22,428	5,923	1,271	0	105,726
4	1	4.8	0.0	50,720	30,841	7,114	360	177	95,971
4	2	7.8	0.0	52,081	32,678	12,229	1,518	0	95,495
4	3	28.9	0.0	44,492	24,746	5,747	1,546	225	101,961
4	4	66.3	0.0	41,802	22,375	5,752	1,446	0	105,774
4	5	168.9	0.0	43,211	23,544	5,982	1,334	122	103,753
4	6	408.7	0.0	41,306	21,883	5,867	1,328	0	106,270
4	7	502.4	0.0	41,294	21,831	5,617	1,603	14	106,211
4	8	1,352.7	0.0	41,001	21,556	5,937	1,279	0	106,575

Table 2.10: Summary of profit maximization with lost sales results for 24 tests with $n = 10$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	3.5	0.00	125,774	54,632	22,502	3,174	1,228	185,561
2	2	4.4	0.00	126,226	59,074	19,037	3,876	0	191,246
2	3	10.1	0.00	119,118	51,663	18,042	5,175	0	198,354
2	4	23.5	0.00	120,925	53,865	19,332	3,473	17	196,463
2	5	41.5	0.00	115,429	48,149	18,686	4,342	14	201,975
2	6	62.6	0.00	112,754	45,365	18,358	4,793	0	204,718
2	7	115.0	0.00	116,020	48,682	18,689	4,374	37	201,265
2	8	161.2	0.00	113,407	46,049	18,697	4,409	13	204,001
3	1	5.5	0.00	126,506	59,752	21,034	1,450	32	190,807
3	2	16.8	0.00	118,782	51,874	18,721	3,949	0	198,690
3	3	67.3	0.00	115,582	47,983	18,020	5,282	58	201,599
3	4	260.8	0.00	112,090	44,729	18,375	4,745	2	205,372
3	5	779.7	0.00	110,825	43,443	18,440	4,695	9	206,603
3	6	3,247.8	0.00	110,914	43,083	18,798	4,209	5	207,111
3	7	12,399.8	0.01	110,727	43,328	18,450	4,688	23	206,631
3	8	32,858.9	0.07	110,693	43,439	18,691	4,325	0	206,779
4	1	12.6	0.00	120,973	53,982	21,260	1,403	90	196,050
4	2	97.8	0.00	119,669	52,851	18,031	4,548	0	197,803
4	3	380.1	0.00	114,928	47,288	17,564	5,811	27	202,411
4	4	2,741.2	0.00	112,868	45,605	18,603	4,418	4	204,584
4	5	13,578.3	0.00	110,679	43,329	18,644	4,467	0	206,793
4	6	35,790.7	0.10	110,325	43,069	18,647	4,370	0	207,147
4	7	46,276.0	0.19	110,862	43,483	18,497	4,633	11	206,554
4	8	53,698.9	0.30	110,337	43,090	18,630	4,379	0	207,135

Table 2.11: Summary of profit maximization with lost sales results for 24 tests with $n = 15$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	6.5	0.00	186,781	43,869	56,756	1,996	24,277	166,940
2	2	7.7	0.00	155,526	49,250	34,974	3,797	7,621	281,473
2	3	15.3	0.00	143,099	49,528	25,915	5,013	2,758	318,214
2	4	17.0	0.00	141,294	48,917	25,117	5,069	2,307	322,274
2	5	54.3	0.00	141,986	49,630	25,112	4,540	2,307	321,582
2	6	71.3	0.00	140,262	47,905	25,112	5,053	2,307	323,306
2	7	136.5	0.00	140,330	47,952	25,117	5,069	2,307	323,238
2	8	179.4	0.00	140,309	47,952	25,112	5,053	2,307	323,259
3	1	12.5	0.00	148,126	54,587	28,891	2,846	1,918	317,387
3	2	31.2	0.00	137,892	49,346	23,495	5,167	0	337,212
3	3	142.7	0.00	138,602	50,120	22,885	5,713	0	336,502
3	4	362.6	0.00	141,142	52,357	24,381	4,473	47	333,728
3	5	538.1	0.00	137,871	49,164	23,990	4,024	37	337,048
3	6	1,489.8	0.00	136,114	47,574	23,183	5,473	0	338,990
3	7	2,497.8	0.00	135,434	46,830	23,628	5,091	0	339,670
3	8	5,880.9	0.00	134,324	45,564	23,968	4,904	4	340,760
4	1	66.6	0.00	144,019	55,391	26,489	2,099	156	330,303
4	2	215.7	0.00	142,561	54,215	22,911	5,551	0	332,543
4	3	2,462.9	0.00	134,518	45,967	22,706	5,960	0	340,586
4	4	6,038.6	0.01	133,341	44,744	23,669	5,021	22	341,653
4	5	9,116.8	0.01	132,061	43,309	23,521	5,304	43	342,829
4	6	16,284.0	0.01	130,115	41,583	23,344	5,304	0	344,989
4	7	40,832.3	0.17	130,512	41,982	23,506	5,138	2	344,584
4	8	43,013.2	0.14	130,090	41,522	23,553	5,130	0	345,014

2. Long-term effects of short planning horizons for inventory routing problems

We provide in Tables 2.12-2.14 the numerical results of the simulation study conducted for the case of a price-setting company. They report the parameters of the test case, the cost metrics, and the recorded profit. Column 9 displays the cost of lost sales.

Table 2.12: Summary of profit maximization under monopoly results for 24 tests with $n = 5$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	3.7	0.00	55,295	40,840	2,171	55	0	116,253
2	2	7.4	0.00	52,771	33,317	3,437	793	833	118,051
2	3	14.4	0.00	52,740	36,792	1,697	607	224	118,326
2	4	30.4	0.00	50,064	37,395	2,201	826	56	119,793
2	5	103.1	0.00	49,783	35,039	1,389	983	142	120,073
2	6	309.9	0.00	48,301	33,109	1,663	972	328	121,397
2	7	3,690.9	0.00	49,476	34,332	1,658	979	279	120,386
2	8	13,333.4	0.03	47,990	32,650	1,738	1,047	327	121,778
3	1	4.2	0.00	54,318	40,914	2,151	59	0	117,513
3	2	10.3	0.00	52,987	36,954	2,265	669	310	118,169
3	3	37.6	0.00	52,324	38,501	1,744	601	188	118,564
3	4	147.9	0.00	49,529	36,228	1,886	607	348	119,983
3	5	880.7	0.00	49,118	37,344	1,741	826	144	120,031
3	6	3,355.6	0.00	48,392	33,223	1,648	1,010	283	120,944
3	7	27,166.4	0.10	48,999	33,796	1,565	1,132	277	120,569
3	8	52,479.8	0.70	49,245	33,988	1,669	1,157	202	120,527
4	1	4.4	0.00	54,579	39,724	2,243	44	0	117,591
4	2	14.3	0.00	52,636	36,718	2,166	508	345	118,514
4	3	55.2	0.00	52,763	36,838	1,932	620	343	118,319
4	4	203.9	0.00	49,637	36,655	1,880	767	104	120,278
4	5	1,727.7	0.0	49,637	36,655	1,880	767	104	120,278
4	6	8570.4	0.1	49,624	34,821	1,447	929	198	120,064
4	7	41,264.8	0.23	48,999	33,796	1,565	1,132	277	120,569
4	8	54,281.1	0.99	49,145	33,913	1,721	1,069	213	120,695

Table 2.13: Summary of profit maximization under monopoly results for 24 tests with $n = 10$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	14.3	0.00	147,618	58,267	42,545	1,844	723	177,988
2	2	31.0	0.00	149,058	56,774	43,944	4,084	18	201,389
2	3	65.5	0.00	138,774	49,416	39,738	5,368	14	218,324
2	4	530.7	0.00	132,263	40,499	41,543	5,910	72	223,513
2	5	1,458.4	0.00	135,312	40,176	45,668	5,203	27	215,427
2	6	7,133.9	0.00	132,125	37,337	45,115	5,400	35	219,203
2	7	34,862.1	0.47	134,895	39,581	45,115	5,931	29	214,861
2	8	54,292.3	0.62	132,193	37,248	44,771	5,787	149	215,073
3	1	29.5	0.00	140,241	57,672	36,474	1,857	0	219,086
3	2	108.0	0.00	133,039	40,992	44,014	3,787	8	217,522
3	3	440.6	0.00	130,524	40,551	40,200	5,514	20	224,531
3	4	12,415.3	0.00	128,642	36,359	44,238	5,967	25	225,698
3	5	47,675.7	0.56	129,296	34,200	45,311	5,537	9	221,555
3	6	54,197.4	1.06	128,472	33,757	44,648	5,812	17	222,952
3	7	54,327.1	1.33	128,864	33,371	45,497	5,722	36	220,531
3	8	54,139.7	1.33	128,248	33,671	44,693	5,611	35	222,668
4	1	75.9	0.00	136,926	54,682	36,120	1,887	0	222,682
4	2	336.2	0.00	131,415	39,549	43,932	3,690	6	221,552
4	3	14,528.1	0.00	128,464	38,108	41,684	4,430	3	227,858
4	4	49,884.4	0.82	127,536	34,673	43,742	4,875	8	226,512
4	5	54,333.8	1.20	128,000	33,532	45,119	5,108	3	223,428
4	6	54,142.6	1.41	128,088	33,997	44,133	5,716	3	223,674
4	7	57,477.2	1.43	128,196	34,223	44,936	5,569	25	221,769
4	8	54,118.7	1.63	129,367	34,289	44,909	5,805	126	220,610

We provide in Tables 2.15-2.17 the cost metrics pertaining to the profit maximization problem with variable production costs. In addition to the aforementioned cost metrics, we define PC , as displayed in column 9, a metric that maps the total production costs.

2. Long-term effects of short planning horizons for inventory routing problems

Table 2.14: Summary of profit maximization under monopoly results for 24 tests with $n = 15$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	33.2	0.0	188,022	37,487	81,416	1,178	8,055	128,277
2	2	153.8	0.0	174,115	46,369	58,585	3,923	5,355	300,531
2	3	13,018.8	0.1	175,728	32,996	67,646	5,313	9,889	252,798
2	4	40,772.0	2.1	168,627	30,922	65,819	6,480	5,521	270,476
2	5	54,223.6	7.8	169,110	32,229	65,102	6,548	5,347	272,752
2	6	54,191.2	9.3	169,289	33,001	64,950	6,435	5,019	271,178
2	7	54,274.4	10.1	170,284	32,573	65,715	6,299	5,813	262,675
2	8	54,242.3	10.1	169,512	31,003	66,292	6,391	5,943	258,550
3	1	98.9	0.0	174,198	57,482	52,088	1,930	2,814	296,325
3	2	6,684.3	0.0	158,989	58,323	35,762	4,213	808	390,277
3	3	53,780.5	1.4	158,739	58,885	34,121	5,707	142	394,275
3	4	54,134.8	5.7	161,644	43,208	49,193	6,211	3,148	346,081
3	5	54,136.2	10.0	168,166	46,362	51,034	6,325	4,560	331,980
3	6	54,070.9	16.1	168,777	44,471	53,027	6,096	5,300	320,894
3	7	54,096.2	23.8	172,265	45,116	54,861	6,397	6,008	306,529
3	8	54,066.6	29.9	176,391	46,383	57,751	6,524	5,849	295,317
4	1	615.7	0.0	164,199	64,804	36,993	2,511	6	387,450
4	2	36,141.0	0.1	153,808	54,436	34,182	4,524	782	398,053
4	3	54,066.0	1.7	152,866	53,969	59,884	5,486	536	401,086
4	4	54,097.9	8.7	156,268	52,198	37,858	5,748	581	388,097
4	5	54,102.8	23.3	161,685	49,835	43,117	5,231	3,618	359,814
4	6	54,086.0	39.0	165,347	52,230	43,674	5,996	3,563	355,429
4	7	54,100.0	52.5	165,984	49,226	45,841	5,952	5,081	339,137
4	8	54,098.4	61.8	174,342	49,872	6,311	52,203	6,071	311,579

Table 2.15: Summary of profit maximization with variable production costs results for 24 tests with $n = 5$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	PC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	1.9	0.0	49,599	38,607	361	55	10,458	118	97,385
2	2	2.3	0.0	36,460	24,751	286	350	9,963	1,110	105,567
2	3	4.0	0.0	36,352	25,056	247	461	10,589	0	111,224
2	4	5.0	0.0	35,480	23,958	256	633	10,633	0	112,096
2	5	8.1	0.0	35,336	23,627	357	682	10,614	56	111,960
2	6	12.4	0.0	34,339	22,729	342	634	10,634	0	113,237
2	7	25.3	0.0	34,161	22,049	310	897	10,645	261	112,112
2	8	46.8	0.0	33,812	22,045	319	748	10,639	61	113,457
3	1	2.3	0.0	47,178	36,248	364	8	10,468	90	99,949
3	2	3.8	0.0	36,216	24,605	248	378	9,970	1,014	106,291
3	3	7.5	0.0	38,575	27,248	226	515	10,574	12	108,944
3	4	8.5	0.0	34,970	23,426	381	527	10,636	0	112,606
3	5	17.9	0.0	36,011	24,429	298	649	10,631	4	111,546
3	6	34.6	0.0	34,737	23,136	275	686	10,627	13	112,773
3	7	87.6	0.0	34,354	22,531	311	862	10,624	24	113,100
3	8	143.4	0.0	33,338	21,462	360	812	10,705	0	114,238
4	1	2.4	0.0	47,218	36,248	364	48	10,468	90	99,909
4	2	3.3	0.0	35,992	24,605	423	248	10,393	323	109,971
4	3	7.0	0.0	36,116	24,795	223	511	10,576	12	111,403
4	4	10.4	0.0	35,016	23,442	284	657	10,633	0	112,560
4	5	19.4	0.0	35,216	23,599	336	648	10,630	4	112,338
4	6	47.0	0.0	33,846	22,244	692	279	10,632	0	113,730
4	7	99.1	0.0	34,049	22,253	805	321	10,615	55	113,252
4	8	241.7	0.0	34,442	22,565	848	324	10,705	0	113,134

Table 2.16: Summary of profit maximization with variable production costs results for 24 tests with $n = 10$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	PC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	2.7	0.00	97,110	56,672	923	242	21,235	18,038	130,173
2	2	9.0	0.00	98,215	56,114	761	2,498	38,645	198	218,269
2	3	17.0	0.00	93,050	49,698	753	3,594	38,743	261	223,118
2	4	60.4	0.00	93,568	49,524	1,456	3,384	39,102	102	223,395
2	5	133.5	0.00	92,103	48,399	1,045	3,677	38,880	103	224,855
2	6	288.3	0.00	90,225	46,224	1,054	3,765	39,142	40	227,049
2	7	333.7	0.00	91,002	46,911	1,071	3,814	39,129	77	226,085
2	8	385.7	0.00	89,042	44,443	1,013	4,260	39,312	15	228,354
3	1	6.7	0.00	113,594	72,214	929	210	37,437	2,804	189,860
3	2	24.8	0.00	95,304	54,409	749	1,680	37,893	572	219,308
3	3	199.0	0.00	90,623	47,250	898	3,492	38,920	63	226,533
3	4	714.6	0.00	90,169	46,314	1,184	3,705	38,956	10	227,252
3	5	10,740.2	0.00	88,413	45,364	970	3,133	38,909	36	228,877
3	6	16,857.0	0.01	86,513	42,894	865	3,756	38,955	44	230,740
3	7	38,100.4	0.17	87,775	43,964	1,069	3,727	38,979	36	229,516
3	8	49,979.8	0.32	86,881	43,211	949	3,645	39,038	38	230,399
4	1	18.3	0.00	106,627	67,130	954	192	38,315	35	210,668
4	2	193.0	0.00	99,453	57,313	654	2,609	38,828	50	217,770
4	3	1,522.6	0.00	91,483	49,266	749	2,598	38,856	14	225,919
4	4	17,521.8	0.00	89,440	47,317	926	2,407	38,726	63	227,718
4	5	51,758.7	0.4	88,303	45,996	946	2,560	38,800	2	229,158
4	6	52,504.0	0.58	87,612	45,097	972	2,741	38,786	17	229,774
4	7	54,032.6	0.81	87,443	44,722	956	2,934	38,809	21	229,922
4	8	54,055.7	0.90	86,828	43,652	950	3,386	38,823	18	230,555

Table 2.17: Summary of profit maximization with variable production costs results for 24 tests with $n = 15$.

L	H	CPU(s)	%Gap	TC	VC	IHSU	IHC	PC	Lost sales	TP
2	1	4.2	0.00	109,558	43,626	1,379	296	18,412	45,845	136,321
2	2	7.1	0.00	105,321	46,436	1,073	3,109	43,583	11,121	314,177
2	3	15.7	0.00	106,472	45,631	965	4,965	50,830	4,082	348,223
2	4	27.2	0.00	109,908	51,269	1,032	3,656	52,799	38	353,580
2	5	66.6	0.00	111,390	50,063	1,259	5,055	52,580	2,432	351,553
2	6	118.4	0.00	109,523	48,513	1,203	4,992	52,262	2,554	352,811
2	7	180.3	0.00	109,061	47,952	1,114	5,069	52,618	2,307	354,507
2	8	182.9	0.00	109,088	47,952	1,132	5,053	52,643	2,307	354,480
3	1	10.8	0.00	111,674	52,695	1,170	243	30,161	27,404	226,407
3	2	23.0	0.00	107,258	50,928	1,019	2,723	52,301	287	366,412
3	3	112.1	0.00	107,874	50,984	1,019	3,362	52,446	64	366,908
3	4	174.4	0.00	108,794	43,874	1,186	4,052	52,915	63	366,118
3	5	842.6	0.00	106,792	49,131	1,142	3,752	52,744	23	368,197
3	6	2,438.3	0.00	104,300	46,360	1,043	4,103	52,720	74	370,435
3	7	7,526.0	0.00	104,567	46,344	1,243	4,023	52,954	4	370,519
3	8	8,764.0	0.00	102,250	44,149	1,338	3,820	52,943	0	372,854
4	1	61.5	0.00	120,344	65,344	1,131	283	43,506	10,079	304,366
4	2	318.5	0.00	101,754	45,193	943	3,026	52,180	413	371,286
4	3	899.6	0.00	103,532	48,917	1,047	5,061	52,560	2,323	371,161
4	4	1,260.5	0.00	102,090	46,843	993	3,215	52,398	82	372,697
4	5	7,064.2	0.01	100,744	43,073	1,174	3,769	52,725	4	374,343
4	6	38,107.1	0.07	97,550	39,996	925	3,856	52,691	81	377,148
4	7	50,325.1	0.50	98,128	40,652	970	3,750	52,734	23	376,861
4	8	52,299.1	1.56	98,146	41,405	10	2,856	53,839	36	375,296

Chapter 3

New benchmark instances for the inventory routing problem

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Jørgen Skålnes Department of Industrial Economics and Technology Management, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Alfred Getz veg 3, 7491 Trondheim, Norway jorgen.skalnes@ntnu.no

Mohamed Ben Ahmed Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway mohamed.ben.ahmed@himolde.no

Lars Magnus Hvattum Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway Lars.M.Hvattum@himolde.no

Magnus Stålhane Department of Industrial Economics and Technology Management, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Alfred Getz veg 3, 7491 Trondheim, Norway magnus.staalhane@ntnu.no

Abstract

The existing sets of benchmark instances for the inventory routing problem (IRP) have been beneficial for investigating and illustrating the properties of the problem. However, they have some limitations. They possess certain properties that could lead to algorithms and models exploiting specific features of the instances not necessarily found in practice. In addition, the known primal and dual bounds on these original instances have been significantly improved, which could discourage the development of new solution methods for the IRP in the future. Therefore, we propose a new collection of 270 real-world-like instances ranging from 10 to 200 customers. These instances vary in terms of the size of the vehicle fleet, the type of vehicles in the homogeneous fleet, and the length of the planning horizon, as well as in the demand structure and the geographical distribution of customers. Transportation and inventory holding costs are modeled following assumptions that resemble cost calculations in practice. We perform an instance space analysis showing that the new instances nicely complement the original instances by covering a larger part of the instance space. To derive lower and upper bounds for each instance, we present computational experiments with two high-quality solution methods: a matheuristic and an exact branch-and-cut method. The results confirm that the new set of instances are intrinsically hard to solve, and they demonstrate the need for developing new solution methods.

Keywords: Distribution, Test instance, Branch-and-cut, Matheuristic, Vendor-managed inventory

3.1 Introduction

The inventory routing problem (IRP) was introduced by Bell et al. [9] and arises in the context of vendor-managed inventory. It has attracted an increasing amount of attention in the recent years. In the standard IRP, a single supplier, denoted 0, delivers a uniform product to a set of customers, \mathcal{N}^C , over a planning horizon divided into a set of discrete time periods \mathcal{T} . In each time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, the supplier produces S_t units of the product, while each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ consumes D_{it} units of the same product. Both the supplier and the customers, $i \in \mathcal{N} = \mathcal{N}^C \cup \{0\}$, have an initial inventory level I_i at the beginning of the planning horizon, a required minimum inventory level \underline{L}_i , and a maximum storage capacity \bar{L}_i . Inventory holding costs H_{it} are incurred for each unit of product at each node $i \in \mathcal{N}$ at the end of time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$. In a given period we assume that deliveries are made before the demands are consumed.

In order to serve the demands, the supplier has a homogeneous fleet of K vehicles, each with a capacity to hold Q units of the product. The problem of routing the vehicles to serve the customers can be defined

on a graph $G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$, where \mathcal{N} is the set of nodes and $\mathcal{A} = \{(i, j) \in \{\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}\} | i \neq j\}$ is the set of arcs connecting the nodes. A cost C_{ij} is incurred when traversing the arc (i, j) , and a customer can be visited at most once per time period. Thus, a route driven by a vehicle can be seen as a simple cycle in the graph starting and ending at the supplier. The objective of the IRP is to create at most one route per vehicle in each time period, minimizing the total transportation and inventory holding costs, while keeping the inventory at each node between its upper and lower limits, \bar{L}_i and \underline{L}_i , respectively. This implies that the decision-maker must simultaneously decide (1) when to visit a customer, (2) how much to deliver to a customer upon a visit, and (3) how to route the available vehicles serving the visited customers in each time period.

Archetti et al. [4] proposed a branch-and-cut (B&C) algorithm for the single-vehicle IRP, while also establishing what later has become the most popular set of benchmark instances for this problem. There are a total of 160 instances ranging from five to 50 customers, with three and six-time periods, respectively. Subsequently, Archetti et al. [3] released 60 additional instances, having a planning horizon of six-time periods and 50, 100, and 200 customers, respectively. Later, both sets of instances were adapted by Coelho, Cordeau, and Laporte [14] to the multi-vehicle IRP by dividing the original vehicle capacity by the number of vehicles considered and rounding to the nearest integer. The instances proposed by Archetti et al. [4] and Archetti et al. [3] are usually referred to as the small and large benchmark instances, respectively. Considering vehicle fleets ranging from one to five vehicles, this yields 798 small instances (two of the five-vehicle instances are infeasible) and 300 large instances.

The exact methods developed for the IRP can mainly be classified into branch-and-price algorithms [16] or branch-and-cut algorithms [1, 4, 7, 15, 22, 25]. In addition, considerable effort has been put into developing efficient heuristic algorithms. Archetti et al. [3] proposed a matheuristic for the single-vehicle IRP combining a tabu search with the solution of a mixed-integer linear program (MILP), which was later modified also to handle multiple vehicles [5], and improved the best-known solutions for 92% of the large multi-vehicle instances. Many of these solutions were further improved by Chitsaz, Cordeau, and Jans [13] who proposed a three-phase decomposition matheuristic. Despite being designed for the assembly routing problem, their algorithm was able to find new best-known solutions for 194 out of the 300 large IRP instances. Recently, Alvarez et al. [2] presented a matheuristic for the IRP with perishable products, combining an iterative local search metaheuristic with two mathematical programming components. This algorithm found high-quality solutions for the variant with perishable products, but it also improved the best-known solution for a few of the small instances on the standard IRP. Another matheuristic for the standard IRP was developed by Diniz, Martinelli, and Poggi [17], where they combined an iterative local search algorithm with a randomized variable neighborhood descent. Using this heuristic, they improved the best-known solutions for several of the small benchmark instances. Vadseth, Andersson, and Stålhane [33] further improved the solutions for 178 of the large benchmark instances by solving the problem with a novel iterative matheuristic. They used a column generation framework where they created an initial route pool by splitting a giant tour. Then they iteratively solved a master problem that combines routes into a feasible solution and a heuristic that identifies potentially improving routes. In addition to obtaining high-quality solutions, they solved the instances considerably faster than the other methods presented in the literature.

Both best-known lower and upper bounds have been considerably improved for all benchmark instances, driven by the rapid development of both exact methods and heuristics, thus highlighting how these instances have provided a solid ground for evaluating various solution methods. However, these benchmark instances possess specific characteristics that can be exploited by tailoring solution methods specifically for these instances. To avoid a research direction of over-fitting new solution methods, we propose a new set of real-world-like instances to complement the current benchmark instances. In doing so, we respond to calls from several practitioners advocating more diversity in IRP instances by allowing for different instance characteristics when it comes to the parameters governing the inventories [6], including time-varying demands [22, 30] and considering longer planning horizons [10]. Our endeavor also finds inspiration in several contributions in the literature that dealt with generating new benchmark instances for routing problems, such as the capacitated vehicle routing problem [32], the liner shipping problem [11], the tramp shipping problem [18], and the maritime inventory routing problem [24]. Kendall et al. [19] also advocate the importance of focusing on the instances themselves when proposing a new benchmark set, without distractions from descriptions of new solution methods. In this paper, we therefore focus on the properties of the new instances. We perform an instance space analysis by using the MATILDA¹ platform [26, 27, 28] demonstrating how the two sets of instances complement each other, in addition to analysing the solutions of instances across the two sets.

¹<https://matilda.unimelb.edu.au/matilda/>

The new instances have non-stationary demands, i.e., a customer does not necessarily have the same demand in every time period of the planning horizon, which we believe corresponds better to customers' demands in practice. We also scale the vehicle fleet based on real-life vehicles such that the routes typically become shorter than in the current benchmark instances. In the new instances, the inventory capacity of the customers has a higher variance, potentially resulting in greater differences in the minimum visiting frequency between each pair of customers. Furthermore, we propose instances where the node locations have different structures. In some instances, the nodes are positioned randomly (R), in others, they are positioned in clusters (C), and finally, some are positioned as a mix between the two prior location structures (RC). This describes different realistic situations where the supplier serves customers scattered across a large city or in the countryside (R) or where the supplier serves several smaller towns or neighborhoods (C) represented by clusters. With the mixed node locations (RC), we allow for a combination of the two prior settings. We additionally incorporate an assumption of economies of scale for the inventories, thus resulting in the supplier having the lowest inventory cost. Hence, the inventory cost at a customer represents the marginal cost increase of storing a product unit at the customer rather than at the supplier. We aim to use realistic values for inventory and transportation costs, thus correctly reflecting their relative importance when solving the IRP. Finally, we apply a rounding of the distances between each pair of nodes such that the triangular inequality is fulfilled.

In Section 3.2 we present the new set of instances and how they are generated. Section 3.3 presents a model formulation for the problem. Then, in Section 3.4 we give a brief description of the B&C method, and the matheuristic used to obtain lower and upper bounds on the new instances, respectively. Finally, we present the instance space analysis and the lower and upper bounds obtained by these methods in Section 3.5, before the concluding remarks are presented in Section 3.6.

3.2 Instance generation

In this section, we describe how the new benchmark instances are generated. Section 3.2.1 presents the demand generation procedure and Section 3.2.2 presents how the node locations are generated. Section 3.2.3 presents how the initial inventory levels and inventory capacities are selected, before Section 3.2.4 presents how the vehicle fleet is generated. Finally, we give an overview of the main characteristics of the proposed instances.

3.2.1 Demand generation

Like previous research, we assume that customers allow at most one visit in each time period. Therefore we scale the average demand at each customer so that total demand over the planning horizon can always be satisfied by a maximum of one visit per time period. To reflect the demand patterns seen in practice, where the demand typically varies from time period to time period, and where it is positively correlated between customers operating within the same sector, we draw random deviations from a constructed demand trajectory for each customer. Such a demand trajectory can capture various demand patterns, e.g., the one seen by grocery stores where the demand is typically high at the beginning of the week, decreasing in the middle of the week, before increasing towards the weekend. To capture this volatile behavior often seen in practice we build the demand trajectory, \bar{D}_{it} for customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ and time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, using a sine function. With the sine function we can for each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ set the frequency between each peak demand with a frequency coefficient θ_i . For each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$, we also define a shift coefficient ϕ_i to define where on the trajectory we are in the first period, e.g. rising or decreasing demand. Furthermore, for each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$, we define the relative magnitude of the peak demands with a coefficient B_i , and we define the average demand, K_i , by adding a constant term to the sine function. The demand trajectory \bar{D}_{it} for customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ and time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$ can then be expressed as follows:

$$\bar{D}_{it} = B_i K_i \sin(\theta_i t + \phi_i) + K_i, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (3.1)$$

All of the above coefficients are drawn from uniform distributions. An illustration of the demand trajectory for a customer can be seen in Figure 3.1, where the solid middle line represents a customer's demand trajectory. Finally, the demand D_{it} for customer i in time period t , seen as squared boxes in the figure, is drawn from a uniform distribution with the mean \bar{D}_{it} and a relative symmetric support in the interval $a = [0, 1]$. For instance, if $\bar{D}_{it} = 10$ and $a = 0.2$, the demand D_{it} is drawn from a uniform

Figure 3.1: Illustration of a customer demand distribution.

distribution with the lower support being 8 and the upper support being 12, rounded to the nearest integer. The lower and upper support are represented with stapled lines in the figure.

For the depot, we assume a constant production rate, $S_t = P$, in each time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, and it is set to be equal to the total demand divided by the number of time periods, rounded up to the nearest integer:

$$P = \left\lceil \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^c} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} D_{it}}{|\mathcal{T}|} \right\rceil. \quad (3.2)$$

3.2.2 Node location

The nodes are located on a 2D map defined over a 500×500 grid. To represent geographical distributions of customers, we generate three classes of instances following the random (R), clustered (C), and random-clustered (RC) positioning, similar to those of Solomon [29] for the vehicle routing problem with time windows. The random location method randomly draws the nodes' coordinates from a uniform distribution. The clustered location method randomly draws the cluster's center from a uniform distribution. Then the customer coordinates are determined by drawing an angle and a radius from the cluster center. The angle is drawn from a uniform distribution before the radius r is drawn from an exponentially decaying distribution:

$$p(x | \lambda) = \lambda e^{-\lambda r}$$

A high value of λ results in a dense cluster where most of the nodes are located close to the cluster's center. The nodes become more dispersed with a lower value of λ . By testing different values we found $\lambda = 50$ to be a reasonable value to better reflect the appearance of a city or town. The random-clustered location method combines the latter two, where 50% of the customers are located with the random method, and the remaining customers are located with the clustering method. The node positions for one of the 50-customer instances are shown in Figure 3.2 for the three location methods: random, clustered, and random-clustered. The depot is represented by a dark square, while the customers are represented by small circular nodes with corresponding node IDs.

Meulen et al. [23] reported an average freight rate of 1.52 euros/km on road transport of containers for a 'truck+trailer' type of vehicle. Ti&Upply [31] reported a similar average in the second quarter of 2020, 1.58 euros/km, but also reported the range on a selected benchmark of direct routes, namely from 0.80 euros/km to 3.16 euros/km. The freight rates involve a profit margin, so the actual variable cost faced by a transportation company is expected to be lower than this. Therefore, for simplicity, we use a cost

Figure 3.2: An example of random, clustered, and random-clustered node positioning.

of 1 euro/km. In addition, we propose two different versions of the cost matrix depending on whether the 2D-grid represents an urban area, C_{ij}^{urban} , or a rural area, C_{ij}^{rural} . We let one unit of distance in the 2D-grid represent 0.1 km for the urban area and 0.5 km for the rural area. This impacts the ratio between the transportation cost and the inventory holding cost, which is expected to be the largest for the latter case. Both cost matrices are based on a distance matrix, E_{ij} , which represents the Euclidean distance between each pair of nodes (i, j) .

$$E_{ij} = \sqrt{(y_j - y_i)^2 + (x_j - x_i)^2}, \quad i, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (3.3)$$

$$C_{ij}^{\text{urban}} = \lfloor 0.1E_{ij} + 1 \rfloor, \quad i, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (3.4)$$

$$C_{ij}^{\text{rural}} = \lfloor 0.5E_{ij} + 1 \rfloor, \quad i, j \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (3.5)$$

Adding one to the term involving an element of the distance matrix and rounding down to the nearest integer ensures that the triangular inequality is satisfied.

3.2.3 Inventory

In practice, the inventory capacity varies from customer to customer. Some customers practice a just-in-time inventory policy where they have the smallest possible inventory capacity, while others want to be less dependent on frequent deliveries and have large inventory capacities. Therefore, we determine the inventory capacity by selecting a minimum visiting frequency, F , in the interval $[1, |T|]$ for each customer i . This visiting frequency is drawn randomly from a continuous uniform distribution. The inventory capacity I_i is then calculated as:

$$I_i = \left\lceil \max\left\{ \max_{t \in T} \{D_{it}\}, \sum_{t \in T} D_{it}/F \right\} \right\rceil, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C. \quad (3.6)$$

In case when the visiting frequency of a customer is equal to one, we set its inventory capacity equal to its total demand over the planning horizon. Conversely, if the visiting frequency is equal to $|T|$, the inventory capacity is set equal to the maximum demand incurred over the planning horizon. We ensure that it is always possible to satisfy customer demands without exceeding the inventory capacity.

Similarly as for the customers, the inventory capacity also varies from supplier to supplier. Some aim to ship out their products directly from production just having a bare minimum of inventory, while others keep large inventories to easier handle peaks in demand. Therefore, we draw the inventory capacity at the depot from a uniform distribution with the following support $\left[\max\{S_t, \max_{t \in T} \{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} D_{it}\}\}, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} \sum_{t \in T} D_{it} \right]$.

The initial inventory represents the remaining inventory from the last time period of the previous planning period. Therefore, we assume that the initial inventory at each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ lies in the interval $[0, \min\{D_{i1} + D_{i2}, \bar{I}_i\}]$. We use the demand of the first two periods as an upper limit to not make the first part of the planning horizon trivial to solve. The initial inventory is then drawn from a uniform distribution with the mentioned support. Similarly, the initial inventory at the depot is drawn

from a uniform distribution with the support $[\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} D_{i0}, \min\{S_1 + S_2, \bar{L}_0\}]$. The lower support is set to $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} D_{i0}$ in order to guarantee that the first-period deliveries are feasible.

Furthermore, we assume that the depot has the smallest inventory cost due to economies of scale. The customers then have a marginal inventory cost increase relative to the depot. The customers' marginal inventory cost per unit of product per time period is drawn from a uniform distribution with the support $[0.0, 0.3]$. The support is based on a multi-case study that covers the inventory holding costs on automated inventory systems [8].

3.2.4 Vehicle fleet

All instances presented in this paper have a vehicle fleet with characteristics based on real life vehicle types. We have defined a set of three vehicle types commonly used. Table 3.1 shows the different vehicle types used to generate the instances where the column 'Vehicles' defines the vehicle name/ID and the column 'Capacity' denotes the corresponding capacity expressed in EUR-pallets. A EUR-pallet has the dimensions 1200mm \times 800mm \times 144mm (47.2in \times 31.5in \times 5.7in), and has a total safe loading weight of 1500 kg. For clarity, we also point out that the demands and the inventory capacities are also expressed in EUR-pallets.

Table 3.1: Types of vehicles used for the instances.

Vehicle type	Capacity (EUR-pallets)
Small truck	8
Truck	18
Trailer truck	38

3.2.5 Feasibility inspection heuristic

We developed an inspection heuristic to ensure that the instances are feasible. It checks if the given customer demands can be covered by a given fleet of vehicles. If this is not possible, the heuristic expands the vehicle fleet or reduces the demand.

Algorithm 1: Feasibility inspection heuristic

```

1 repeat
2   Run an IRP construction heuristic (Algorithm 2)
3   for  $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ ,  $t \in \mathcal{T}$  do
4     | Let  $\sigma_{it} = \max(D_{it} - I_{it}, 0)$ 
5   end
6   Let  $\bar{k} = \min(K^{\max} - K, \left\lceil \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sigma_{it}}{Q \times |\mathcal{T}|} \right\rceil)$ 
7   if  $\bar{k} > 0$  then
8     |  $K \leftarrow K + \bar{k}$ 
9   end
10  else
11    Let  $\bar{d} = \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sigma_{it}}{|\mathcal{T}|}$ 
12    for  $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ ,  $t \in \mathcal{T}$  do
13      |  $D_{it} \leftarrow D_{it} - \bar{d}$ 
14    end
15  end
16 until no stock-outs

```

The basic scheme of our feasibility inspection heuristic is illustrated in Algorithm 1. The heuristic starts by invoking a construction heuristic for the IRP, which computes the delivered quantities to each customer in each time period. Next, given the inventory position at the beginning of each time period t , and the demand requirements D_{it} , the feasibility heuristic estimates the stock-out value σ_{it} , $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$, $t \in \mathcal{T}$. If the solution comprises stock-outs at customers, two procedures are invoked to recover feasibility. The

first procedure increases the fleet size by \bar{k} identical vehicles. The value of \bar{k} is chosen such that the shortages at customers are covered and such that the fleet size K does not exceed a preset limit K^{\max} . If no more vehicles can be added, the second procedure is performed. It reduces customer demands by an amount of \bar{d} , which absorbs the encountered stock-out. Whenever a change in the fleet size or the demand requirements occurs, a new IRP solution is generated, and the process is iterated until a feasible one is obtained.

Construction heuristic for the IRP: For the sake of completeness, we describe the construction heuristic we developed to derive IRP solutions. For each time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, we construct two subsets of customers. The first one, referred by *urgent customers*, \mathcal{N}_t^{UC} , $t \in \mathcal{T}$, which includes all customers whose inventory level I_{it} is not sufficient to cover the demand D_{it} in the current time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, while the *non-urgent customers* subset, \mathcal{N}_t^{NUC} , $t \in \mathcal{T}$, contains the remaining ones. Starting with the first subset, each customer is considered sequentially, and the delivered quantity q_{it} is set as the potential stock-out, that we denote by σ_{it} , $i \in \mathcal{N}_t^{UC}$, $t \in \mathcal{T}$. The customer is assigned to the vehicle with the highest residual capacity r_{kt} , $t \in \mathcal{T}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Note that such a solution might be infeasible in terms of stock-outs at the supplier and vehicles' capacities. However, when combined with the feasibility inspection heuristic described in Algorithm 1, we guarantee that it is always possible to satisfy all customers' demands. Next, for every element i in the second subset, we add a visit at day $t < |\mathcal{T}|$ using the vehicle with the highest residual capacity r_{kt} , $t \in \mathcal{T}$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$. The quantity q_{it} delivered to customer i on day t is the minimum between: (i) the maximum quantity that can be delivered without exceeding the maximum inventory capacity \bar{L}_i , (ii) the highest available vehicle's residual capacity, and (iii) the quantity $I_{0,t}$ available at the supplier. Each vehicle's route is ultimately constructed using the Lin-Kernighan heuristic [21]. The proposed construction heuristic is presented in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: A construction heuristic for the inventory routing problem

```

1  for  $t \in \mathcal{T}$  do
2  | Let  $\mathcal{N}_t^{UC} := \{i \in \mathcal{N}^C : I_{it} < D_{it}\}$ 
3  | for  $i \in \mathcal{N}_t^{UC}$  do
4  | | Let  $\sigma_{it} = \max(D_{it} - I_{it}, 0)$ 
5  | | Let  $k$  the index of the vehicle with the highest residual capacity  $r_{kt}$ 
6  | |  $q_{itk} \leftarrow \sigma_{it}$ 
7  | | Update vehicle and inventory calculations
8  | end
9  | Let  $\mathcal{N}_t^{NUC} := \{i \in \mathcal{N}^C : I_{it} \geq D_{it}\}$ 
10 | for  $i \in \mathcal{N}_t^{NUC}$  do
11 | | if  $t < T$  then
12 | | | if ( $i$  is visited) then
13 | | | | Let  $k$  be the index of the vehicle serving customer  $i$ 
14 | | | |  $q_{itk} \leftarrow q_{itk} + \min(r_{kt}, \min(U_i - I_{it}, I_{0,t}))$ 
15 | | | end
16 | | | else
17 | | | | Let  $k$  the index of the vehicle with the highest residual capacity  $r_{kt}$ 
18 | | | |  $q_{itk} \leftarrow \min(r_{kt}, \min(U_i - I_{it}, I_{0,t}))$ 
19 | | | end
20 | | | Update vehicle and inventory calculations
21 | | end
22 | end
23 | for  $k \in \mathcal{K}$  do
24 | | Build the vehicle's route using the Lin-Kernighan algorithm
25 | end
26 end

```

3.2.6 Instance overview

This section provides an overview of the main attributes of the instances proposed in this paper, and a brief comparison with the original instances. The instances are ordered by the number of customers ranging from 10 to 200. We defined two geographical areas: urban and rural. Each area yields a different transportation to inventory costs ratio as described in Section 3.2.2. Node positioning can be random, clustered, or random clustered. The planning horizon length varies between 6, 9, and 12 time periods. A vehicle can have a capacity of either 8, 18, or 38 EUR-pallets. In so doing, it is likely that the average route length on instances with different vehicle types vary. The number of available vehicles K is calculated by running the feasibility inspection heuristic presented in Section 3.2.5. For each instance, only one vehicle type is selected, creating a homogeneous fleet of vehicles. An overview of the instances' main attributes is presented in Table 3.2. By varying these attributes, one at a time, we obtain 270 instances with distinct configurations. Finally, the name of an instance follows the format C-L-N-Q-T, where C is the geographical area (rural or urban), L is the node positioning (random, clustered, or random clustered), N is the number of customers, Q represents the vehicle capacity, and T is the length of the planning horizon. The new benchmark instances are publicly available at the AXIOM project web page: <http://axiomresearchproject.com/publications/>. The instance files and the best known solutions from the B&C method and the matheuristic are available at this web page.

Table 3.2: Overview of the main attributes of the new set of benchmark instances for the IRP.

Area	Positioning	Periods	Customers	Vehicle capacity
Urban, Rural	R,C,RC	6, 9, 12	10, 25, 50, 100, 200	8, 18, 38

Considering these attributes, some instances overlap with the original instances, namely those with random node positioning, six-time periods, and 10 and 25 customers. Since we scale the vehicle fleet to the number of customers, only some of the 10 and 25 customer instances have a vehicle fleet of the same size as in the original instances, and the remaining instances have a vehicle fleet strictly larger than the original instances. Even though these instances have overlapping attributes, some key features are different and which we expect to affect the solution structure.

The new instances have smaller average vehicle capacity to inventory capacity ratios than the original instances, which hypothetically can reduce the maximum feasible route length, thus yielding a smaller solution space. On the other hand, instances with a large vehicle fleet have been proven to be more challenging for B&C methods [1, 7, 15, 22, 25]. The new instances have time-varying demands for each customer, while the original instances have constant demands. This might affect the diversity of routes in a good solution. When the demands are time-varying, it might be worse to reuse a route in other time periods than when the demands are constant.

Another feature that differs from the original instances is the inventory holding costs. Since the depot in the new instances always has the lowest inventory holding cost, it is possible to derive an upper bound on the delivered quantity to each customer, which is equal to the total demand over the planning horizon. This is only possible for a subset of customers in the original instances, potentially making the dual bounds in an exact method better for the new instances. However, calculating such a bound is possible only if the inventory capacity at the depot cannot be violated, which might occur in the new instances. This makes it hard to predict whether it is possible to use such a bound or not without assessing each individual instance. In the new instances, the inventory capacities and the initial inventory levels also make the minimum visiting frequency vary more across customers compared to the original instances. Some customers must be visited more frequently than in the original instances, while others may be visited less frequently. The net effect of this behavior is hard to predict. Due to the mentioned features of the new instances, we show in Section 3.5.2 that the net effect of these features does not make the problem significantly easier to solve than the comparable original instances, i.e., those with the same number of customers, number of periods and number of vehicles.

3.3 Model formulation

In this section, we present a MILP formulation for the IRP. In addition to the notation presented in Section 3.1 we introduce the following decision variables. Let x_{ijt} be 1 if a vehicle traverses arc $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$ in time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, 0 otherwise. To improve readability of the model we introduce for each node $i \in \mathcal{N}$ and time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$ an integer variable δ_{it} , which denotes the number of times node i is visited in time period t (binary for the customers $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$). For each node $i \in \mathcal{N}$ and time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, we also

introduce a non-negative variable s_{it} , which represents the inventory level at node i at the end of time period t . Finally, we define for each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ and time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$ a non-negative variable q_{it} , which determines the quantity delivered to customer i in time period t . We can now formulate the standard IRP as the MILP described by Skålnes et al. [25]:

$$\min \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} C_{ij} x_{ijt} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} H_{it} s_{it} \quad (3.7)$$

$$s_{0t} = S_t - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} q_{it} + s_{0(t-1)}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$s_{it} = q_{it} - D_{it} + s_{i(t-1)}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.9)$$

$$\underline{L}_i \leq s_{it} \leq \bar{L}_i, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.10)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} q_{it} \leq Q \delta_{0t}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.11)$$

$$q_{it} \leq \bar{L}_i - s_{i(t-1)}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.12)$$

$$q_{it} \leq \min\{\bar{L}_i - I_{it}, Q\} \delta_{it}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.13)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} x_{ijt} = \delta_{it}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.14)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} x_{ijt} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} x_{jit}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.15)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in (\mathcal{S}:\mathcal{S})} x_{ijt} \leq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}} \delta_{it} - \delta_{mt}, \quad \mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{N}^C, \quad |\mathcal{S}| \geq 2, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad m \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (3.16)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in (\mathcal{S}:\mathcal{N} \setminus \mathcal{S})} Q x_{ijt} \geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}} q_{it}, \quad \mathcal{S} \subset \mathcal{N}^C, \quad |\mathcal{S}| \geq 2, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.17)$$

$$q_{it} \geq 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.18)$$

$$\delta_{it} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.19)$$

$$\delta_{0t} \in \{0, 1, \dots, K\}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.20)$$

$$x_{ijt} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (i, j) \in \mathcal{A}, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (3.21)$$

where $s_{00} = I_0$ and $s_{i0} = I_i$, $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$. The objective function (3.7) sums up of the transportation cost and the inventory holding cost. The inventory holding cost associated with the initial inventory level is a constant term, and thus has been omitted from the object function. Constraints (3.8) and (3.9) balance the inventory at the supplier and the customers, respectively, while constraints (3.10) make sure that the inventory levels always stay between their lower and upper limits at the supplier and at the customers. Constraints (3.11) state that the vehicles used in a given period never delivers more than its capacity. The maximum level inventory policy is enforced by constraints (3.12), and constraints (3.13) ensure that a delivery only can be made to a customer if the customer is visited. Constraints (3.14) are the degree constraints and constraints (3.15) ensure a correct vehicle-flow between nodes. The subtour and generalized subtour-elimination constraints are stated in constraints (3.16) and (3.17), respectively, where the notation on the form $(\mathcal{E} : \mathcal{F}) = \{(i, j) : i \in \mathcal{E}, j \in \mathcal{F} \setminus \{i\}\}$ denotes the set of arcs going from the nodes in the set of nodes, \mathcal{E} , to the nodes in the set of nodes, \mathcal{F} . Finally, constraints (3.18)–(3.21) define the variable domains.

3.4 Solution methods

This section describes the B&C method and the matheuristic used to derive primal and dual bounds on the new benchmark instances. For instances where these methods fail to obtain a feasible solution, we show that they are feasible by running the construction heuristic given in Algorithm 2. Section 3.4.1 briefly describes the B&C algorithm, and Section 3.4.2 describes the matheuristic.

3.4.1 Branch-and-cut method

The B&C method starts by solving the linear relaxation of the MILP defined the formulation (3.7)–(3.15) and (3.18)–(3.21). The standard and generalized subtour-elimination constraints, (3.16) and (3.17),

respectively, are added dynamically at every node of the branch-and-bound tree. In addition, we use the same valid inequalities as Skålnes et al. [25], i.e., those of Coelho and Laporte [15], the capacity inequalities of Desaulniers, Rakke, and Coelho [16] and the Disjoint Route (DR) inequalities of Avella, Boccia, and Wolsey [7], but where we omit the h -DR inequalities. For the 100 and 200 customer instances these valid inequalities become too expensive to separate using the suggested route length of $h = 8$. Finding the best parameter settings for these valid inequalities on larger instances is outside the scope of this paper and is better left to future research. In addition, it is worth pointing out that we are not using the customer schedule formulation of Skålnes et al. [25] since the enumeration of the customer schedules is too time-consuming for 9 and 12 time periods. The a priori generation of these schedules is better suited for six time periods or less. The capacity inequalities of Desaulniers, Rakke, and Coelho [16] and the simple DR inequalities of Avella, Boccia, and Wolsey [7] are separated exactly, and added only in the root node due to the computational complexity of these separation algorithms. Further details on these separation algorithms are presented by Skålnes et al. [25] and Avella, Boccia, and Wolsey [7].

For completeness, we present the formulations for the mentioned valid inequalities. Skålnes et al. [25] presented the following valid inequalities for an arc-flow formulation of the IRP:

$$x_{ijt} \leq \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} x_{jkt}, \quad (i, j) \in \mathcal{N}^C \times \mathcal{N}^C, t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (3.22)$$

The valid inequalities (3.22) make sure that the flow from a customer j is larger than or equal to the flow between two customers i and j , preventing a direct flow back to i from j .

In addition, we include the following valid inequalities proposed by Coelho and Laporte [15]:

$$\delta_{it} \leq \delta_{0t}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.23)$$

$$\sum_{t'=1}^t \delta_{it'} \geq \left\lceil \left[\left(\sum_{t'=1}^t D_{it'} - I_i \right) / \min\{\bar{L}_i, Q\} \right] \right\rceil, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.24)$$

$$\sum_{t'=t_1}^{t_2} \delta_{it'} \geq \left\lceil \left[\left(\sum_{t'=t_1}^{t_2} D_{it'} - \bar{L}_i \right) / \min\{\bar{L}_i, Q\} \right] \right\rceil, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t_1 \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \{1\}, \quad t_2 \in \mathcal{T}, \quad t_2 \geq t_1, \quad (3.25)$$

$$\sum_{t'=t_1}^{t_2} \delta_{it'} \geq \left\lceil \left[\left(\sum_{t'=t_1}^{t_2} D_{it'} - s_{i(t_1-1)} \right) / \min\{\bar{L}_i, Q, \sum_{t'=t_1}^{t_2} D_{it'}\} \right] \right\rceil, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}^C, \quad t_1, t_2 \in \mathcal{T}, \quad t_2 \geq t_1. \quad (3.26)$$

The valid inequalities (3.23) give in each period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, a tighter relationship between the δ_{it} variables between the depot, 0, and the customers $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$. Valid lower bounds on the number of visits to a customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ within a time interval are imposed by the valid inequalities (3.24)-(3.26). The valid inequalities (3.24) impose a lower bound on the number of visits to a given customer over all time intervals starting in the first period, thus being able to take into account the initial inventory level. The valid inequalities (3.25) compute such a lower bound for all time intervals, but can no longer take into account the initial inventory level and use instead the maximum storage capacity, \bar{L}_i . Both inequalities (3.24) and (3.25) can be rounded up to the nearest integer, because all entries used to calculate the valid lower bound are parameters. This is not true for the valid inequalities (3.26), because they include the actual inventory level at a customer in a given time period, $s_{i(t_1-1)}$, and rounding up these expressions would make the model non-linear.

Furthermore, we use the capacity inequalities of Desaulniers, Rakke, and Coelho [16], modified to an arc-flow formulation by Skålnes et al. [25]. These valid inequalities are inspired by the rounded capacity inequalities for the capacitated vehicle routing problem [20]. Before we present these inequalities, let us define some additional notation. For each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ and time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, assuming a first-in, first-out inventory policy, let I_{it} be the quantity left in the inventory from the initial inventory, $I_{it} = \max\{I_i - \sum_{s=1}^t D_{is}, 0\}$. Then, for each customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ and time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, we can define the residual demand, \bar{D}_{it} as the demand that cannot be covered by the initial inventory, $\bar{D}_{it} = \max\{D_{it} - I_{it}, 0\}$. We define the set of all positive residual demands, $\mathcal{RD} = \{(i, t) \in \mathcal{N}^C \times \mathcal{T} \mid \bar{D}_{it} > 0\}$, and the subset $\mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathcal{RD}$. For customer $j \in \mathcal{N}^C$ and period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, the positive residual demand \bar{D}_{jt} can be covered by a vehicle traversing arc (i, j) in period t or earlier as long as the inventory capacity is not violated. Therefore, we define a set, $\mathcal{P}_{jt}^- = \{(i, j, m) \in \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{N}^C \times \mathcal{T} \mid (\bar{D}_{jt} > 0 \wedge m \leq t \wedge (\sum_{l=m}^t \bar{D}_{jl} + I_{jm} \leq \bar{L}_j))\}$, containing the arcs (i, j) traversed in period m , denoted (i, j, m) , that can cover the residual demand \bar{D}_{jt} at customer $j \in \mathcal{N}^C$ in period $t \in \mathcal{T}$. Finally, let $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{U}} = \{(i, j, m) \in \mathcal{P}_{jt}^- \mid (j, t) \in \mathcal{U}\}$ be the set of arcs that

can cover the residual demands in the subset of residual demands \mathcal{U} . To be clear, we point out that an arc (i, j, m) may serve several consecutive residual demands at customer j , but appears at most once in $\mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{U}}$. Then, we define the capacity inequalities as follows:

$$\sum_{(i,j,t) \in \mathcal{A}_{\mathcal{U}}} x_{ijt} \geq \left\lceil \sum_{(i,t) \in \mathcal{U}} \bar{D}_{it} / Q \right\rceil, \quad \mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathcal{RD}. \quad (3.27)$$

which in principal impose a valid lower bound on the number of arcs needed to cover a given subset of residual demands \mathcal{U} .

We also incorporate the Simple DR inequalities that were initially proposed by Avella, Boccia, and Wolsey [7]. Let \mathcal{R} be the set of arcs in a route and let $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R})$ be the set of nodes in that route. For a given time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, a subset $S \subseteq \mathcal{N}^C$, a partition $(\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3, \mathcal{S}_4)$ of S , and the coefficients $\mu_{ij} \geq 0$ for all $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$, a general valid DR inequality can be written as follows:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} \mu_{ij} x_{ijt} \geq \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_1} q_{jt} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_2} (q_{jt} - s_{j(t+1)}) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_3} (q_{jt} - s_{jt}) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_4} (s_{jt} - (\bar{L}_j - \sum_{m=t-1}^t D_{jm})) \quad (3.28)$$

if

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{R}} \mu_{ij} \geq \min\{Q, \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R}) \cap \mathcal{S}_1} \bar{L}_i + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R}) \cap \mathcal{S}_2} (D_{it} + D_{i(t+1)}) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R}) \cap \mathcal{S}_3} D_{it} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R}) \cap \mathcal{S}_4} D_{i(t-1)}\}. \quad (3.29)$$

for every route starting and ending at the supplier.

The simple DR inequalities arise when fixing the coefficients μ_{ij} in such a way that the resulting DR inequality is always valid regardless of how the customers in S are partitioned. The separation algorithm then aims to find the optimal subset S and corresponding partition given predetermined coefficients μ_{ij} . For completeness we state the Simple DR inequalities here, but more details are presented by Avella, Boccia, and Wolsey [7]. For each period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, assume a partition $(\mathcal{S}_0, \mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3, \mathcal{S}_4)$ of S , where we define $v_i = Q$ for $i \in \mathcal{S}_0$, $v_i = \bar{L}_i$ for $i \in \mathcal{S}_1$, $v_i = D_{it} + D_{i(t+1)}$ for $i \in \mathcal{S}_2$, $v_i = D_{it}$ for $i \in \mathcal{S}_3$, $v_i = D_{i(t-1)}$ for $i \in \mathcal{S}_4$, and $v_i = 0$ for $i \in \mathcal{N} \setminus S$. Then, we set $\mu_{ij} = \min\{Q - v_i, v_j\}$ for all $(i, j) \in \mathcal{A}$, and define the Simple DR inequalities for each $t \in \mathcal{T}$:

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}} \mu_{ij} x_{ijt} \geq \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_0 \cup \mathcal{S}_1} q_{jt} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_2} (q_{jt} - s_{j,t+1}) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_3} (q_{jt} - s_{jt}) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}_4} (s_{jt} - (\bar{L}_j - \sum_{s=t-1}^t D_{js})). \quad (3.30)$$

3.4.2 Matheuristic

We have implemented the matheuristic of Archetti, Boland, and Speranza [5], which has been successful for the original benchmark instances of the IRP. The proposed method involves three phases: a construction phase, a tabu search algorithm, and an improvement phase. Both the construction and improvement phases rely on the solution of MILP models.

The construction phase aims to generate a starting solution and relies on a relaxation of an exact MILP formulation, where only the integrality of the δ -variables is retained. The relaxation does not have to be optimal, and any feasible relaxation obtained within a specified time limit is accepted. A solution to the IRP is next completed by applying the Lin-Kernighan algorithm to derive vehicle routes. The construction phase includes a fail-safe heuristic that constructs an IRP solution when the MILP relaxation fails to achieve that within the given time limit. However, the feasibility of the fail-safe solution is not guaranteed.

The tabu search looks for an enhanced solution to the IRP within the neighborhood of the starting solution. The neighborhood exploration employs five move operators: adding a visit, removing a visit, moving a visit to another day, swapping two visits, or moving to a different route. Delivered quantities are meanwhile adjusted to avoid stock-outs at customers. Vehicle capacity violations and stock-outs at the supplier are permitted during the tabu search, and specific recovery mechanisms are incorporated to restore the solution's feasibility. The improvement phase incorporates information collected during the

tabu search and attempts to fix the values of certain variables to zero. The MILP formulation becomes easier to solve, and it is rerun to obtain a new solution.

Finally, we emphasize that our reimplementations of the matheuristic may not be identical to the one used by Archetti, Boland, and Speranza [5], although when solving the original instances, we obtain the same solutions as the original implementation after most phases of the matheuristic. That is, we believe any differences in performance from the original implementation is due to implementation details such as the choice of data structures.

3.5 Computational results

In this section, we compare the two sets of instances and we discuss which attributes of the problem that seem to be the drivers of an instance’s difficulty, assessed by the performance of the matheuristic and the B&C method. The algorithms are implemented in C++, and the MILPs are solved by the commercial solver Gurobi 9.5, with default settings, except that we use a single thread for the computations. The experiments have been run on a Lenovo NextScale nx360 M5 machine, with a dual 2.3GHz Intel E5-2670v3 processor with 64 GB RAM memory. The B&C method has a computational time limit of 7,200 seconds, while the matheuristic has a computational time limit of 1,800 seconds for the instances with 10 and 25 customers and 2,400 seconds for the remaining instances. The detailed results can be found in the online supplement of this paper.

In Section 3.5.1, we present an instance space analysis comparing the new set of instances to the original. Section 3.5.2 further compares the original and new instances by examining how the matheuristic and the B&C method perform on a selected set of comparable instances. Then, the remaining part of this computational study investigates potential drivers of an instance’s difficulty, such as the number of customers and node locations in Section 3.5.3, the number of periods in Section 3.5.4 and the vehicle capacity in Section 3.5.5.

3.5.1 Instance space analysis

In this section, we present an instance space analysis of both the original and new set of instances, by using the research platform MATILDA [26, 27, 28]. Based on a defined set of features, we can describe the instance space for the IRP. Once the instance space is determined we use the toolkit provided by the MATILDA platform to create a 2D-projection of the instance space, visualizing the instances in this space along with an estimate of the theoretical boundary of the instance space. We show that the new instances nicely complement the original instances.

The number of features used to describe an instance, and ultimately the instance space, may be very large. Intuitively, a large set of features may seem beneficial, because it may capture more aspects of the underlying problem. On the other hand, a large set of features is also more likely to have overlapping features that may skew the representation of the instance space towards recurring features. In addition, a large feature set is more likely to run into numerical issues in the MATILDA toolkit. Therefore, we aim to define a small set of features that best describe the underlying problem and which we believe to be the best predictors for algorithm performance. To achieve this we avoid using nominal values of entities like demand, inventory capacity and vehicle capacity since these can be scaled without affecting the underlying problem structure. Instead, we define features capturing the relationship between these entities and how they vary from period to period and customer to customer. We also include the meta-data such as the number of customers, number of periods and number of vehicles as these have been shown to be good predictors for algorithm performance on instances of the IRP. Therefore, we define the following features describing the instance space:

1. Number of customers, $|\mathcal{N}^C|$.
2. Number of periods, $|\mathcal{T}|$.
3. Number of vehicles, $|\mathcal{K}|$.
4. Average standard deviation of demand, $\sigma^D = \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}^C} \left(\sqrt{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (D_{it} - \mu_i^D)^2} / |\mathcal{T}| \right)}{|\mathcal{N}^C|}$, where the average demand for customer $i \in \mathcal{N}^C$ is defined as $\mu_i^D = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} D_{it} / |\mathcal{T}|$.

5. Standard deviation of inventory capacity, $\sigma^I = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sqrt{(\bar{L}_i - \mu^I)^2} / |\mathcal{N}|$, where we define the average inventory capacity $\mu^I = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \bar{L}_i / |\mathcal{N}|$.
6. Average edge cost, $\mu^E = \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A}^E} C_{ij} / |\mathcal{A}^E|$, where $\mathcal{A}^E = \{(i,j) \in \mathcal{A} \mid i < j\}$ is the set of edges.
7. Average inventory-cost to average edge-cost ratio, $R^{IE} = \mu^{IC} / \mu^E$, where $\mu^{IC} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} H_{it} / |\mathcal{N}| |\mathcal{T}|$ is the average inventory cost.
8. Average demand to average inventory capacity ratio, $R^{DI} = \mu^D / \mu^I$.
9. Average demand to vehicle capacity ratio, $R^{DQ} = \mu^D / Q$.
10. Average inventory capacity to vehicle capacity ratio, $R^{IQ} = \mu^I / Q$.

Based on these features, methods of the MATILDA toolkit calculates a 2D-projection matrix that aims to retain as much as possible of the variation of the original 10D instance space in the new 2D instance space. The 2D-projection matrix maps the original feature values onto a new coordinate system $[z_1, z_2]$. The axes z_1 and z_2 do not have a practical interpretation, but instances that lie close in the 2D instance space have similar feature values, while those that lie far apart have larger differences in feature values. The coordinates for each instance is calculated by doing the following 2D-projection:

$$\begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.2295 & 0.5181 \\ 0.1804 & 0.4903 \\ 0.3642 & 0.3166 \\ 0.3926 & 0.3232 \\ -0.5161 & 0.1563 \\ -0.2123 & 0.0201 \\ -0.0921 & 0.4731 \\ 0.0483 & -0.4811 \\ 0.5423 & -0.0171 \\ 0.5185 & 0.0087 \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} |\mathcal{N}^C| \\ |\mathcal{T}| \\ |\mathcal{K}| \\ \sigma^D \\ \sigma^I \\ \mu^E \\ R^{IE} \\ R^{DI} \\ R^{DQ} \\ R^{IQ} \end{bmatrix}$$

where the features are normalized to $[0, 1]$ within the MATILDA platform. We also tested other instance spaces, like omitting the three first features, or adding additional features such as average demand, average inventory capacity, a classifier to distinguish between randomly, clustered or random-clustered node positions. All the instance spaces that we tested resulted in various shifts and stretches in the 2D-space, but the relative positions between the instances within the 2D-space remained similar. We therefore consider the instance space to be quite robust, and that it captures the most important characteristics of the underlying problem. Figure 3.3 shows the 2D-projection of the instance space generated by the MATILDA toolkit. The red dots represent the new instances while the blue dots represent the original instances. We see that the new instances nicely complements the original instances, where only a small number of the instances overlap.

Figure 3.4 shows the same 2D-projection of the instance space as shown in Figure 3.3, but where the color now represent the number of customers in a given instance. The number of customers are normalized so that the yellow color ($N=1$) represent the 200 customer instances and the dark blue color ($N=0$) represent the 5 customer instances. In addition, the red line surrounding the instances represent the theoretical boundary of the instance space. Note that this by no means are an exact boundary, but is just an estimate. The MATILDA toolkit creates this estimate based on the correlations between the defined features, so there is no guarantee that the white space within the boundary is actually feasible with respect to the underlying problem, and there might also be possible to create instances that lie outside of the boundary. Despite this fact, it is still a powerful visual aid that help us gain insight regarding the instances, and we see that the two sets nicely complement each other. We can observe that there is a possibility of creating even more instances to fill in the gap between the two sets of instances, but this is not the focus of this work. We aim to create an instance set of more real-world-like instances that complement the original benchmark instances.

Figure 3.3: 2D-visualization of the instance space highlighting which instances belong to the original and new set of instances.

3.5.2 Impact of instance features

In this section, we compare the original and new instances to demonstrate that the net impact of the features discussed in Section 3.2.6 does not make the new instances significantly easier to solve than the original instances. There are 90 of the new instances that are comparable to the original instances if we only consider the number of customers and the number of periods, i.e., the instances with 10, 25, 50, 100, and 200 customers and six time periods. If we only consider the number of customers and the number of vehicles, i.e., instances with two, four, or five vehicles, the number of comparable instances drops to 51. None of the new instances have a fleet of three vehicles. If we consider all three attributes, the number of customers, the number of periods, and the number of vehicles, there are only 18 of the new instances that are directly comparable to the original instances. Therefore, for the fairest comparison, we focus on these 18 instances.

First, in order to show that our matheuristic is a reasonable reimplemention of that of Archetti, Boland, and Speranza [5], we compare these two implementations in Table 3.3 on a subset of the original instances, i.e., the instances of six-time periods and up to 30 customers. This subset can be further partitioned into smaller disjoint subsets defined by the number of customers (N) and the number of vehicles (K). The table reports the average relative difference between the upper bound found by our reimplemention (UB^R) and the original matheuristic (UB^A): $\frac{UB^R - UB^A}{UB^A}$. This means a negative number denotes an improvement in favor of our reimplemention, highlighted in bold. From Table 3.3 we see that our reimplemention obtains slightly worse upper bounds on average; however, better performance is achieved on the smallest instances. The subsets with the worst performance are the 30-customer instances with 4 and 5 vehicles. Despite this, we consider our reimplemention to be of sufficient quality to carry on the analyses presented in this paper.

Now, we focus on how our reimplemention of the matheuristic performs on the set of comparable instances, i.e., for the 10 and 25-customer instances with six-time periods and two, four, and five vehicles. Table 3.4 compares the average gaps and average computational times in seconds between the comparable instances of the original and new set obtained by the matheuristic. The number of instances ('# Instances') is also reported for each subset. We define the gap as $(UB - LB)/LB$, where UB is the upper bound,

Figure 3.4: 2D-visualization of the instance space highlighting the normalized number of customers, i.e., yellow ($N=1$) indicates 200 customers and dark blue ($N=0$) indicates 5 customers.

Table 3.3: Average difference from the results of Archetti, Boland, and Speranza [5] in percentage.

N \ K	K				Average
	2	3	4	5	
5	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	-0.03	1.94	-1.10	-1.89	-0.27
15	-0.04	-1.07	-2.57	-2.56	-1.56
20	0.18	-0.16	0.97	0.56	0.39
25	0.28	2.13	-0.33	0.64	0.68
30	0.77	2.92	5.09	6.01	3.70
Average	0.19	0.96	0.34	0.48	0.49

and LB is the lower bound obtained from the B&C method. Here we see that the average gap for the 10-customer instances is slightly better for the new instances than for the original instances, which indicates that the matheuristic performs better on this subset of the new instances than on the old. However, the average computational times pull in the opposite direction, namely that the new instances induce a much longer run time to obtain a good feasible solution. The computational times are almost doubled, even though the average gap is better. Note that, for a few situations, the matheuristic may converge before the preset time limit because either the mathematical component in Phase 1 quickly return a solution, or the Phase 3 fails to return a feasible solution. For the comparable instances of 25 customers, the average gap is slightly worse for the new instances compared with the old ones, while the average computational time is similar. Overall, the matheuristic seems to find worse solutions on average and spends more time doing so on the new instances compared to the old.

Let us now shift our focus to the B&C method. Table 3.5 reports the average gaps and average computational times for the comparable 10 and 25-customer instances with six-time periods and two, four, and five vehicles. Here the B&C method performs quite similarly on the original and new instances, but striking differences appear in instances with 10 customers. The B&C seems to struggle more on the new two-vehicle instances, while it performs better on the new four- and five-vehicle instances. For

Table 3.4: Comparison of the performance of the matheuristic on the original and new instances.

N	K	Original			New		
		Gap [%]	Seconds	# Instances	Gap [%]	Seconds	# Instances
10	2	0.60	267	10	1.28	1,339	6
10	4	1.96	1,082	10	0.99	1,800	3
10	5	2.06	1,217	10	1.17	1,800	3
Average 10 customers		1.54	855	30	1.18	1,570	12
25	5	9.17	1,769	10	10.46	1,800	6
Average all		3.45	1,084	40	4.27	1,646	18

the 25-customer instances, the B&C performs slightly better on the new instances than the old, but on average, both the gaps and the computational times are relatively similar. This indicates that the net impact of the changed features of the new instances is small and that they maintain the same difficulty as the original instances when the main attributes are kept equal, i.e., the number of customers, number of periods, and the number of vehicles.

Table 3.5: Comparison of the B&C method on the original and new instances.

N	K	Original			New		
		Gap [%]	Seconds	# Instances	Gap [%]	Seconds	# Instances
10	2	0.56	1,984	10	1.26	4,812	6
10	4	0.94	7,200	10	0.30	4,807	3
10	5	0.55	6,049	10	0.23	4,810	3
Average 10 customers		0.68	5,078	30	0.76	4,810	12
25	5	3.58	7,199	10	3.00	7,199	6
Average all		1.41	5,608	40	1.51	5,606	18

3.5.3 Impact of node locations on algorithm performance

In this section, we examine how the two solution methods perform on the new set of instances, focusing on the number of customers and the node locations. Table 3.6 gives an overview of the number of feasible solutions obtained by the construction heuristic, the matheuristic, and the B&C method. The left-most column denotes the number of customers, and for each block of the table, 'R', 'C', and 'RC' denote random, clustered, and random-clustered node distributions. The columns 'Sum' shows the total number of feasible instances on each row for each solution method, and the row 'Sum' shows the total number of feasible instances for each column. The matheuristic found feasible solutions on all instances of 10 and 25 customers, a total of 108 instances, but the computational time limit was reached before the algorithm successfully obtained any feasible solutions for the remaining instances. The B&C algorithm found feasible solutions on the same instances, but only on some of the 50 and 100-customer instances. No feasible solutions were found by either the matheuristic or the B&C method on the 200-customer instances. As expected, the B&C method struggles to find feasible solutions within the time limit when the number of customers becomes high, i.e., 50 customers or more. However, it is more surprising that the matheuristic does not find any feasible solutions for 50 customers or more. A likely reason for this is that the vehicle fleet is scaled proportionally to the number of customers, making the relaxed vehicle-indexed MILPs of the matheuristic much slower than when the vehicle fleet is small. Another interesting observation is that the B&C method struggles to find feasible solutions for the clustered instances, and it finds the most feasible solutions in the random-clustered instances. We expected the random and clustered instances to represent two extreme points while the random-clustered instances would be somewhere in between. This is not the case, and it might simply be a random effect as the set of instances are relatively small, but it might as well be a result of the B&B phase of the MILP solver. Once the MILP solver has been able to determine which clusters to visit in which periods, it is likely that there are many near-optimal solutions with slight variations on how to accomplish this. This could lead to weak branching decisions as branching on an arc or node visit within a cluster is likely not to affect the dual bound by much, i.e., the cost of visiting a cluster with a given vehicle is high compared to the marginal cost of visiting an additional customer within the cluster with the same vehicle.

Moreover, the B&C method can prove optimality on only 13 out of 270 instances. These 13 instances are all among the 10 customer instances, where six are among the random, one among the clustered, and six among the random-clustered instances, respectively. This further supports the theory that the MILP solver especially struggles to find feasible solutions and close the gap on the clustered instances. In addition, the matheuristic found one of the optimal solutions among the random-clustered instances.

Table 3.6: Overview of the number of feasible solutions.

N	Constructive				Matheuristic				B&C			
	R	C	RC	Sum	R	C	RC	Sum	R	C	RC	Sum
10	18	18	18	54	18	18	18	54	18	18	18	54
25	18	18	18	54	18	18	18	54	18	18	18	54
50	18	18	18	54	0	0	0	0	5	3	10	18
100	18	18	18	54	0	0	0	0	3	0	4	7
200	18	18	18	54	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sum	90	90	90	270	36	36	36	108	44	39	50	133

Table 3.7 reports the average gaps between the upper bound and the best-known lower bound (LB), i.e., the lower bound obtained from the B&C algorithm. We define this as $\text{Gap} = \frac{\text{UB}^j - \text{LB}}{\text{LB}}$, where UB^j is the upper bound found by method j . Moreover, the table only includes the gaps for the instances where the method j found a feasible solution, i.e., for the construction heuristic, all instances are included except for two instances where no lower bound was successfully obtained. In contrast, for the matheuristic, 108 instances are included, and for the B&C method, 133 instances are included. The same is valid for the remaining tables. Results obtained using the construction heuristic are displayed, albeit not being the main focus of this study, only to assess the quality of solutions found by the matheuristic and the B&C methods. Recall that the construction heuristic in practice represents a naive planning approach where deliveries more or less are allocated randomly onto vehicles, and then the routes are found by solving a TSP for each vehicle. Such a solution is likely to perform badly, as seen in the 10 and 25-customer instances. However, for the B&C method, the solution quality drops significantly for the 50-customer instances, and for the 100-customer instances, the feasible solutions are much worse than those obtained by the construction heuristic. Therefore, it is not easy to draw conclusions from the 50 and 100-customer instances, but we present the results of these instances for the sake of completeness.

Table 3.7: Overview of average gaps (%).

N	Constructive				Matheuristic				B&C			
	R	C	RC	All	R	C	RC	All	R	C	RC	All
10	49.9	52.8	53.9	52.2	2.35	0.91	1.33	1.53	1.24	0.50	0.52	0.75
25	53.0	45.3	60.4	52.9	14.10	10.01	14.50	12.87	3.54	1.03	2.42	2.33
50	64.1	51.5	65.5	60.3	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	25.99	25.59	34.50	30.65
100	89.1	71.7	104.5	88.4	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	252.7	n/a	293.6	276.1
200	135.8	146.4	145.0	142.5	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
All	77.8	73.5	85.2	78.8	8.22	5.46	7.92	7.20	22.14	2.67	31.44	19.93

The most interesting observation from Table 3.7 is that the clustered instances have smaller average gaps than the other instances for both the matheuristic and the B&C method. For the B&C method, this is somewhat skewed because the B&C method finds fewer feasible solutions for the set of clustered instances. However, if we focus on the 10 and 25 customer instances where both methods found a feasible solution on all instances of this subset, we observe the same trend: the clustered instances have a better average gap. One possible explanation for this finding is that the main cost drivers are the arcs connecting the clusters in these instances. To see what we mean by this, let us examine the typical structure of the root node solution of the IRP. Figure 3.5 shows a visual representation of the root node solution in period 3 of the trailer truck ($Q = 38$) instance with 10 customers, 12 time periods, urban cost setting, and random node locations. The depot is marked by a square and the customers with small circular nodes. The nodes are green when the binary requirement is satisfied, and red if not. In this case, the binary requirement is only satisfied at customer 4 which are not visited. The customer ID is displayed next to the node, and the stapled arcs represent the fractional arc-flow that violates the binary requirements. The number

next to an arc states the actual flow on that arc. Here we see an underlying VRP solution structure, but where the binary relaxation allows the MILP solver to increase deliveries wherever necessary by sending an additional direct flow from the depot to a single customer or a small subset of customers. Note that customer 6 is served by a relatively large flow, but that most of it returns to the depot immediately, while a small part of it is forwarded to customer 5. The additional flow necessary to deliver the desired quantity to customer 5 arrives directly from the depot. Let us now assume that these customers instead belonged to a cluster where the distances within the cluster are small. Then the benefit of routing the flow in this way would diminish as the main driver of the routing cost would be the minimum flow required to serve the cluster. The flow within the cluster would behave similarly as we have seen in this example, but the relative impact on the cost from the internal flow of a cluster would be small, thus, on average, leading to a stronger lower bound on clustered instances than when the customers are randomly scattered across a region.

Figure 3.5: A visual representation of the root node solution in period 3 of the instance with 10 customers, vehicle capacity of 38, 12 time periods and random node locations.

3.5.4 Impact of number of periods on the solution quality

If we turn our attention to the number of periods of an instance, we expect the difficulty to increase with an increasing number of periods. Table 3.8 reports the average gaps per number of customers and per number of periods. For the matheuristic, we notice that the average gap is higher when the number of periods increases. The same can be observed for the B&C method, but with a few exceptions. The 25-customer and nine-period instances have an average gap lower than the 25-customer and six-period instances. This is most likely because the internal Gurobi heuristics managed to find a few more good feasible solutions for the nine-period instances than for the six-period instances. The same goes for the 100-customer instances where the feasible solutions for the six and nine-period instances are extremely bad, skewing the overall average. Disregarding the seven 100 customer instances where the B&C method found a feasible solution, the average gap for six, nine, and twelve periods becomes 4.84%, 5.96% and 6.40%, respectively. This confirms that it becomes harder to solve the instances when the number of

periods increases. However, it is interesting to see how small the impact of the number of periods has on the average gap compared with the number of customers. A possible reason for this is that a higher number of customers comes with a larger vehicle fleet, making the instances much more difficult.

Table 3.8: Overview of average gaps per number of customers and per number of time periods (%).

		Constructive				Matheuristic				B&C			
N	T	6	9	12	All	6	9	12	All	6	9	12	All
	10		56.14	49.67	50.80	52.20	0.90	1.47	2.22	1.53	0.52	0.66	1.08
25		55.50	48.73	54.47	52.90	9.46	12.49	16.66	12.87	2.01	1.82	3.15	2.33
50		65.05	61.39	54.56	60.34	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	19.16	39.90	44.94	30.65
100		91.32	89.06	84.92	88.43	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	276.3	334.8	40.8	276.1
200		135.0	155.5	136.2	142.5	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
All		80.61	80.88	74.82	78.80	5.18	6.98	9.44	7.20	16.39	35.18	7.24	19.93

In addition to the average gaps, let us investigate the number of periods' impact on the computational time. For most of the instances, the matheuristic and the B&C method did not terminate before they reached their respective time limits. However, they did for some of the 10 customer instances, and here the trend is clear, a higher number of periods require longer computational times. Table 3.9 reports the average computational times for the 10 customer instances across the vehicle capacity Q and the number of periods T . It is quite clear that the six-period instances require less computational time to be solved for both methods. However, a more surprising observation from this table is the impact on the average computational times from the vehicle capacity. The B&C method recorded the shortest solution time for the small truck instances, while the matheuristic has the shortest solution time for the trailer truck instances. A possible explanation for this is that the matheuristic heavily relies on the solution of a MILP formulation, which does not perform well for instances with a large number of vehicles.

Table 3.9: Average computational times for the 10 customer instances in seconds.

		Matheuristic				B&C			
Q	T	6	9	12	All	6	9	12	All
	Small truck (8)		1,800	1,800	1,800	1,800	1,498	3,617	5,265
Truck (18)		1,800	1,800	1,800	1,800	4,808	7,200	7,200	6,403
Trailer truck (38)		1,339	1,800	1,800	1,646	4,812	7,200	7,200	6,404
All		1,646	1,800	1,800	1 749	3,706	6,006	6,555	5,422

3.5.5 The impact of vehicle capacity on the solution quality

The somewhat surprising impact on the average computational times from the vehicle capacity motivates some further analysis along this dimension. Table 3.10 therefore reports the average gaps per number of customers and for each type of vehicle fleet denoted by the vehicle capacity. Let us start by focusing on the matheuristic. Despite having the shortest average computational time for the trailer truck ($Q = 38$) instances, it does not seem to reflect the quality of the solutions. The matheuristic obtained better solutions for the small truck ($Q = 8$) instances. This indicates that even though the relatively high number of vehicles has a negative impact on the average computational time for the matheuristic, it is easier to find reasonably good solutions on these instances.

The B&C method seems to obtain average gaps more correlated with the average computational time. Here the solution quality seems to drop when the vehicle capacity goes up. The average gaps are so significant for the 50 and 100 customer instances that it becomes hard to identify any trend, skewing the overall average. The apparent drop in solution quality also could be caused by a weaker linear relaxation when the vehicle capacity is large. Due to constraints (3.13), the delivered quantity to a given customer requires a smaller arc-flow the larger the vehicle capacity Q is. Thus, a larger vehicle capacity might give a worse lower bound on the objective function value than when the vehicle capacity is small. Nevertheless, from the 10 and 25 customer instances, where the average gaps are reasonably good, it is clear that it is

Table 3.10: Overview of average gaps per number of customers and vehicle capacity (%).

N \ Q	Constructive				Matheuristic				B&C			
	8	18	38	All	8	18	38	All	8	18	38	All
10	49.52	37.83	69.27	52.20	0.52	1.53	2.54	1.53	0.11	0.39	1.76	0.75
25	42.60	36.79	79.31	52.90	9.17	13.79	15.65	12.87	0.68	2.47	3.83	2.33
50	41.58	38.50	100.92	60.34	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	27.45	50.30	24.72	30.65
100	47.62	53.21	164.5	88.43	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	42.23	n/a	587.8	276.1
200	61.78	97.19	284.2	142.5	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
All	48.62	52.70	136.3	78.80	4.84	7.66	9.10	7.20	9.51	5.19	45.65	19.93

Figure 3.6: Overview of the route length on a subset of the new instances.

harder to prove that we have obtained an optimal or near-optimal solution when the vehicle capacity is large.

The solutions found by the B&C method obtained the best average gaps, so let us now shift our attention to how the vehicle capacity affects the structure of these solutions. We focus on how the average route length changes with the vehicle capacity. Let us define the route length as the number of customers in a route.

Figure 3.6 presents a box-plot giving an overview of the route lengths across selected subsets of the new instances. The bottom and top edges of the boxes represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, while the slightly thicker line within the edges of a box represents the median. The whiskers extend to 1.5 times the interquartile range, i.e., the difference between the third and first quartile, on both sides of the box. However, the whisker is limited to never exceeding any data point, so we do not see the whisker on the bottom side of the corresponding box for the small truck and the truck instances. The outliers are marked with a small circle.

For the small truck ($Q = 8$) instances, we can see that the majority of the routes, i.e., more than 75% of the routes, are direct routes visiting only one customer. For the truck ($Q = 18$) instances, there are still more than 50% of the routes that only visit one customer, but there is also a significant portion of routes with several customer visits. For the trailer truck ($Q = 38$) instances, less than 25% of the routes visit only one customer, and more than half of the routes visit three or more customers.

Focusing on the distribution of the route lengths for a subset of the original instances, we can see how the new instances nicely complement the original instances. In Figure 3.7, the route lengths for the original 10, 25, and 50-customer instances and two, three, four, and five vehicles are displayed in a box plot. In general, we observe that the route lengths are much longer for the original instances than for the new

Figure 3.7: Overview of the route lengths on a subset of the original instances.

instances. This indicates that the new instances represent a different business segment than the original instances. We can also observe that the route lengths increase much more for the original instances than the new instances going from 10 to 25 customers and going from 25 customers to 50 customers. This indicates that the vehicle fleet is scaled well for the new instances, capturing a behavior expected to see in practice, namely that an increase of customers is met by expanding the vehicle fleet, not the capacity of each vehicle.

3.6 Conclusion

In this work, we proposed a new set of real-world-like benchmark instances for the IRP, intended to complement the existing ones. The generated instances exhibit new features that should allow for a better assessment of the performance of the existing methodology and perhaps stimulate further thinking about new solution methods for the IRP. A total of 270 new instances were generated. Each instance is characterized by varied problem parameters. We conducted extensive computational experiments using two high-quality solution methods to derive lower and upper bounds for each instance and to study the impact of the instances' features on the methods' performance. Our analysis shows that the instances have the desired level of diversity and complexity and suggest the need to adapt the existing methodology accordingly.

We believe that these instances will possibly favor the use of commodity flow formulations since these formulations scale well for instances with a large number of vehicles and periods [22]. The new instances may also promote the application of branch-and-price algorithms over B&C algorithms, which are less effective when vehicle routes contain a few numbers of customer visits [16]. Besides, investigating the impact of valid inequalities and branching decisions on the new instances becomes a clear path for research. Regarding heuristic and matheuristic solution methods, we expect that the design of more complex neighborhoods and more problem-specific heuristics will provide the impetus for obtaining good results. The existing algorithms may also be improved by exploiting instance-specific information, such as partitioning the nodes into clusters by location or consumption rate, as suggested by Cao and Glover [12].

Finally, we emphasize that these instances can be extended to other rich IRP variants as needed by providing additional attributes like multiple depots, multiple products, time windows, or heterogeneous fleet of vehicles.

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Appendix 3.A Detailed results for the new instances

Table 3.11: Random node positioning and rural area.

N	Q	T	Construction		Matheuristic		B&C		
			UB	Seconds	UB	Seconds	LB	UB	Seconds
10	8	6	13,249.40	0	7,306.35	1,800	7,218.91	7,219.63	404
10	8	9	19,075.70	0	14,279.60	1,800	14,221.30	14,222.50	38
10	8	12	30,074.00	0	24,773.20	1,800	24,734.90	24,736.60	44
10	18	6	9,608.84	0	6,701.70	1,800	6,615.15	6,667.00	7,200
10	18	9	7,930.06	0	6,041.41	1,800	5,934.52	5,950.01	7,200
10	18	12	18,126.80	0	15,555.20	1,800	15,529.90	15,531.70	7,200
10	38	6	6,820.39	0	4,772.80	1,800	4,693.04	4,772.80	7,200
10	38	9	8,627.35	0	6,132.67	1,800	5,906.97	5,959.90	7,200
10	38	12	10,626.20	0	7,587.88	1,800	6,930.60	7,366.15	7,200
25	8	6	27,700.70	0	22,132.90	1,800	21,113.60	21,321.20	7,199
25	8	9	34,568.40	0	25,615.29	1,800	24,078.50	24,087.20	7,198
25	8	12	70,433.90	0	51,443.73	1,800	47,852.10	48,185.00	7,200
25	18	6	18,932.20	0	15,371.50	1,800	13,717.50	14,097.90	7,199
25	18	9	25,445.00	0	24,496.78	1,800	21,082.10	21,227.60	7,199
25	18	12	27,839.80	0	27,500.75	1,800	23,609.30	25,369.20	7,199
25	38	6	11,952.20	0	6,555.82	1,800	6,052.46	6,394.81	7,199
25	38	9	25,691.90	0	18,048.16	1,800	15,614.20	16,179.90	7,198
25	38	12	24,918.10	0	17,574.61	1,800	13,381.30	14,347.20	7,199
50	8	6	50,979.30	0	n/a	2,400	35,542.70	n/a	7,191
50	8	9	101,604.00	0	n/a	2,400	72,789.60	78,321.40	7,198
50	8	12	174,307.00	0	n/a	2,400	111,912.00	160,103.00	7,193
50	18	6	39,387.90	0	n/a	2,400	22,625.80	n/a	7,194
50	18	9	54,725.60	0	n/a	2,400	39,625.60	n/a	7,192
50	18	12	53,320.40	0	n/a	2,400	42,969.50	n/a	7,193
50	38	6	28,851.40	0	n/a	2,400	13,628.00	n/a	7,194
50	38	9	43,120.80	0	n/a	2,400	22,461.90	n/a	7,192
50	38	12	52,335.40	0	n/a	2,400	27,160.60	n/a	7,192
100	8	6	139,690.00	1	n/a	2,400	108,699.00	150,078.00	7,194
100	8	9	182,648.00	1	n/a	2,400	130,462.00	187,451.00	7,192
100	8	12	286,004.00	2	n/a	2,400	162,883.00	n/a	7,196
100	18	6	100,660.00	0	n/a	2,400	60,412.00	n/a	7,192
100	18	9	121,369.00	1	n/a	2,400	79,301.30	n/a	7,192
100	18	12	166,628.00	1	n/a	2,400	118,391.00	n/a	7,193
100	38	6	62,345.10	0	n/a	2,400	28,554.80	n/a	7,193
100	38	9	130,663.00	1	n/a	2,400	36,732.20	285,172.00	7,194
100	38	12	83,495.90	0	n/a	2,400	32,620.90	n/a	7,193
200	8	6	220,954.00	7	n/a	2,400	161,239.00	n/a	7,211
200	8	9	331,363.00	13	n/a	2,400	221,085.00	n/a	7,214
200	8	12	591,800.00	18	n/a	2,400	355,401.00	n/a	7,229
200	18	6	190,499.00	3	n/a	2,400	85,232.60	n/a	7,209
200	18	9	236,283.00	4	n/a	2,400	121,943.00	n/a	7,226
200	18	12	212,598.00	11	n/a	2,400	112,595.00	n/a	7,221
200	38	6	108,353.00	1	n/a	2,400	28,436.90	n/a	7,207
200	38	9	154,284.00	2	n/a	2,400	40,962.30	n/a	7,215
200	38	12	168,727.00	3	n/a	2,400	n/a	n/a	7,221

Table 3.12: Random node positioning and urban area.

N	Q	T	Construction		Matheuristic		B&C		
			UB	Seconds	UB	Seconds	LB	UB	Seconds
10	8	6	2,166.93	0	1,553.46	1,800	1,551.68	1,551.68	6
10	8	9	4,190.46	0	2,572.59	1,800	2,560.31	2,562.70	7,200
10	8	12	5,160.40	0	2,607.86	1,800	2,601.48	2,601.74	2,745
10	18	6	1,733.17	0	1,341.72	1,800	1,321.26	1,321.38	22
10	18	9	2,771.31	0	2,146.03	1,800	2,045.30	2,087.51	7,200
10	18	12	2,478.89	0	1,810.38	1,800	1,787.96	1,791.45	7,200
10	38	6	1,229.15	0	822.15	1,800	799.41	822.15	7,200
10	38	9	1,929.21	0	1,135.59	1,800	1,088.90	1,125.80	7,200
10	38	12	2,301.88	0	1,353.49	1,800	1,271.05	1,319.16	7,200
25	8	6	5,749.55	0	4,810.25	1,800	4,480.08	4,539.95	7,199
25	8	9	12,520.30	0	9,246.15	1,800	8,520.40	8,607.99	7,200
25	8	12	13,054.20	0	9,993.56	1,800	8,747.69	8,799.26	7,199
25	18	6	5,564.38	0	3,449.67	1,800	3,065.11	3,214.79	7,200
25	18	9	5,981.87	0	5,350.71	1,800	4,556.26	4,676.05	7,198
25	18	12	7,492.67	0	6,961.32	1,800	6,155.47	6,597.74	7,199
25	38	6	3,064.04	0	2,048.07	1,800	1,704.36	1,761.59	7,200
25	38	9	5,057.60	0	3,219.04	1,800	2,777.69	2,924.19	7,199
25	38	12	6,339.94	0	4,263.77	1,800	3,387.46	3,666.35	7,199
50	8	6	13,709.20	0	n/a	2,400	10,477.80	14,218.80	7,197
50	8	9	21,808.00	0	n/a	2,400	16,178.10	n/a	7,197
50	8	12	33,512.70	0	n/a	2,400	22,389.20	n/a	7,189
50	18	6	7,043.67	0	n/a	2,400	4,534.75	5,620.24	7,196
50	18	9	14,865.40	0	n/a	2,400	11,237.50	n/a	7,191
50	18	12	12,781.60	0	n/a	2,400	10,417.30	n/a	7,191
50	38	6	5,202.06	0	n/a	2,400	2,259.37	2,703.34	7,195
50	38	9	7,160.50	0	n/a	2,400	3,298.60	n/a	7,194
50	38	12	10,657.40	0	n/a	2,400	5,104.72	n/a	7,193
100	8	6	24,079.90	1	n/a	2,400	18,481.20	n/a	7,193
100	8	9	33,563.50	1	n/a	2,400	20,165.80	n/a	7,192
100	8	12	61,970.90	2	n/a	2,400	35,747.80	n/a	7,197
100	18	6	18,042.50	0	n/a	2,400	10,587.80	n/a	7,191
100	18	9	33,142.80	1	n/a	2,400	20,134.20	n/a	7,195
100	18	12	29,412.30	1	n/a	2,400	19,330.20	n/a	7,196
100	38	6	11,643.90	0	n/a	2,400	4,860.50	n/a	7,191
100	38	9	18,641.90	0	n/a	2,400	7,874.87	n/a	7,193
100	38	12	20,587.40	0	n/a	2,400	8,725.20	n/a	7,194
200	8	6	53,322.90	8	n/a	2,400	38,237.50	n/a	7,209
200	8	9	101,567.00	11	n/a	2,400	59,031.80	n/a	7,222
200	8	12	117,193.00	18	n/a	2,400	59,462.40	n/a	7,231
200	18	6	33,304.20	2	n/a	2,400	16,994.80	n/a	7,209
200	18	9	52,886.60	5	n/a	2,400	25,762.30	n/a	7,217
200	18	12	87,014.10	7	n/a	2,400	44,956.90	n/a	7,226
200	38	6	24,142.50	1	n/a	2,400	6,918.92	n/a	7,206
200	38	9	34,372.80	2	n/a	2,400	8,755.60	n/a	7,217
200	38	12	40,483.20	3	n/a	2,400	11,656.00	n/a	7,218

Table 3.13: Clustered node positioning and rural cost structure.

N	Q	T	Construction		Matheuristic		B&C		
			UB	Seconds	UB	Seconds	LB	UB	Seconds
10	8	6	7,378.79	0	5,974.75	1,800	5,970.01	5,970.59	16
10	8	9	26,506.30	0	19,177.50	1,800	19,155.10	19,162.40	7,200
10	8	12	16,663.70	0	9,957.34	1,800	9,879.11	9,887.20	7,200
10	18	6	3,034.10	0	2,008.91	1,800	2,006.73	2,008.91	7,200
10	18	9	7,101.85	0	5,378.35	1,800	5,348.75	5,363.36	7,200
10	18	12	11,167.30	0	10,039.70	1,800	10,001.00	10,007.00	7,200
10	38	6	4,065.59	0	2,396.66	1,800	2,334.55	2,396.66	7,200
10	38	9	10,382.00	0	6,595.08	1,800	6,569.73	6,579.44	7,200
10	38	12	5,132.08	0	3,274.09	1,800	3,207.78	3,245.02	7,200
25	8	6	45,732.00	0	36,479.54	1,800	35,983.70	36,031.90	7,200
25	8	9	46,746.30	0	36,989.90	1,800	35,091.30	35,133.30	7,200
25	8	12	75,355.40	0	56,066.15	1,800	53,010.90	53,398.70	7,200
25	18	6	11,162.70	0	8,121.86	1,800	7,486.21	7,544.34	7,200
25	18	9	24,357.60	0	22,772.79	1,800	19,759.70	19,845.30	7,199
25	18	12	45,552.70	0	40,399.06	1,800	38,486.70	38,807.80	7,198
25	38	6	13,505.20	0	10,233.00	1,800	9,875.91	9,939.82	7,198
25	38	9	12,521.80	0	8,444.52	1,800	8,189.84	8,389.26	7,198
25	38	12	18,705.50	0	13,598.35	1,800	11,983.20	12,125.40	7,198
50	8	6	44,692.20	0	n/a	2,400	32,347.70	n/a	7,193
50	8	9	110,306.00	0	n/a	2,400	83,448.80	n/a	7,192
50	8	12	184,403.00	0	n/a	2,400	117,340.00	175,306.00	7,196
50	18	6	36,146.50	0	n/a	2,400	23,041.80	n/a	7,195
50	18	9	45,238.80	0	n/a	2,400	32,299.30	n/a	7,190
50	18	12	79,602.80	0	n/a	2,400	62,552.50	n/a	7,192
50	38	6	23,797.20	0	n/a	2,400	11,096.80	13,255.00	7,195
50	38	9	27,925.80	0	n/a	2,400	17,947.50	n/a	7,192
50	38	12	54,763.90	0	n/a	2,400	35,803.60	n/a	7,191
100	8	6	141,390.00	1	n/a	2,400	108,073.00	n/a	7,194
100	8	9	258,958.00	1	n/a	2,400	169,036.00	n/a	7,195
100	8	12	348,544.00	2	n/a	2,400	222,959.00	n/a	7,196
100	18	6	93,699.70	0	n/a	2,400	58,222.20	n/a	7,191
100	18	9	117,709.00	0	n/a	2,400	84,778.20	n/a	7,195
100	18	12	149,969.00	1	n/a	2,400	110,995.00	n/a	7,195
100	38	6	50,587.00	0	n/a	2,400	20,827.90	n/a	7,192
100	38	9	113,412.00	0	n/a	2,400	63,231.70	n/a	7,192
100	38	12	137,057.00	0	n/a	2,400	49,841.50	n/a	7,195
200	8	6	272,759.00	7	n/a	2,400	188,649.00	n/a	7,214
200	8	9	417,595.00	11	n/a	2,400	252,938.00	n/a	7,218
200	8	12	575,146.00	18	n/a	2,400	296,848.00	n/a	7,229
200	18	6	148,659.00	3	n/a	2,400	81,160.80	n/a	7,210
200	18	9	178,887.00	4	n/a	2,400	120,529.00	n/a	7,220
200	18	12	220,543.00	8	n/a	2,400	112,696.00	n/a	7,225
200	38	6	108,826.00	1	n/a	2,400	26,556.60	n/a	7,212
200	38	9	165,433.00	2	n/a	2,400	26,911.30	n/a	7,216
200	38	12	192,580.00	3	n/a	2,400	53,081.60	n/a	7,217

Table 3.14: Clustered node positioning and urban cost structure

N	Q	T	Construction		Matheuristic		B&C		
			UB	Seconds	UB	Seconds	LB	UB	Seconds
10	8	6	7,378.79	0	5,974.75	1,800	5,970.01	5,970.59	16
10	8	9	26,506.30	0	19,177.50	1,800	19,155.10	19,162.40	7,200
10	8	12	16,663.70	0	9,957.34	1,800	9,879.11	9,887.20	7,200
10	18	6	3,034.10	0	2,008.91	1,800	2,006.73	2,008.91	7,200
10	18	9	7,101.85	0	5,378.35	1,800	5,348.75	5,363.36	7,200
10	18	12	11,167.30	0	10,039.70	1,800	10,001.00	10,007.00	7,200
10	38	6	4,065.59	0	2,396.66	1,800	2,334.55	2,396.66	7,200
10	38	9	10,382.00	0	6,595.08	1,800	6,569.73	6,579.44	7,200
10	38	12	5,132.08	0	3,274.09	1,800	3,207.78	3,245.02	7,200
25	8	6	45,732.00	0	36,479.54	1,800	35,983.70	36,031.90	7,200
25	8	9	46,746.30	0	36,989.90	1,800	35,091.30	35,133.30	7,200
25	8	12	75,355.40	0	56,066.15	1,800	53,010.90	53,398.70	7,200
25	18	6	11,162.70	0	8,121.86	1,800	7,486.21	7,544.34	7,200
25	18	9	24,357.60	0	22,772.79	1,800	19,759.70	19,845.30	7,199
25	18	12	45,552.70	0	40,399.06	1,800	38,486.70	38,807.80	7,198
25	38	6	13,505.20	0	10,233.00	1,800	9,875.91	9,939.82	7,198
25	38	9	12,521.80	0	8,444.52	1,800	8,189.84	8,389.26	7,198
25	38	12	18,705.50	0	13,598.35	1,800	11,983.20	12,125.40	7,198
50	8	6	44,692.20	0	n/a	2,400	32,347.70	n/a	7,193
50	8	9	110,306.00	0	n/a	2,400	83,448.80	n/a	7,192
50	8	12	184,403.00	0	n/a	2,400	117,340.00	175,306.00	7,196
50	18	6	36,146.50	0	n/a	2,400	23,041.80	n/a	7,195
50	18	9	45,238.80	0	n/a	2,400	32,299.30	n/a	7,190
50	18	12	79,602.80	0	n/a	2,400	62,552.50	n/a	7,192
50	38	6	23,797.20	0	n/a	2,400	11,096.80	13,255.00	7,195
50	38	9	27,925.80	0	n/a	2,400	17,947.50	n/a	7,192
50	38	12	54,763.90	0	n/a	2,400	35,803.60	n/a	7,191
100	8	6	141,390.00	1	n/a	2,400	108,073.00	n/a	7,194
100	8	9	258,958.00	1	n/a	2,400	169,036.00	n/a	7,195
100	8	12	348,544.00	2	n/a	2,400	222,959.00	n/a	7,196
100	18	6	93,699.70	0	n/a	2,400	58,222.20	n/a	7,191
100	18	9	117,709.00	0	n/a	2,400	84,778.20	n/a	7,195
100	18	12	149,969.00	1	n/a	2,400	110,995.00	n/a	7,195
100	38	6	50,587.00	0	n/a	2,400	20,827.90	n/a	7,192
100	38	9	113,412.00	0	n/a	2,400	63,231.70	n/a	7,192
100	38	12	137,057.00	0	n/a	2,400	49,841.50	n/a	7,195
200	8	6	272,759.00	7	n/a	2,400	188,649.00	n/a	7,214
200	8	9	417,595.00	11	n/a	2,400	252,938.00	n/a	7,218
200	8	12	575,146.00	18	n/a	2,400	296,848.00	n/a	7,229
200	18	6	148,659.00	3	n/a	2,400	81,160.80	n/a	7,210
200	18	9	178,887.00	4	n/a	2,400	120,529.00	n/a	7,220
200	18	12	220,543.00	8	n/a	2,400	112,696.00	n/a	7,225
200	38	6	108,826.00	1	n/a	2,400	26,556.60	n/a	7,212
200	38	9	165,433.00	2	n/a	2,400	26,911.30	n/a	7,216
200	38	12	192,580.00	3	n/a	2,400	53,081.60	n/a	7,217

Table 3.15: Random-clustered node positioning and rural area.

N	Q	T	Construction		Matheuristic		B&C		
			UB	Seconds	UB	Seconds	LB	UB	Seconds
10	8	6	14,746.00	0	10,773.70	1,800	10,762.00	10,763.10	96
10	8	9	19,977.10	0	15,627.00	1,800	15,613.10	15,614.50	45
10	8	12	35,659.60	0	25,085.60	1,800	24,873.20	25,054.50	7,200
10	18	6	5,847.09	0	3,907.04	1,800	3,895.65	3,896.01	29
10	18	9	11,346.40	0	8,317.24	1,800	8,224.23	8,238.37	7,200
10	18	12	13,658.70	0	12,196.21	1,800	12,143.80	12,157.90	7,200
10	38	6	6,531.75	0	3,519.75	1,800	3,516.06	3,516.38	39
10	38	9	5,375.90	0	2,789.97	1,800	2,744.25	2,786.52	7,200
10	38	12	8,660.96	0	4,977.98	1,800	4,953.73	4,956.09	7,200
25	8	6	39,952.40	0	34,477.90	1,800	31,545.30	31,573.30	7,199
25	8	9	48,728.30	0	40,879.19	1,800	38,927.00	38,956.40	7,199
25	8	12	67,835.20	0	48,196.47	1,800	44,421.30	45,072.10	7,200
25	18	6	18,837.20	0	14,086.27	1,800	12,809.30	13,015.70	7,199
25	18	9	47,348.10	0	36,437.21	1,800	31,439.10	32,128.90	7,199
25	18	12	25,956.60	0	25,724.00	1,800	20,560.50	20,691.10	7,198
25	38	6	11,935.00	0	5,909.60	1,800	5,371.96	5,665.70	7,199
25	38	9	20,617.00	0	13,019.36	1,800	11,234.00	11,747.40	7,199
25	38	12	26,483.50	0	14,865.39	1,800	11,957.70	12,412.10	7,199
50	8	6	50,984.10	0	n/a	2,400	40,202.50	42,396.10	7,199
50	8	9	112,998.00	0	n/a	2,400	89,475.10	94,072.70	7,195
50	8	12	201,268.00	0	n/a	2,400	129,804.00	186,777.00	7,189
50	18	6	36,566.20	0	n/a	2,400	24,173.70	30,263.80	7,194
50	18	9	79,805.40	0	n/a	2,400	67,172.60	n/a	7,192
50	18	12	102,798.00	0	n/a	2,400	81,865.20	n/a	7,193
50	38	6	26,320.50	0	n/a	2,400	12,590.50	n/a	7,194
50	38	9	55,307.10	0	n/a	2,400	18,657.80	25,312.40	7,191
50	38	12	51,830.00	0	n/a	2,400	21,724.00	n/a	7,192
100	8	6	115,596.00	1	n/a	2,400	90,296.80	n/a	7,195
100	8	9	171,176.00	1	n/a	2,400	116,568.00	170,638.00	7,197
100	8	12	232,299.00	2	n/a	2,400	152,972.00	215,387.00	7,198
100	18	6	83,117.20	0	n/a	2,400	50,908.10	n/a	7,192
100	18	9	137,352.00	0	n/a	2,400	93,443.60	n/a	7,191
100	18	12	170,774.00	1	n/a	2,400	111,287.00	n/a	7,193
100	38	6	47,831.70	0	n/a	2,400	18,874.10	n/a	7,192
100	38	9	96,818.10	1	n/a	2,400	24,790.00	166,749.00	7,194
100	38	12	118,733.00	0	n/a	2,400	41,977.30	n/a	7,194
200	8	6	239,608.00	7	n/a	2,400	173,200.00	n/a	7,208
200	8	9	274,577.00	12	n/a	2,400	156,459.00	n/a	7,221
200	8	12	659,002.00	18	n/a	2,400	375,560.00	n/a	7,230
200	18	6	161,923.00	4	n/a	2,400	67,216.70	n/a	7,211
200	18	9	263,219.00	8	n/a	2,400	145,809.00	n/a	7,216
200	18	12	251,454.00	9	n/a	2,400	94,148.20	n/a	7,225
200	38	6	108,641.00	1	n/a	2,400	30,227.20	n/a	7,208
200	38	9	158,884.00	2	n/a	2,400	31,767.40	n/a	7,212
200	38	12	188,558.00	2	n/a	2,400	n/a	n/a	7,224

Table 3.16: Random-clustered node positioning and urban area.

N	Q	T	Construction		Matheuristic		B&C		
			UB	Seconds	UB	Seconds	LB	UB	Seconds
10	8	6	1,507.98	0	1,208.53	1,800	1,203.28	1,203.40	1,267
10	8	9	5,979.09	0	5,064.45	1,800	5,040.68	5,040.75	20
10	8	12	2,958.27	0	1,484.66	1,800	1,456.79	1,459.00	7,200
10	18	6	2,026.22	0	1,253.13	1,800	1,237.02	1,239.60	7,200
10	18	9	1,835.79	0	1,520.50	1,800	1,474.35	1,486.45	7,200
10	18	12	4,064.09	0	3,001.28	1,800	2,874.87	2,885.74	7,200
10	38	6	1,396.33	0	851.73	818	851.66	851.73	31
10	38	9	1,364.44	0	750.02	1,800	742.18	748.12	7,200
10	38	12	1,970.40	0	1,162.62	1,800	1,095.75	1,143.27	7,200
25	8	6	7,881.24	0	6,916.03	1,800	6,083.32	6,090.56	7,200
25	8	9	9,582.61	0	6,966.52	1,800	5,796.21	5,900.69	7,199
25	8	12	8,743.74	0	5,623.77	1,800	5,081.56	5,158.15	7,200
25	18	6	4,008.62	0	3,145.32	1,800	2,734.26	2,848.64	7,199
25	18	9	4,853.19	0	3,736.42	1,800	3,253.77	3,331.08	7,198
25	18	12	9,535.76	0	8,820.58	1,800	7,577.99	7,842.27	7,199
25	38	6	2,480.00	0	1,501.74	1,800	1,356.69	1,391.07	7,200
25	38	9	4,664.00	0	3,231.86	1,800	2,815.71	2,899.55	7,199
25	38	12	3,401.56	0	2,111.68	1,800	1,749.59	1,831.33	7,199
50	8	6	14,865.10	0	n/a	2,400	11,296.50	12,546.20	7,197
50	8	9	20,473.10	0	n/a	2,400	13,166.30	19,658.10	7,193
50	8	12	31,809.10	0	n/a	2,400	21,075.70	30,221.80	7,193
50	18	6	8,856.05	0	n/a	2,400	5,571.00	n/a	7,195
50	18	9	14,832.60	0	n/a	2,400	9,488.87	19,145.80	7,192
50	18	12	11,391.40	0	n/a	2,400	9,553.21	n/a	7,189
50	38	6	6,571.21	0	n/a	2,400	3,558.33	4,416.37	7,196
50	38	9	9,889.73	0	n/a	2,400	4,783.31	n/a	7,193
50	38	12	10,968.90	0	n/a	2,400	6,577.93	n/a	7,191
100	8	6	27,094.80	1	n/a	2,400	18,362.60	n/a	7,193
100	8	9	47,738.90	1	n/a	2,400	34,366.50	n/a	7,196
100	8	12	54,547.80	2	n/a	2,400	34,542.80	n/a	7,196
100	18	6	19,644.60	0	n/a	2,400	11,673.90	n/a	7,193
100	18	9	22,151.20	0	n/a	2,400	15,039.10	n/a	7,197
100	18	12	41,255.70	1	n/a	2,400	29,504.90	n/a	7,194
100	38	6	29,838.00	1	n/a	2,400	5,701.85	35,035.90	7,194
100	38	9	17,568.80	0	n/a	2,400	7,784.86	n/a	7,193
100	38	12	25,214.40	0	n/a	2,400	11,719.40	n/a	7,195
200	8	6	67,897.60	7	n/a	2,400	50,067.60	n/a	7,211
200	8	9	81,475.30	12	n/a	2,400	52,485.00	n/a	7,218
200	8	12	117,634.00	18	n/a	2,400	61,796.00	n/a	7,231
200	18	6	29,050.60	2	n/a	2,400	14,342.20	n/a	7,210
200	18	9	38,011.90	5	n/a	2,400	19,778.40	n/a	7,219
200	18	12	40,045.00	18	n/a	2,400	20,321.40	n/a	7,228
200	38	6	26,596.30	1	n/a	2,400	7,878.25	n/a	7,208
200	38	9	36,289.10	2	n/a	2,400	10,530.10	n/a	7,217
200	38	12	48,586.90	3	n/a	2,400	13,074.40	n/a	7,230

Chapter 4

Experimental evaluation of using different mathematical formulations in a matheuristic for the production routing problem

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Mohamed Ben Ahmed Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway mohamed.ben.ahmed@himolde.no

Lars Magnus Hvattum Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway Lars.M.Hvattum@himolde.no

Agostinho Agra DMat and CIDMA, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal aagra@ua.pt

Abstract

We perform an experimental study to evaluate the performance of a matheuristic for the production routing problem (PRP). First, we develop a basic matheuristic that prescribes starting from a partial initial solution, completing it using a sequence of constructive heuristics, and improving it using a general-purpose mixed-integer programming heuristic. Next, we investigate the effect of three state-of-the-art mathematical formulations on the proposed matheuristic convergence. The formulations are implemented and tested with and without the use of valid inequalities. In addition, by suggesting different techniques to generate a feasible starting solution for our matheuristic, we assess the contribution of an initial solution to the matheuristic's overall performance. We conduct extensive computational experiments on benchmark data instances for the PRP. The results show that a proper choice of an embedded mathematical formulation depends on the data instances' features, such as the number of customers and the length of the planning horizon. The comparisons undertaken in this study contradict the common findings on the importance of selecting a good initial solution, as having a better initial solution does not necessarily lead to finding a better final solution.

Keywords: Lot sizing, Inventory routing, Mixed integer formulation, Valid inequality, Proximity search, Experimental analysis

4.1 Introduction

This study investigates the production routing problem (PRP) with a discrete and finite time horizon. The problem combines three famous subproblems from the literature: lot-sizing, vehicle routing, and inventory management problems. Contributions dealing with the PRP appeared in the mid-1990 when Chandra [12] and Chandra and Fisher [13] successfully combined production and distribution decisions. However, the problem remained widely unexplored until mid-2010s, when the interest in it gained momentum, perhaps in connection to the growing application of vendor-managed inventory (VMI) policies in the business. This interest is demonstrated by the surging number of its solution methods, which are often disparate. We differentiate between (i) exact algorithms, (ii) heuristic algorithms, and (iii) the hybridization of heuristic and exact algorithms, yielding the so-called matheuristic algorithms. For a comprehensive review on solution methods for the PRP, we refer the readers to Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [2], Díaz-Madroño, Peidro, and Mula [17]. Hrabec, Hvattum, and Hoff [23] also reviewed some pertinent contributions to the PRP and showed that solving a PRP is better than solving sequential problems if the optimality gap of the integrated problem is below a certain threshold (11%).

Matheuristics, which are reputable for obtaining high-quality solutions, have recently come under the spotlight. For example, Russell [35] developed a matheuristic that involves the solution of a relaxed version

of a mixed-integer program (MIP) to derive lot-sizing decisions, followed by the use of a vehicle routing algorithm to determine final routes. Avci and Yildiz [7] proposed a matheuristic that decomposes the problem into a sequence of subproblems. Distribution and routing subproblems are solved heuristically, while a mathematical model is used to derive the lot-sizing, inventory, and delivery quantity decisions. Chitsaz, Cordeau, and Jans [14] proposed a three-phase matheuristic for the joint assembly, production, and inventory routing problem. The first phase determines a setup schedule, while the second phase optimizes production quantities, supplier visit schedules, and shipment quantities. The third phase solves a vehicle routing problem for each period in the planning horizon. Recently, Manousakis et al. [29] designed an efficient matheuristic for solving the PRP. The crux is that exploring both feasible and infeasible solution spaces with a local search can lead to improved PRP solutions. The matheuristic employs mathematical models to restore feasibility and improve incumbent solutions. Mousavi, Bashiri, and Nikzad [31] proposed a matheuristic for solving the stochastic PRP with perishable products. It breaks down the problem into five subproblems, where the solution to one subproblem is conveyed to the following one. Other approaches that go in line with the aforementioned contributions can be found in Miranda et al. [30], Neves-Moreira et al. [32], and Avci and Yildiz [6].

The applications of matheuristics are not solely limited to the context of the PRP, and matheuristics have been implemented to solve other routing problems as documented by Doerner and Schmid [18] and Archetti and Speranza [5]. Other surveys on matheuristics are presented by Blum et al. [10], Hanafi and Todosijević [21], and Boschetti and Maniezzo [11]. In the vast majority of these contributions, the design of matheuristics is involved in a manual, experimental approach guided by the algorithm designers' experience and the exploitation of problem-specific knowledge. The developed matheuristics are ad-hoc and do not necessarily provide an understanding of how a combination of MP-based exact methods and heuristic search techniques can best improve algorithmic performance [10]. Besides, a deeper understanding of the performance of mathematical components is lacking, which would eventually provide, if it exists, insights into the optimal configuration of matheuristics for the PRP. Finally, one needs to further investigate the sensitivity of matheuristics to the initial solution. While hypothetically, an excellent initial solution can improve the performance of a matheuristic, it may be, in some cases, challenging to improve, resulting in higher execution times.

This paper's main contribution is to design a novel matheuristic for the PRP and evaluate its performance under different mathematical formulations. The matheuristic incorporates three phases. The first phase is a mixed-integer programming (MIP) relaxation of the entire problem where only the integrality of lot-sizing decisions is maintained. In the second phase, we develop a sequence of construction heuristics to determine the distribution and the routing decisions, thus yielding a complete initial solution. The last phase uses a general-purpose MIP heuristic that iteratively attempts to improve the given solution. Three mathematical formulations are developed and tested within the matheuristic framework, namely: (1) a four-index vehicle flow formulation, (2) a three-index vehicle flow formulation, and (3) a two-commodity flow formulation. The first formulation uses integer variables associated with each pair of nodes to count the number of times a vehicle travels between them. In the second formulation, these variables are aggregated over all vehicles. The third formulation defines two continuous flow variables for each pair of nodes representing the vehicle's total load and empty space while traversing these two nodes, respectively. These formulations are tested with and without using valid inequalities to assess the impact of these inequalities on the algorithm's overall performance. Furthermore, by allowing for different techniques to generate a feasible starting solution for our matheuristic, we aim to measure the contribution of an initial solution to the matheuristic's overall performance. Detailed experimental analyses follow our study, and we apply several metrics to evaluate the matheuristic components' performance.

To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies in the existing literature that adopted a similar experimental methodology where the study of models is done while embedded in the matheuristics. A handful of similar contributions appeared concerning the design of metaheuristics. For example, Hemmati et al. [22] investigated the importance of randomization in adaptive large neighborhood search when solving maritime pickup and delivery problems, whereas Sousa et al. [36] evaluated the importance of initial solution algorithms in simulated annealing when solving energy resource scheduling problems.

We are not aware of existing studies that compare PRP formulations with respect to their role in heuristic search. However, one can find insightful contributions in the literature about the quality of linear programming (LP) relaxations of different formulations for the inventory routing problem [4] and the multi-depot routing problem [8], as well as the performance of flow formulations for the capacitated location-routing problem when used in a branch-and-cut framework [16].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 4.2, we introduce the formal definition of the PRP and some useful notation used in the following sections. In Section 4.3 we introduce different formulations for the PRP. The details of the matheuristic framework are presented in Section 4.4. This

is followed by a description of the experimental setup and the tests performed in Section 4.5 and some concluding remarks in Section 4.6.

4.2 Problem description

The PRP can be defined on a complete undirected graph $G = (N, E)$ where $N = N^C \cup \{0\}$ is the set of nodes, N^C is the subset of customers nodes, node 0 represents the plant facility, and $E = \{(i, j) : i, j \in N, i < j\}$ is the set of edges. We define the set $T = \{1, \dots, H\}$ of time periods. With each edge $(i, j) \in E$ is associated a routing cost c_{ij} . A fleet of m identical vehicles is made available in each period $t \in T$, and every vehicle has a transportation capacity of Q units. For each node $i \in N^C$ and time period $t \in T$, let d_{it} denote the demand of customer i in period t . For each node $i \in N$, a starting inventory level I_{i0} and a maximum inventory level L_i are given. We denote by h_i the inventory holding cost at node $i \in N$. The setup cost at the plant and the variable production cost are represented by s and u , respectively. The production capacity at the plant facility is given by C . Hence, the PRP aims at determining a production and a distribution plan such that:

- Production capacity at the plant facility is respected.
- Vehicle capacities and inventory capacities at both customers and the production plant are satisfied.
- Stock-out at customers are not allowed.
- Backlog of demand is not allowed.
- Each customer is visited at most once in each time period.
- Vehicle routes start and end at the plant in each time period.
- The total cost, given by the sum of the setup cost at the plant, the variable production cost, the inventory holding cost at the customers and the plant, plus the routing costs, is minimized.

We define the following additional notation. Let $\Delta(S) = \{(i, j) \in E : i \in S, j \notin S \text{ or } i \notin S, j \in S\}$ be the set of edges incident to a node set S (for simplicity, we write $\Delta(i)$ to represent the set of edges incident to $i \in N$). Let $E(S)$ the set of edges $(i, j) \in E$, such that $i, j \in S$, where $S \subseteq N$.

4.3 Multi-vehicle formulations for the PRP

This section introduces three state of the art mathematical formulations of the generic PRP version: a four-index vehicle flow formulation, a three-index vehicle flow formulation, and a two-commodity flow formulation.

4.3.1 A four-index vehicle flow formulation

In the four-index vehicle flow formulation, originally presented by Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1], we define for every time period $t \in T$ the binary decision variable x_{ijtk} that assumes value 1 if and only if a vehicle $k \in K$ travels directly between nodes $i, j \in N$. We also define z_{ikt} as a binary variable taking the value 1 if node i is visited by vehicle $k \in K$ in period $t \in T$. In addition, I_{it} is a continuous decision variable corresponding to the inventory level of node $i \in N$ at the end of time period $t \in T$, while q_{itk} represents the quantity delivered to customer $i \in N^C$ by means of vehicle $k \in K$ in period $t \in T$. Finally, let y_t be the binary setup variable, and p_t the continuous production level variable, both defined for each time period $t \in T$. With these decision variables, the four-index vehicle flow formulation of the PRP, henceforth called FIVF, is given by:

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(up_t + sy_t + \sum_{i \in N} h_i I_{it} + \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \sum_{k \in K} c_{ij} x_{ijtk} \right), \quad (1.1)$$

subject to

$$I_{0,t-1} + p_t = \sum_{i \in N^C} \sum_{k \in K} q_{ikt} + I_{0t}, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.2)$$

$$I_{i,t-1} + \sum_{k \in K} q_{ikt} = d_{it} + I_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.3)$$

$$p_t \leq \min \left\{ C, \sum_{i \in N^C} \sum_{l=t}^H d_{il} \right\} y_t, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.4)$$

$$I_{0t} \leq L_0, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.5)$$

$$I_{i,t-1} + \sum_{k \in K} q_{ikt} \leq L_i, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.6)$$

$$\sum_{i \in N^C} q_{ikt} \leq Qz_{0kt}, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.7)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K} z_{ikt} \leq 1, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.8)$$

$$q_{ikt} \leq \min \left\{ L_i, Q, \sum_{l=t}^H d_{il} \right\} z_{ikt}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.9)$$

$$\sum_{j:(i,j) \in E} x_{ijkt} = 2z_{ikt}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.10)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E(S)} x_{ijkt} \leq \sum_{i \in S} z_{ikt} - z_{ekt}, \quad S \subseteq N^C, \quad e \in S, \quad |S| \geq 2, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.11)$$

$$z_{0kt} \geq z_{0,k+1,t}, \quad 1 \leq k \leq m-1, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.12)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^j 2^{(j-i)} z_{ikt} \geq \sum_{i=1}^j 2^{(j-1)} z_{i,k+1,t}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.13)$$

$$p_t, I_{it}, q_{ikt} \geq 0, \quad i \in N, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.14)$$

$$y_t, z_{ikt} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in N, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.15)$$

$$x_{ijkt} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (i, j) \in E : i \in N^C, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (1.16)$$

$$x_{0jkt} \in \{0, 1, 2\}, \quad j \in N^C, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T. \quad (1.17)$$

The objective function (1.1) calls for the minimization of the total operational costs, that is, the sum of the setup costs, the unit production costs, the transportation costs, and the inventory holding costs at both the plant facility and the customers. Constraints (1.2)–(1.3) define the inventory level at the production plant and at the customers, respectively. If production occurs at a specific time period $t \in T$, then a setup cost is incurred at the production facility and is forced via constraints (1.4). The produced quantity cannot surpass the production capacity neither the total demand in the remaining time periods. Constraints (1.5)–(1.6) ensure that the inventory quantities at the plant and the customers, respectively, do not exceed their capacities at the end of each period. Constraints (1.7) are vehicle capacity constraints. Constraints (1.8) allow each customer to be visited at most once during each time period. If there is a positive delivery to a node, then a visit is forced by constraints (1.9). Constraints (1.10) are the degree constraints of customers; they require the number of edges incident to each node to be equal to 2 if it is visited or 0 otherwise. Constraints (1.11) are the subtour elimination constraints (SEC) for each vehicle route and each period. Constraints (1.12)–(1.13) are symmetry breaking constraints. Finally, constraints (1.14)–(1.17) define the domains of the variables.

The SECs are dynamically generated in each node of the branch-and-bound tree. Their separation amounts to the solution of the classical min-cut problem presented in Padberg and Rinaldi [33]. Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] also strengthen the formulation (1.1)–(1.17) using several valid inequalities. They are valid for the multivehicle PRP with capacitated production, and they are described in Appendix A.1. The tighter formulation is, henceforth, referred to by FIVF-VI.

4.3.2 A three-index vehicle flow formulation

The previous formulation has the drawback that the number of variables grows in proportion to the number of vehicles. Alternatively, one can express the routing constraints with variables that do not

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comprise a vehicle index, in a similar manner to Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1]. The formulation is written using the variables q , z , and x with the same notation, but the vehicle index k is dropped. The only exception is that variable z_{0t} , which is changed to be an integer variable representing the number of vehicles leaving the plant in period $t \in T$. Below, the three-index vehicle flow formulation is provided, henceforward named TIVF:

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(up_t + sy_t + \sum_{i \in N} h_i I_{it} + \sum_{(i,j) \in E} c_{ij} x_{ijt} \right) \quad (2.1)$$

subject to (1.5)–(1.6) and

$$I_{0,t-1} + p_t = \sum_{i \in N^C} q_{it} + I_{0t}, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.2)$$

$$I_{i,t-1} + q_{it} = d_{it} + I_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.3)$$

$$p_t \leq \min \left\{ C, \sum_{i \in N^C} \sum_{l=t}^H d_{il} \right\} y_t, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.4)$$

$$I_{0t} \leq L_0, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.5)$$

$$I_{i,t-1} + q_{it} \leq L_i, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.6)$$

$$q_{it} \leq \min \left\{ L_i, Q, \sum_{l=t}^H d_{il} \right\} z_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.7)$$

$$\sum_{j:(i,j) \in E} x_{ijt} = 2z_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.8)$$

$$z_{0t} \leq m, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.9)$$

$$Q \sum_{(i,j) \in E(S)} x_{ijt} \leq \sum_{i \in S} (Qz_{it} - q_{it}), \quad S \subseteq N^C, \quad |S| \geq 2, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.10)$$

$$p_t, I_{it}, q_{it} \geq 0, \quad i \in N, \quad t \in T. \quad (2.11)$$

$$y_t, z_{it} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.12)$$

$$z_{0t} \in \mathbb{Z}^+, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.13)$$

$$x_{ijt} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (i, j) \in E : i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (2.14)$$

$$x_{0jt} \in \{0, 1, 2\}, \quad j \in N^C, \quad t \in T. \quad (2.15)$$

Constraints (2.2)–(2.8) are similar to (1.2)–(1.3), (1.6), and (1.9)–(1.10), respectively. Constraints (2.9) limit the number of vehicles leaving the production facility to the number of available vehicles in each period. Constraints (2.14) are the subtour elimination and vehicle capacity constraints. They have a form similar to the generalized fractional subtour elimination constraints (GFSEC) for the vehicle routing problem, and they are separated using the four heuristic separation algorithm presented by Lysgaard, Letchford, and Eglese [27]. Besides, the model can be further strengthened by adding valid inequalities. We describe in Appendix 1.2 the valid inequalities associated with the TIVF formulation. The tighter formulation is, henceforward, called TIVF-VI.

4.3.3 A two-commodity flow formulation

The third formulation for solving the basic variant of the PRP is based on the two-commodity flow formulation introduced by Manousakis et al. [29]. The formulation requires an extended graph $G' = (N', E')$ obtained from G by adding the artificial node $n + 1$, duplicating the production facility. Vehicle paths now start from vertex 0 and end at vertex $n + 1$. The formulation is written using the variables q , z , and x with the same notation, but the vehicle index k is dropped. In addition, two continuous flow variables f_{ijt} and f_{jit} are introduced for each edge $(i, j) \in E'$ and they represent the load and the residual capacity of the vehicle traveling from i to j at time $t \in T$, respectively. More specifically, for any route of a feasible solution, the flow variables define two directed paths, one from node 0 to $n + 1$, whose variables represent the vehicle load, and another from node $n + 1$ to 0, whose variables represent the residual capacity of the vehicle. The two-commodity flow formulation is as follows, henceforward referred to as *TCF*:

$$\min \sum_{t \in T} \left(up_t + sy_t + \sum_{i \in N'} h_i I_{it} + \sum_{(i,j) \in E'} c_{ij} x_{ijt} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

subject to (2.2)–(2.7) and

$$p_t \leq \sum_{i \in N^C} \left(\sum_{l=t}^H d_{il} - I_{i,t-1} \right) - I_{0,t-1}, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\sum_{j: (i,j) \in E} x_{ijt} = 2z_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\sum_{i \in N^C} x_{0it} \leq m, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.4)$$

$$\sum_{j \in N^C} x_{0jt} = \sum_{i \in N^C} x_{i,n+1,t}, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.5)$$

$$f_{ijt} + f_{jit} = Qx_{ijt}, \quad i, j \in N', \quad i < j, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.6)$$

$$\sum_{j \in N, i \neq j} f_{ijt} = Qz_{it} - q_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.7)$$

$$\sum_{j \in N^C} f_{0jt} = \sum_{i \in N^C} q_{it}, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\sum_{i \in N^C} f_{i,n+1,t} = 0, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.9)$$

$$p_t, I_{it}, q_{it} \geq 0, \quad i \in N', \quad t \in T. \quad (3.10)$$

$$y_t, z_{it} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.11)$$

$$f_{ijt} \geq 0, \quad i, j \in N', \quad i \neq j, \quad t \in T, \quad (3.12)$$

$$x_{ijt} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (i, j) \in E', \quad t \in T. \quad (3.13)$$

The objective function (3.1) minimizes the total production, setup, inventory, and routing costs. Constraints (3.2) ensure that the produced quantities together with the remaining plant facility inventory at any time period $t \in T$ cannot exceed the actual customers' stocks. These constraints serve to further tighten the formulation, and they were presented in the previous formulations. Constraints (3.3) are the degree constraints for the customers. Constraints (3.4) ensure that the number of vehicles leaving the plant facility are equal to those returning to it, and their number should not exceed the fleet size as defined by constraints (3.5). Constraints (3.6) define the relationship between vehicle flow and commodity flow variables. Constraints (3.7) and (3.8) impose the correct values for the commodity flow variables incident to the plant facility vertices. Finally, constraints (3.9)–(3.13) set the domains and the integrality of the decision variables. For completeness, we describe the valid inequalities associated with the TCF formulation in Appendix 1.3, and which were originally presented by Manousakis et al. [29]. The tighter formulation is, henceforth, referred to by TCF-VI.

4.4 Solution method

To solve the PRP, we propose a matheuristic that is composed of three phases: an initialization phase, a completion phase, and an improvement phase. In Phase I, we run a MIP relaxation of the PRP. Phase II takes as an input the partial solution obtained from the previous stage and completes it using a sequence of heuristics. Once a complete solution is obtained, a weighted proximity search algorithm is invoked in Phase III to improve the incumbent solution. In the following, we describe each phase in detail. The outline of the overall matheuristic is displayed in Figure 5.1.

4.4.1 Initialization phase

In Phase I, we decide when to produce and how much to produce by solving a relaxation of the PRP model. Only the integrality of the production variables is retained, while the subtour elimination constraints are removed from the formulation. Note that maintaining the routing and distribution requirements in a

Figure 4.1: Matheuristic for the production routing problem.

relaxed form ensures that there can exist a feasible compatible solution to the y -variables (in terms of vehicle capacities and stock-out at customers); however, it does not ensure that deliveries do not split. This follows from the facts that the q -variables satisfy the vehicle capacity, the maximum level inventory policy requirements, and the constraints that disallow stock-outs. The optimal value of the relaxed model yields a lower bound on the original model's optimal value.

4.4.2 Completion phase

At this stage, decisions about visit times, customers' assignment to vehicles, and vehicle routes must be determined to obtain a complete solution to the PRP. These decisions are made by solving a sequence of heuristics. The obtained solution may be infeasible in terms of vehicle capacity and stock-out constraints at the production plant. However, it can be used to initialize Phase III even if it is infeasible. We hence proceed as follows:

1. Assign customer to time periods and set the quantities to be delivered to each customer in each time period using a construction heuristic, that we refer to as the customer urgency heuristic.
2. Assign customers to vehicles by applying a modified version of the first fit decreasing bin packing algorithm [24].
3. Determine the route of each vehicle on each day by solving a TSP on the subset of customers visited by each vehicle and using the Lin-Kernighan algorithm [26].

The customer urgency heuristic is a merge-and-round heuristic that iterates over the set of fractional z -variables. Any *fractional* visit (given by a fractional value of z) is shifted to the next one in time, and both deliveries are merged. If this operation induces stock-outs at customer inventories, then the rounding is performed in the opposite direction. If a merge can not be performed, or no other fractional value of z exists, the heuristic will round up the fractional visit to 1. Algorithm 3 describes the main steps of the customer urgency heuristic. The modified next fit decreasing algorithm assigns customer deliveries, ordered from the largest to the smallest, to vehicles. If a delivery fits none of the available vehicles, then it is assigned to the one with the largest residual capacity. Algorithm 4 describes the bin-packing algorithm.

Since the values of the z -variables in Phase I can be fractional, we cannot ensure deliveries do not split; thus, violations may occur concerning vehicle capacities and stock-outs at the production plant. We allow for an infeasible starting solution; however, we propose later a procedure to recover vehicles and the plant infeasibilities.

Algorithm 3: Customer urgency heuristic.

```

1 for  $t \leftarrow 1$  to  $H$  do
2   for  $i \in N^C$  do
3     Define  $r_{it} = I_{i,t-1}/d_{it}$ , the urgency ratio
4   end
5   Let  $\mathcal{N}_t^{UC} := \{i \in N^C : r_{it} < 1 \text{ and } 0 < z_{it} < 1\}$ 
6   Sort  $\mathcal{N}_t^{UC}$  by  $\downarrow r_{it}$ 
7   for  $i \in \mathcal{N}_t^{UC}$  do
8     Let  $t_i^* \leftarrow$  next fractional visit of customer  $i$ 
9     if  $\langle \text{Feasibility condition} \rangle$  then
10       $q_{it} \leftarrow q_{it} + q_{i,t_i^*}$ 
11       $I_{st} \leftarrow I_{st} + q_{i,t_i^*}, \quad s = t, \dots, t_i^* - 1$ 
12       $z_{it} \leftarrow 1, \quad z_{i,t_i^*} \leftarrow 0, \quad q_{i,t_i^*} \leftarrow 0$ 
13    end
14  end
15  Let  $\mathcal{N}_t^{NUC} := \{i \in N^C : r_{it} \geq 1 \text{ and } 0 < z_{it} < 1\}$ 
16  Sort  $\mathcal{N}_t^{NUC}$  by  $\uparrow r_{it}$ 
17  for  $i \in \mathcal{N}_t^{NUC}$  do
18    Let  $t_i^* \leftarrow$  next fractional visit for customer  $i$ 
19    if  $\langle \text{Feasibility condition} \rangle$  then
20       $q_{i,t_i^*} \leftarrow q_{i,t_i^*} + q_{it}$ 
21       $I_{st} \leftarrow I_{st} - q_{it}, \quad s = t, \dots, t_i^* - 1$ 
22       $z_{it} \leftarrow 0, \quad z_{i,t_i^*} \leftarrow 1, \quad q_{it} \leftarrow 0$ 
23    end
24  end
25 end
26 Round to 1 all remaining fractional  $z$ -values (if exist).
```

Remark 4.4.1. The feasibility condition introduced in lines 9 and 19 in Algorithm 3 is given by:

$$I_{it} + q_{i,t_i^*} \leq L_i, \quad t \in T, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_t^{UC}, \quad t_i^* \in T, \quad t_i^* > t,$$

$$I_{is} - q_{it} \geq 0, \quad t \in T, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_t^{NUC}, \quad t_i^* \in T, \quad t_i^* > t, \quad s = t, \dots, t_i^* - 1.$$

It ensures that customers' inventory levels remain within the preset limits.

4.4.3 Improvement phase

The improvement phase includes a weighted proximity search (WPS) algorithm and a feasibility recovery procedure. The latter is invoked only if the starting solution is infeasible, and it works by eliminating violations of vehicle capacities and stock-outs at the production plant. Both components are described below.

4.4.3.1 Weighted proximity search

The improvement phase is based on the WPS algorithm [34], which is adapted from the classic proximity search proposed by Fischetti and Monaci [20]. The WPS aims to improve a given solution to the PRP, referred to as $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$, by looking within the search space for an improved solution with a fixed minimum amount. This can be done by replacing the problem's original objective function with a Hamming distance function centered on the given solution. The new objective function, henceforth called the proximity function, is defined by:

4. Experimental evaluation of using different mathematical formulations in a matheuristic for the production routing problem

Algorithm 4: A modified next fit decreasing bin packing algorithm.

```

1 for  $t \leftarrow 1$  to  $H$  do
2   Let  $N_t$  the set of customer to be served on time period  $t$ 
3   Sort elements of  $N_t$  by  $\downarrow q_{it}$ 
4   Let  $\mathcal{K} = \emptyset$  the set of bins used so far
5   for  $i \in N_t$  do
6     for  $k \leftarrow 1$  to  $|\mathcal{K}|$  do
7       Let  $\sigma_k$  the residual capacity of bin  $k$ 
8       if  $\sigma_k \geq q_{it}$  then
9         Assign customer  $i$  to bin  $k$ 
10         $\sigma_k \leftarrow \sigma_k - q_{it}$ 
11        break
12      end
13    end
14    if  $k = |\mathcal{K}|$  and  $|\mathcal{K}| < m$  then
15       $|\mathcal{K}| \leftarrow |\mathcal{K}| + 1$ 
16      Assign customer  $i$  to bin  $|\mathcal{K}|$ 
17       $\sigma_{|\mathcal{K}|} \leftarrow Q - q_{it}$ 
18    else
19      Let  $k^*$  be the bin with highest residual capacity
20      Assign customer  $i$  to bin  $k^*$  even it violates the capacity
21       $\sigma_{k^*} \leftarrow \sigma_{k^*} - q_{it}$ 
22    end
23  end
24 end

```

$$\Delta_w^x(x, \bar{x}) := \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{(i,j) \in E | \bar{x}_{ijt}=0} w_{ijt}^x x_{ijt} + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{(i,j) \in E | \bar{x}_{ijt}=1} w_{ijt}^x (1 - x_{ijt}), \quad (4.1)$$

$$\Delta_w^y(y, \bar{y}) := \sum_{t \in T | \bar{y}_t=0} w_t^y y_t + \sum_{t \in T | \bar{y}_t=1} w_t^y (1 - y_t), \quad (4.2)$$

$$\Delta_w^z(z, \bar{z}) := \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{i \in N^C | \bar{z}_{it}=0} w_{it}^z z_{it} + \sum_{t \in T} \sum_{i \in N^C | \bar{z}_{it}=1} w_{it}^z (1 - z_{it}), \quad (4.3)$$

$$\min \Delta_w := \Delta_w^x(x, \bar{x}) + \Delta_w^y(y, \bar{y}) + \Delta_w^z(z, \bar{z}). \quad (4.4)$$

where $w_{ijt}^x \in \mathbb{R}$ represent the weights of variables x_{ijt} , $(i, j) \in E, t \in T$, $w_t^y \in \mathbb{R}$ the weights of variables $y_t, t \in T$, and $w_{it}^z \in \mathbb{R}$ the weights of variables $z_{it}, i \in N^C, t \in T$, respectively. These weights intend to capture information about which variables are more promising to change to find an improved solution. Therefore, given a feasible solution, higher weights should be assigned to the less promising variables to change, while lower weights should be associated with the more promising variables to change.

Hence, by using the weighted Hamming distance function (4.4), the WPS can be described as follows. We start with the initial solution, obtained from Phase II. Then, at each iteration, the cutoff constraint:

$$f(x, y, z) \leq f(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}) - \theta \quad (4.5)$$

(depending on a given cutoff tolerance value $\theta > 0$) is added to the MIP problem, the objective function is replaced by the Hamming distance function (4.4), and the resulting model is solved using a MIP solver. The obtained solution is then used to recenter the Hamming distance function and define the new cutoff constraint, and the process is repeated until a given stopping criterion is reached. Algorithm 6 describes the steps of the WPS.

4.4.3.2 Feasibility recovery procedure

The feasibility recovery procedure is based on the idea that the WPS (see Section 4.4.3.1) can be extended to eliminate violations of vehicle capacities and stock-outs constraints at the plant. This is done by

Algorithm 5: The weighted proximity search algorithm

```

1 Let  $(x^0, y^0, z^0)$  be an initial feasible solution.
2 Set  $(\bar{x}) := (x^0)$ ,  $(\bar{y}) := (y^0)$ , and  $(\bar{z}) := (z^0)$ ,
3 repeat
4   add the cutoff constraint (4.5) to the MIP problem
5   replace the original objective function by the Hamming distance function (4.4), and add
   flaligns (4.1)–(4.3) to the model
6   run the MIP solver on the modified problem
7   if a new feasible solution  $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$  is found then
8     recenter  $\Delta_w$  at the new solution  $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ 
9     update weights' calculations
10  else
11    go to (12)
12  end
13  update  $\theta$  (facultative)
14 until until a termination criteria is reached;
15 return  $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ 

```

identifying in the incumbent solution customers and vehicles yielding an infeasibility and adding a cut-off constraint to the WPS model to reduce the amount of these infeasibilities. Prior to describing the recovery procedure, we introduce the following notation. Given an infeasible solution $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$, let \mathcal{R}_t denote the set of routes of $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ that yield an excess vehicle load over the vehicle capacity Q in each period $t \in T$. We introduce a_{itr} a parameter that takes value 1 if customer $i \in N^C$ is visited by route $r \in \mathcal{R}_t, t \in T$, and 0 otherwise. We define $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$, a variable that represents the amount exceeding the vehicle load, computed as follows:

$$\xi = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \left(\sum_{i \in N^C} a_{itr} q_{it} \right) - Q.$$

Also, let $\mathcal{T} \subseteq T$ denote the set of time periods when a stock-out occurs at the plant node 0. Similarly, let $\psi \in \mathbb{R}$, be a variable that defines the amount for stock-outs at the plant, obtained by:

$$\psi = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} -I_{0t}.$$

Hence, a new cut-off constraint (4.6) that replaces the original one (4.5) is appended to the MIP model for the sake of reducing the infeasibility:

$$\xi + \psi \leq \bar{\xi} + \bar{\psi} - \theta_f. \quad (4.6)$$

where $\theta_f > 0$ is a given cutoff tolerance, $\bar{\xi}$ is the constant amount associated with vehicle excess in $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$, and $\bar{\psi}$ is the constant amount associated with stock-outs at the plant in $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$, respectively. The resulting model is solved using a MIP solver. One needs to run this process only once since the vehicle capacity and the inventory constraints will enforce a feasible solution. The cutoff constraint (4.6) helps, in this regard, the MIP solver to repair infeasibilities within short computing times by increasing the *relaxation grip* of the formulation [19]. Finally, to ensure that the recovery procedure does not deteriorate the solution quality, an additional cut-off constraint (4.7), defined by:

$$f(x, y, z) \leq f(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z}) + \theta_q. \quad (4.7)$$

is appended to the MIP model, and where $\theta_q > 0$ is a given quality deviation value.

4.4.3.3 Weight calculations

Here we explain how the weights associated with the proximity search binary variables are computed. We use a combination of the *Linear Relaxation Proximity (LRP)* approach and the *Three-Value System*

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(3-VS) approach, both introduced by Rodrigues et al. [34]. By applying the LPR, the weight w_j associated with any generic variable x_j can be expressed at each iteration by:

$$w_j = 1 - |\bar{x}_j - x_j^{LP}|.$$

where x_j^{LP} is the optimal value taken by x_j in the model's LP-relaxation, and \bar{x}_j its integer value in the incumbent solution. Then, a variable x_j whose value in the current solution is closer to its value in the LP-relaxation yields a higher weight. Hence, the weights associated with the x -variables, the y -variables, and the z -variables in Equation (4.4) are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} w_{ijt}^x &= 1 - |\bar{x}_{ijt} - x_{ijt}^{LP}|, \quad (i, j) \in E, \quad t \in T, \\ w_t^y &= 1 - |\bar{y}_t - y_t^{LP}|, \quad t \in T, \\ w_{it}^z &= 1 - |\bar{z}_{it} - z_{it}^{LP}|, \quad i \in N, \quad t \in T. \end{aligned}$$

The LRP approach performs well for optimization problems with an optimal solution close to the solution of the LP-relaxation [34]. It is not computationally intensive, since the required computational time corresponds only to the solution time of the LP-relaxation.

Remark 4.4.2. Given that: (i) we are solving a relaxation of the PRP model in Phase I of our matheuristic, (ii) the integrality of the production variables is maintained in this relaxation, and (iii) the production costs are usually the major cost component in a PRP setting, it would be natural to assume that the objective function of the solution obtained in Phase I is relatively close to the optimal one; thus it could be effectively used to compute the proximity search weights. In doing so, the weights associated with the y -variables will turn to zero.

Next, we apply the 3-VS discretization approach to transform the problem's weights into discrete values. This is done in two steps. First, the weights are discretized into R different values $\{1, \dots, R\}$, where R is an integer number greater than one defined a priori. The weights associated with the x -variables can be transformed as follows:

$$w_{ijt}^x = (R_x + 1) - \left\lceil R_x - \frac{(w_{ijt}^x - w^{\min,x})(R_x - 1)}{w^{\max,x} - w^{\min,x}} \right\rceil, \quad (i, j) \in E, \quad t \in T.$$

where $w^{\min,x} = \min\{w_{ijt}^x : (i, j) \in E, t \in T\}$ and $w^{\max,x} = \max\{w_{ijt}^x : (i, j) \in E, t \in T\}$. The resulting weights are next converted into a three-value system as follows:

$$w_{ijt}^x = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq w_{ijt}^x < t_2^x, \\ R_x/2, & \text{if } t_2^x \leq w_{ijt}^x < t_3^x, \\ R_x, & \text{if } t_3^x \leq w_{ijt}^x < R_x, \end{cases} \quad (i, j) \in E, \quad t \in T.$$

where t_2^x and t_3^x are integer threshold values between 1 and R defined a priori such that $t_2^x \leq t_3^x$. Similarly, we proceed for the z -variables to obtain:

$$w_{it}^z = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } 1 \leq w_{it}^z < t_2^z, \\ R_z/2, & \text{if } t_2^z \leq w_{it}^z < t_3^z, \\ R_z, & \text{if } t_3^z \leq w_{it}^z < R_z, \end{cases} \quad i \in N, \quad t \in T.$$

where t_2^z and t_3^z are integer threshold values between 1 and R and $t_2^z \leq t_3^z$. With respect to the y -variables whose initial weights are equal to 0, we set their corresponding weights as follows:

$$w_{it}^y = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \bar{y}_t \neq y_t^{LP}, \\ R_y, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad t \in T.$$

Remark 4.4.3. Variables' weights under their initial continuous representation would induce a computationally hard model [34] and thus, must be mapped into discrete values using the 3-VS discretization approach. To avoid any loss of quality due to the approximation, the choice of the parameters t_2 and t_3 is extensively studied in the computational section.

4.5 Computational experiments

Computational experiments were carried out using a Lenovo NextScale nx360 M5 machine, with a dual 3.5GHz Intel E5-2670v3 processor with 64 GB RAM. The matheuristic was implemented in C++, compiled with the Linux compiler g++ in release mode. The mathematical components were solved using CPLEX 12.10 with the default settings, except when solving the proximity search subproblems, where we emphasize the search toward finding early feasible solutions.

4.5.1 Experimental setup

Our computation experiments follow three main goals. First, we evaluate the impact of mathematical formulations within a matheuristic framework by comparing three state-of-the-art formulations for the PRP. Second, we expand our analysis by assessing the effect of valid inequalities using the considered formulations. Finally, we evaluate the matheuristic's convergence behavior with different starting solutions. For these analyses, we create a set of experiments by selecting, in each trial, a distinct mathematical formulation to be used by the mathematical components (namely, Phase I & Phase III) of the matheuristic described in Section 4.4. Hence, the matheuristic is run once using each of the $3^2 = 9$ combinations of formulations. By further considering the use of valid inequalities, the number of experiments is doubled, yielding a total of $9 \times 2 = 18$ variations of the matheuristic. The tests are conducted on benchmark data instances for the PRP [1]. The data set contains 168 instances with N^C from 10 to 50 and with time horizons of $H = 3, 6, \text{ and } 9$ periods, respectively. The number of vehicles is set to either $m = 2$ or $m = 3$ for the instances with $N \leq 25$ and to $m = 3$ or $m = 4$ for the rest of instances.

4.5.2 Choice of parameters and calibration

This section explains the choice of the parameters used in our computational experiments. First, the matheuristic method has a computational time limit of 4 hours, of which 600 seconds is the time limit imposed on Phase I. No limit was imposed on the total number of iterations in Phase III; however, each iteration stops when the first feasible solution is found [20]. Besides, the duration of every single iteration was restricted to one hour at maximum. We consider cut-off tolerances of $\theta = 1$ and $\theta_f = 1$, respectively. Rodrigues et al. [34] demonstrated that a unitary value of the cut-off tolerance performs better than higher values. For the quality deviation, using $\theta_q = 5\%$ of the starting solution's objective value led to subproblems that were relatively quickly solved, while leading to the first feasible solution being found having a comparable objective function value as the starting solution.

The discretization scheme described in Section 4.4.3.3 requires defining a maximum possible value for the weights R . We set $R = R_x = R_z = 100$ for both x and z variables, whereas we assign a higher value $R_y = 1000$ for the y -variables to restrict the change in their values during the WPS. Next, we choose the parameters t_2 and t_3 of the 3 – VS discretization approach. Three combinations of values are tested: (20,40), (30,60), and (40,80). Preliminary experiments for each setting of values were carried out on a training set of 27 instances. Moreover, we tested the classic proximity search (PS) heuristic where all weights are equal to one. Table 4.1 displays the average obtained results. The first column defines the discretization scheme, while the following columns present the average gap $\frac{Z^M - Z^{best}}{Z^{best}}$ to the best-known upper bound and the average running time used by the matheuristic, respectively.

Table 4.1: Comparison of the matheuristic's performance for different schemes of 3 – VS discretization

Scheme	Average gap (in %)	Average time (in sec.)
PS	0.63	4980
3 – $VS_{(20,40)}$	0.52	5184
3 – $VS_{(30-60)}$	0.37	5509
3 – $VS_{(40-80)}$	0.5	4594

The results indicate that the WPS approach is instrumental to improve the matheuristic performance. Under all discretization schemes, it provides better results on the set of selected instances than the standard PS without a significant increase in the computational time. According to Table 4.1, the lowest average gap corresponds to $(t_2, t_3) = (30, 60)$, which will be selected in our study.

4.5.3 Main results

In this section, we provide the main results derived from the set of tests performed on Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] instances. Table 4.2 describes, in columns 1-3, the configuration of each conducted test, that is to say, the formulation implemented in each mathematical component of the matheuristic. Then, for each test, we report the average percentage deviation of the MIP-relaxation bound (MIP gap) with respect to the value of the best-known upper bound and the average computing time in seconds. Columns 4 and 5 display the average percentage deviation of the constructive solution objective to the best-known upper bound (Cnst. gap) and the MIP-relaxation bound (LB gap), respectively. The computing time of Phase II is always negligible (a few milliseconds) and thus not reported. Columns 6-8 relate to the results derived from Phase III of our matheuristic. They display the average percentage deviation of the final solution's objective to the best-known upper bound (Final gap), the average percentage improvement (% impr.) with respect to the starting solution, and the average computing time in seconds, respectively. Finally, columns 9 and 10 report the number of new best bounds matched and found by the matheuristic for each test configuration. In all columns of Table 4.2, we put boldface letters on the shortest average computing time and average deviation to the best-known upper bounds; otherwise, boldface letters are used for the best average improvement to the starting solution.

Table 4.2: Average results obtained from the tests performed on Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] instances

Test #	Configuration			Phase I			Phase II			Phase III			Best bounds*	
	Phase I	Phase III		MIP gap (%)	CPU (s)		Cnst. gap (%)	LB gap (%)		Final gap (%)	% impr.	CPU (s)	New	Matched
	FIVF-VI	FIVF-VI		7.16	2.51		9.77	19.41		1.26	7.16	8,396	0	65
2		TCF-VI		7.16	2.51		9.77	19.41		1.49	6.98	8,798	3	58
3		TIVF-VI		7.16	2.55		9.79	19.43		1.91	6.13	4,724	0	68
4	FIVF	FIVF		8.35	0.46		9.50	20.83		1.50	6.81	8,138	0	53
5		TCF		8.35	0.45		9.50	20.83		2.12	6.31	8,262	8	61
6		TIVF		8.33	0.45		9.57	20.88		2.13	6.64	5,606	0	56
7		TIVF-VI		7.22	0.24		9.30	18.94		1.95	6.23	5,168	1	54
8		TCF-VI		7.16	0.26		9.35	18.91		1.33	6.85	8,580	2	63
9		FIVF-VI		7.16	0.27		9.35	18.91		1.15	6.99	8,482	0	65
10		TIVF		9.54	0.07		9.03	22.23		2.29	5.73	5,494	0	53
11		TCF		9.56	0.06		9.06	22.28		2.21	5.89	7,949	7	59
12		FIVF		9.56	0.06		9.06	22.28		1.42	6.52	8,425	1	51
13		TCF-VI		4.48	3.01		8.89	14.41		1.60	6.33	8,669	2	60
14		FIVF-VI		4.48	3.00		8.89	14.41		1.37	6.50	8,358	0	65
15		TIVF-VI		4.48	3.04		8.84	14.35		1.27	6.48	5,274	0	64
16		TCF		5.76	0.36		9.48	16.83		2.07	6.38	8,058	4	72
17		FIVF		5.76	0.36		9.48	16.83		1.61	6.74	7,867	0	50
18		TIVF		5.74	0.38		9.48	16.79		1.59	6.73	5,477	0	61

* Indicates the number of new best bounds found, or matched out of 168 instances.

Table 4.2 abounds with interesting observations. A first observation is that the TCF formulation produces, on average, tighter MIP relaxations than the other formulations, which are at most within 5.75% of the best-known integer bound. Besides, the FIVF formulation outperforms the TIVF formulations in this regard. This observation extends the findings of Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] and Archetti et al. [3], which showed that the FIVF formulation is superior to the TIVF one in terms of root node lower bounds and optimality gaps. The relaxed form of the TIVF formulation, in general, converges faster than the alternative formulations. A further observation is that the relaxed representation does not produce the same results across all runs (for example tests four and five). This issue is related to floating point arithmetic, where the rounding of continuous values is unpredictable and can cause the same program to produce different results on the same operating machine/system [25].

The matheuristic builds initial solutions always within at most 10% of the best primal bound. We see that the initial solutions produced by the TCF formulation yield a better optimality gap than those derived from alternative formulations, which is, on average, 8.84% far from the best integer bound. Additionally, the gap between the starting solution and the MIP relaxation, given by *Cnst. gap*, is relatively high. It increases to up to 22.28% for solutions derived from the TIVF formulation, while it is lower for those obtained by the FIVF formulation, averaging up to 20.88%. However, the starting solutions originating from the TCF formulation deviate less from their MIP relaxation by up to 14.41% on average. On one side, these observations explain that the quality of the produced initial solution is highly contingent on the mathematical formulation used. On the other side, they show that the TCF formulation fits better with the constructive heuristic associated with our matheuristic.

Next, we are interested in evaluating the quality of the final solutions derived from Phase III. Surprisingly, the FIVF formulation, when used to guide the WPS, provides the best performance on the benchmark PRP instances where the deviations from the optimal solutions or best upper bounds range between 1.15% and 1.61%. Better performance is achieved when valid inequalities are considered. The percentage improvement with respect to the starting solutions is significant and increases to 7.16% on average. The results obtained from the alternative formulations are slightly worse, where gaps of the best upper bound for the TIVF and TCF formulations are at most 2.29% and 2.21%, respectively; the corresponding average percentage improvements are 5.73% and 5.89%, respectively. On average, the execution times are lower when the TIVF formulation is used to drive the search. However, this behavior is a direct consequence of the non-improvement termination criterion imposed during the WPS. Clearly, after a few iterations, it becomes difficult for the TIVF formulation to improve the incumbent solution, thus, forcing the matheuristic to stop. The matheuristic does not necessarily perform better with good initial solutions, although whose choice may affect the search quality. We further investigate this aspect in the following sections. Additionally, our experiments showed that Phase III often starts with an infeasible solution in terms of vehicle capacities and stock-outs at the production plant. The feasibility recovery procedure was capable, however, of quickly restoring feasibility (in a few seconds or less) without significantly increasing the objective function value.

Finally, columns 9 and 10 in Table 4.2 indicate that our matheuristic competes with the state-of-the-art approach of Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] by matching or improving the best-known upper bounds. Our matheuristic, under an optimal configuration, matched the best-known solutions in 72 out of 168 test instances and improved the best-known upper bounds of 11 instances, aggregated over all the tested configurations. Interestingly, improved bounds are more likely to be found when the TCF formulation is implemented, and this seems to be contradicting the reported results on the average solution quality of this formulation. Finally, we provide in Appendix B more detailed results, and we compare them to the results reported in Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1].

4.5.4 Experimental analysis

In this section, we analyze the factors influencing the matheuristic's performance. Toward this aim, we use the primal gap of Berthold [9] as a performance measure. Given an incumbent solution (x, y, z) with the objective function value Z , and assume that an optimal (or best-known solution) is given with the objective function value Z^{best} , the primal gap of (x, y, z) is defined as

$$\gamma(x, y, z) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } Z = Z^{best}, \\ 1, & \text{if } (x, y, z) \text{ is infeasible,} \\ |Z^{best} - Z| / \max\{|Z^{best}|, |Z|\}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Then, assuming that we are given the objective function values of intermediate incumbent solutions and the points in time when they have been found, we define the primal gap function $p(t)$ as

$$p(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if no feasible solution has been found until point } t, \\ \gamma(x_t, y_t, z_t), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

where (x_t, y_t, z_t) being the incumbent solution at point t . The function $p(t)$ is, by definition, a step function that measures the quality of the solution found over time, and it changes whenever a new incumbent solution is found. It monotonically decreases and converges to 0 if an optimal solution is found.

4.5.4.1 Effect of valid inequalities

As a first analysis, we compare the performance of the matheuristic using the primal gaps when running with and without valid inequalities. Comparisons are carried out for different options of mathematical formulations, thus contrasting the results of test scenarios (described in Table 4.2) 1 to 4, 7 to 10, and 13 to 16, respectively. We show in Figure 4.2 the evolution of the primal gap over time. The figure is based on the average result of all instances. We express the time as the ratio to the total permitted running time ($t^{max} = 4$ hours), hence, we provide a baseline for comparison over all tested instances. Figure 4.2 has a logarithmic representation, which helps to highlight the scale of performance variations between the tested scenarios.

Figure 4.2: Course of the primal gap when running the matheuristic with and without valid inequalities.

Figure 4.2 demonstrates the importance of valid inequalities within a matheuristic search. The convergence of the primal gap when using valid inequalities (represented by the solid black line in the figure) is faster overall than without using valid inequalities (represented by the dotted red line). However, a limited variability is observed in the case of the FIVF-embedded matheuristic. The plots' trajectories are indistinguishable for minimal values of (t/t^{max}) , which indicates that the effect of valid inequalities is marginal for: (i) small-sized instances (those that do not require a significant computational time), and (ii) in the very early stages of heuristic search. Hence, one may conclude that using valid inequalities within a matheuristic setting is overall superior in terms of the primal gap. For this reason, only experiments with valid inequalities are considered subsequently.

4.5.4.2 Effect of mathematical formulations

The second experiment examines whether the choice of mathematical formulations affects algorithmic convergence. Hence, contributions gained from the mathematical formulations embedded within the WPS (Phase III) are weighted against each other. Precisely, we are contrasting the average results obtained from tests scenarios $\{1,9,14\}$ against those obtained from $\{2,8,13\}$, and $\{3,7,14\}$, respectively. For a comprehensive evaluation, analyses are carried out separately on data instances with comparable numbers of customers and planning horizon lengths. First, instances are arranged into the following subsets:

- Small: First 48 instances including 10 to 15 customers.
- Medium: Next 72 instances including 20 to 30 customers.
- Large: Last 48 instances including 35 to 50 customers.

Figure 4.3: Course of the primal gap when running the matheuristic with different mathematical formulations – Comparison by instance size.

Figure 4.3 compares the course of the primal gap obtained by the matheuristic for each subset of instances and where different mathematical formulations are implemented within the WPS. The solid black line corresponds to the course of the average primal gap function (taken over each subset of instances) when running the matheuristic with the FIVF-VI formulation. Additionally, the dotted red line and the dashed blue line correspond to the course of the average primal gap function when running the matheuristic with the TIVF-VI and the TCF-VI formulations, respectively. On the subset of small-sized instances, we observe that the three implementations find good-quality solutions (the average final primal gap is less than 1%) and that the FIVF-implementation acts more effectively almost at any point of the time (for $t/t^{max} \geq 1\%$). The TCF implementation performs poorly in general, converging toward good-quality solutions only later in the run. Regarding the subset of medium-sized instances, it is difficult to establish a clear dominance among the three formulations, although the TIVF-implementation led to the best improvement in the primal gap on average. The TIVF-implementation is inferior to the values reported on the subset of small-sized instances, which was expected considering the added complexity caused

by the increased number of customers. Regarding the subset of large instances, the TIVF-embedded matheuristic quickly finds a good-quality solution but fails later to achieve significant improvements. The TIVF formulation does not appear to be competitive in large-sized instances as widely claimed in the literature. The TCF-embedded matheuristic is slightly better, particularly in the early and the late stages of the search, which could explain its ability to improve the best-known upper bounds (Table 4.2). Looking also at Table 4.3 in Appendix B, we see that many of the improved best-known upper bounds belonged to the subset of large-sized instances and were obtained using a TCF formulation.

Next, our comparisons are conducted on new subsets of instances, arranged following the length of their planning horizon. The subsets include 72 instances with $H = 3$, 56 instances with $H = 6$, and 40 instances with $H = 9$, respectively. Figure 4.4 shows the course of the primal gap recorded by the matheuristic on each subset of instances and with different implemented mathematical formulations in Phase III.

Figure 4.4: Course of the primal gap when running the matheuristic with different mathematical formulations – Comparison by the planning horizon length.

As visible in Figure 4.4, the TIVF-implementation yields the worst performance among the three implementations in instances with short planning horizons. The implementation’s performance is worsened for higher values of (t/t^{max}) due to its deficiency on large-sized instances (as shown previously). Recall that higher values of (t/t^{max}) correspond primarily to instances with many customers. Such interference is further corroborated when looking at the plot associated with the TCF implementation, which records the lowest primal gap for high values of (t/t^{max}) . The FIVF-implementation has a consistent behavior regardless of (t/t^{max}) values (by inference, of customers’ number), which might suggest its usefulness on this subset of instances. On the subset of instances with $H = 6$, the same assessment as before for the TIVF-implementation still holds, while both the FIVF and the TCF implementations exhibit better behaviors, intriguingly proportionate. Larger planning horizons have a more pronounced effect on the FIVF and the TIVF implementations whose performances degraded, while the TIVF-implementation is seemingly more efficacious on instances with $H = 9$.

4.5.4.3 Effect of initial solutions

As a final experiment, we investigate whether the starting solution's quality significantly affects the performance of the matheuristic. We test the matheuristic with three starting solutions, each derived from the MIP relaxation of a different PRP formulation. In all cases, the mathematical formulation associated with the WPS is varied to rule out any bias that might be induced by the performance inequality of the three formulations. That is, we are contrasting the average results from test case one against those resulting from 9 and 14, from test case two against those from 8 and 13, and finally, the results obtained from test case three against the results of tests 7 and 15 (described in Table 4.2), respectively. Similar to the previous experiments, we map in each run the course of the matheuristic's primal gap over time, and it is shown in Figure 4.5. The solid black line corresponds to the course of the average primal gap function (taken over 168 instances) when initiating the matheuristic with a FIVF-based solution. In contrast, the dotted red line and the dashed blue line correspond to the course of the average primal gap function when initiating the matheuristic with TIVF-based and TCF-based solutions, respectively. Each subplot within the figure corresponds to an alternative implementation of the matheuristic obtained using a different formulation during Phase III, and where valid inequalities are appended.

Figure 4.5: Course of the primal gap when running the matheuristic under different initial solutions options.

Figure 4.5 puts in evidence almost similar behaviors of the matheuristic for different options of starting solutions. In the first and the third implementations, initiating the matheuristic with a TIVF-based solution leads to a tiny improvement in the primal gap. However, when the TIVF formulation simultaneously initiates and guides the algorithmic search, the matheuristic becomes less efficient. The same observation is also valid for the other two formulations. Another indication provided by Figure 4.5 is that the best initial solution, in this case, obtained through the TCF formulation, does not necessarily lead to finding the best final solution.

4.6 Concluding remarks

This paper presents an experimental study of matheuristic performance for the PRP considering different mathematical formulations. For the sake of this study, we developed a novel matheuristic consisting of three phases. First, initial lot-sizing decisions are obtained by a master problem relaxation. Next, a sequence of heuristic algorithms completes the associated partial solution in terms of distribution and routing decisions. Finally, the incumbent solution is iteratively improved using a general-purpose MIP heuristic. Vehicle capacity violations and inventory stock-outs at the plant facility are permitted in the construction phase; however, they are later repaired using a recovery procedure. Three mathematical formulations have been implemented and tested within the matheuristic framework: a four-index vehicle flow formulation, a three-index vehicle flow formulation, and a two-commodity flow formulation. The proposed matheuristic turned out to be very competitive with state-of-the-art algorithms by matching or improving the best-known upper bounds, although this was not the primary aim of this effort.

The experimental study assesses the impact of various design alternatives and choices of matheuristics for the PRP. More specifically, we investigated the computational effects stemming from the choice of mathematical formulations, using valid inequalities, and alternating the starting solutions within a matheuristic framework. We perform extensive computational tests on benchmark PRP instances and use consistent performance measures to compare the performance of the matheuristic under the proposed configurations. The results give us a better view of the models that work better for a matheuristic in practice. In particular, they showed that the contribution of a mathematical formulation to the matheuristic convergence is instance-specific and mainly attributable to the number of customers and the length of the planning horizon considered. It is also clear that integrating valid inequalities is highly beneficial, regardless of the considered mathematical formulation. Additionally, a matheuristic with a strong initial solution (in terms of optimality gap) is not necessarily superior to one with a weaker initial solution. Several reasons might explain this behavior, and they relate to the data instances' inherent features, the definition of the search neighborhood, and the particular features of solvers, all of which are details often not fully known to the practitioner.

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Appendix 4.A Valid inequalities.

Several valid inequalities have been added to strengthen the proposed PRP formulations, and all of them originate from the existing literature. In what follows, we present the valid inequalities associated with each mathematical formulation.

4.A.1 Valid inequalities for the FIVF formulation

We present here the inequalities that are valid for the FIVF formulation, and which were originally proposed by Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1]. Denote by t' and t'' the earliest period when the plant must produce and the earliest period when at least one customer must be replenished to prevent a stock-out, respectively; i.e., $t' = \operatorname{argmin}_{1 \leq t \leq H} \left\{ \sum_{i \in N^C} \max\{0, \sum_{j=1}^t d_{ij} - I_{i0}\} - I_{00} > 0 \right\}$, and $t'' = \min_{i \in N^C} t_i$, where $t_i = \operatorname{argmin}_{1 \leq t \leq H} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^t d_{ij} - I_{i0} > 0 \right\}$. Let M be the minimum shipping quantity in t'' ; i.e., $M = \sum_{i \in N^C} \max\left\{0, \sum_{j=1}^{t''} d_{ij} - I_{i0}\right\}$. The first two inequalities are intended to prevent stock-outs and are given by:

$$\sum_{t=1}^{t'} y_t \geq 1, \quad (\text{A.1.1})$$

$$\sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t=1}^{t''} z_{0kt} \geq \left\lceil \frac{M}{Q} \right\rceil. \quad (\text{A.1.2})$$

Constraints (A.1.1) ensure that a production process will be launched no later than t' , while constraints (A.1.2) compute a lower bound on the number of used vehicles. The following inequalities further strengthen customer replenishment:

$$I_{i,t-l-1} \geq \left(\sum_{j=0}^l d_{i,t-j} \right) \left(1 - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{j=0}^l z_{ik,t-j} \right), \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad l = 0, 1, \dots, t-1. \quad (\text{A.1.3})$$

Constraints (A.1.3) imply that if a customer $i \in N^C$ is not served at time period $t \in T$, then the available stock at inventory I_{it} should cover the customer's demand in the corresponding period. Finally, the following inequalities are concerned with the routing decisions:

$$z_{ikt} \leq z_{0kt}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.1.4})$$

$$x_{ijkt} \leq z_{jkt} \text{ and } x_{ijkt} \leq z_{ikt}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad k \in K, \quad t \in T. \quad (\text{A.1.5})$$

Constraints (A.1.4) force the plant node and the customer node to be included in the same route traveled at time $t \in T$, if customer $i \in N^C$ is visited, that is $z_{it} = 1$. Constraints (A.1.5) are referred to as logical inequalities, and they say that if a customer i is the successor, respectively the predecessor, of customer j in the route traveled at period $t \in T$, then j has to be visited too.

4.A.2 Valid inequalities for the TIVF formulation

The valid inequalities proposed above can be adapted for the TIVF formulation as follows:

$$\sum_{t=1}^{t'} y_t \geq 1, \quad (\text{A.2.1})$$

$$\sum_{t=1}^{t''} z_{0t} \geq \left\lceil \frac{M}{Q} \right\rceil, \quad (\text{A.2.2})$$

$$I_{i,t-l-1} \geq \left(\sum_{j=0}^l d_{i,t-j} \right) \left(1 - \sum_{j=0}^l z_{i,t-j} \right), \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad l = 0, 1, \dots, t-1, \quad (\text{A.2.3})$$

$$z_{it} \leq z_{0t}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.2.4})$$

$$x_{ijt} \leq z_{it} \text{ and } x_{ijt} \leq z_{jt}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad t \in T. \quad (\text{A.2.5})$$

Besides, we add a priori the following inequalities:

$$Qz_{0t} \geq \sum_{i \in N^C} q_{it}, \quad t \in T. \quad (\text{A.2.6})$$

Constraints (A.2.6) ensures that the number of routed vehicles is sufficient to carry the total delivered quantities to all customers at each time period. Finally, because the GFSECs (2.14) are weak, we can further strengthen the TIVF formulation by considering the following subtour elimination constraints (SECs):

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E(S)} x_{ijt} \leq \sum_{i \in S} z_{it} - z_{et}, \quad S \subseteq N^C, \quad |S| \geq 2, \quad e \in S, \quad t \in T. \quad (\text{A.2.7})$$

These inequalities are inserted to prevent subtours in each time period, however, they do not prevent violations at vehicle capacities, and they must necessarily be used together with the GFSECs (2.14). These cuts are separated dynamically using the min-cut algorithm.

4.A.3 Valid inequalities for the TCF formulation

In their paper, Manousakis et al. [29] described and implemented three sets of valid inequalities for the TCF formulation. The first set of inequalities is adopted from a similar formulation for the inventory routing problem, which was described in Manousakis et al. [28]. These inequalities are given by:

$$x_{0it} \leq z_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.1})$$

$$x_{ijt} \leq z_{it}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.2})$$

$$x_{ijt} \leq z_{jt}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.3})$$

$$f_{ijt} \geq d_{jt}x_{ijt} - I_{j,t-1}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.4})$$

$$f_{jit} \geq d_{it}x_{ijt} - I_{i,t-1}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.5})$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^t z_{il} \geq \left\lceil \frac{\sum_{l=1}^t d_{il} - I_{i0}}{\min(Q, L_i)} \right\rceil, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.6})$$

$$\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} z_{il} \geq \left\lceil \frac{\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} d_{il} - L_i}{\min(Q, L_i)} \right\rceil, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t_1, t_2 \in T, \quad t_1 < t_2, \quad (\text{A.3.7})$$

$$\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} z_{il} \geq \frac{\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} d_{il} - I_{i,t_1-1}}{\min(Q, L_i)}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t_1, t_2 \in T, \quad t_1 < t_2, \quad (\text{A.3.8})$$

$$\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} z_{il} \geq \frac{\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} d_{il} - I_{i,t_1-1}}{\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} d_{il}}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t_1, t_2 \in T, \quad t_1 < t_2. \quad (\text{A.3.9})$$

Inequalities (A.3.1)-(A.3.3) are the logical inequalities, and they are similar to those described within the two previous formulations. Inequalities (A.3.4) and (A.3.5) define lower bounds on the flow variables. It ensures that the flow (which translates to the load carried by a vehicle before visiting a customer $i \in N^C$, or the residual capacity after visiting customer $i \in N^C$) is higher or equal to the stock-out at the customer. Moreover, inequalities (A.3.6)-(A.3.9) impose a lower bound on the number of performed visits to a customer $i \in N^C$ during any time interval within the planning horizon. An additional set of inequalities was proposed by Manousakis et al. [29], and they describe as follow:

$$f_{ijt} \leq Qx_{ijt}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.10})$$

$$f_{jit} \leq Qx_{ijt}, \quad (i, j) \in E(N^C), \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.11})$$

$$q_{it} \leq \min \left\{ L_i + d_{it}, Q, \sum_{l=t}^H d_{il} \right\} z_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.12})$$

$$q_{it} \leq \min \left\{ L_i + d_{it} - I_{i,t-1}, \sum_{l=t}^H d_{il} - I_{i,t-1} \right\} z_{it}, \quad i \in N^C, \quad t \in T. \quad (\text{A.3.13})$$

Inequalities (A.3.10) and (A.3.11) are the logical constraints related to the flow variables. These variables can be positive only when the edge (i, j) is traversed. Furthermore, inequalities (A.3.12) and (A.3.13) impose an upper bound on the delivered quantities. Finally, Manousakis et al. [29] presented new valid inequalities for the production setup variables, and which were inspired from the work of Coelho and Laporte [15]. They can be described as follows:

$$y_t^C \geq \sum_{i \in N^C} (d_{it} - I_{i,t-1}) - I_{0,t-1}, \quad t \in T, \quad (\text{A.3.14})$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^t y_l \geq \left\lceil \frac{\sum_{i \in N^C} \sum_{l=1}^t d_{il} - I_{i0}}{C} \right\rceil, \quad t \in T, \quad t > 1, \quad (\text{A.3.15})$$

$$\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} y_l \geq \left\lceil \frac{\sum_{i \in N^C} \left(\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} d_{il} \right) - L_i - L_0}{C} \right\rceil, \quad t_1, t_2 \in T, \quad t_1 < t_2, \quad (\text{A.3.16})$$

$$\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} y_l \geq \frac{\sum_{i \in N^C} \left(\sum_{l=t_1}^{t_2} d_{il} \right) - I_{i,t_1-1} - I_{0,t_1-1}}{C}, \quad t_1, t_2 \in T, \quad t_1 < t_2. \quad (\text{A.3.17})$$

Inequalities (A.3.14) ensure that a production process will be launched when the stock at both the customer and the plant is not enough to satisfy the demands. Inequalities (A.3.15)-(A.3.17) impose lower bounds on the minimum number of setups during any time interval within the planning horizon.

Appendix 4.B Detailed numerical results.

In Table 4.3, we report the results obtained by the proposed matheuristic, aggregated over all the tested configurations, versus the ones reported in Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] for the multivehicle PRP. Recall that the results from Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] correspond to the solutions of a branch & cut (B&C) algorithm solved using multi-core processors. For each instance, we report first the objective value of the best integer solution (Z^{BC}) obtained by the B&C algorithm and its ratio to the lower bound. Next, we display the objective value of the best integer solution (Z^M) obtained by the matheuristic, its ratio to the lower bound, and the percentage deviation (DEV) from the B&C solutions. We highlight in bold solutions where the matheuristic improves the best-known upper bounds. In the final row of Table 4.3, we report the average calculations over all instances. Since the two methods were run on machines with different capabilities and parameter settings, comparing CPU times becomes inconsistent. We prefer thereby not to report them.

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Table 4.3: Detailed results obtained on Adulyasak, Cordeau, and Jans [1] benchmark data instances using the matheuristic

Instance	Name	Branch & cut		Matheuristic		
		Z^{BC}	LB (%)	Z^M	LB (%)	DEV (%)
1	MVPRP_C10_P3_V2_I1.dat	13,924	100.00	13,924	100.00	0.00
2	MVPRP_C10_P3_V2_I2.dat	98,434	100.00	98,434	100.00	0.00
3	MVPRP_C10_P3_V2_I3.dat	19,751	100.00	19,751	100.00	0.00
4	MVPRP_C10_P3_V2_I4.dat	10,792	100.00	10,792	100.00	0.00
5	MVPRP_C10_P3_V3_I1.dat	14,002	100.00	14,002	100.00	0.00
6	MVPRP_C10_P3_V3_I2.dat	98,512	100.00	98,512	100.00	0.00
7	MVPRP_C10_P3_V3_I3.dat	20,550	100.00	20,550	100.00	0.00
8	MVPRP_C10_P3_V3_I4.dat	10,974	100.00	10,974	100.00	0.00
9	MVPRP_C10_P6_V2_I1.dat	29,559	100.00	29,559	100.00	0.00
10	MVPRP_C10_P6_V2_I2.dat	197,769	100.00	197,769	100.00	0.00
11	MVPRP_C10_P6_V2_I3.dat	40,249	100.00	40,249	100.00	0.00
12	MVPRP_C10_P6_V2_I4.dat	21,248	100.00	21,248	100.00	0.00
13	MVPRP_C10_P6_V3_I1.dat	29,897	100.00	29,897	100.00	0.00
14	MVPRP_C10_P6_V3_I2.dat	198,107	100.00	198,107	100.00	0.00
15	MVPRP_C10_P6_V3_I3.dat	41,668	100.00	41,668	100.00	0.00
16	MVPRP_C10_P6_V3_I4.dat	21,559	100.00	21,559	100.00	0.00
17	MVPRP_C10_P9_V2_I1.dat	50,929	100.00	50,929	100.00	0.00
18	MVPRP_C10_P9_V2_I2.dat	369,259	100.00	369,259	100.00	0.00
19	MVPRP_C10_P9_V2_I3.dat	69,464	100.00	69,464	100.00	0.00
20	MVPRP_C10_P9_V2_I4.dat	39,631	100.00	39,631	100.00	0.00
21	MVPRP_C10_P9_V3_I1.dat	51,739	100.00	51,739	100.00	0.00
22	MVPRP_C10_P9_V3_I2.dat	370,069	100.00	370,069	100.00	0.00
23	MVPRP_C10_P9_V3_I3.dat	72,148	100.00	72,148	100.00	0.00
24	MVPRP_C10_P9_V3_I4.dat	40,276	100.00	40,276	100.00	0.00
25	MVPRP_C15_P3_V2_I1.dat	19,488	100.00	19,488	100.00	0.00
26	MVPRP_C15_P3_V2_I2.dat	136,128	100.00	136,128	100.00	0.00
27	MVPRP_C15_P3_V2_I3.dat	28,687	100.00	28,687	100.00	0.00
28	MVPRP_C15_P3_V2_I4.dat	15,163	100.00	15,163	100.00	0.00
29	MVPRP_C15_P3_V3_I1.dat	19,680	100.00	19,680	100.00	0.00
30	MVPRP_C15_P3_V3_I2.dat	136,320	100.00	136,320	100.00	0.00
31	MVPRP_C15_P3_V3_I3.dat	30,376	100.00	30,376	100.00	0.00
32	MVPRP_C15_P3_V3_I4.dat	15,469	100.00	15,469	100.00	0.00
33	MVPRP_C15_P6_V2_I1.dat	41,627	100.00	41,627	100.00	0.00
34	MVPRP_C15_P6_V2_I2.dat	273,827	100.00	273,827	100.00	0.00
35	MVPRP_C15_P6_V2_I3.dat	57,294	100.00	57,294	100.00	0.00
36	MVPRP_C15_P6_V2_I4.dat	29,556	100.00	29,556	100.00	0.00
37	MVPRP_C15_P6_V3_I1.dat	42,191	100.00	42,191	100.00	0.00
38	MVPRP_C15_P6_V3_I2.dat	274,391	100.00	274,391	100.00	0.00
39	MVPRP_C15_P6_V3_I3.dat	60,087	100.00	60,087	100.00	0.00
40	MVPRP_C15_P6_V3_I4.dat	30,090	100.00	30,090	100.00	0.00
41	MVPRP_C15_P9_V2_I1.dat	73,204	100.00	73,294	99.88	0.12
42	MVPRP_C15_P9_V2_I2.dat	522,754	100.00	522,896	99.97	0.03
43	MVPRP_C15_P9_V2_I3.dat	102,002	100.00	103,138	98.90	1.11
44	MVPRP_C15_P9_V2_I4.dat	56,644	100.00	56,680	99.94	0.06
45	MVPRP_C15_P9_V3_I1.dat	74,854	98.74	74,787	98.83	-0.09
46	MVPRP_C15_P9_V3_I2.dat	524,376	99.84	524,387	99.84	0.00
47	MVPRP_C15_P9_V3_I3.dat	108,055	94.67	111,351	91.87	3.05
48	MVPRP_C15_P9_V3_I4.dat	57,914	98.15	57,919	98.14	0.01
49	MVPRP_C20_P3_V2_I1.dat	22,209	100.00	22,209	100.00	0.00
50	MVPRP_C20_P3_V2_I2.dat	157,479	100.00	157,479	100.00	0.00
51	MVPRP_C20_P3_V2_I3.dat	31,708	100.00	31,708	100.00	0.00
52	MVPRP_C20_P3_V2_I4.dat	17,171	100.00	17,171	100.00	0.00
53	MVPRP_C20_P3_V3_I1.dat	22,375	100.00	22,375	100.00	0.00
54	MVPRP_C20_P3_V3_I2.dat	157,645	100.00	157,645	100.00	0.00
55	MVPRP_C20_P3_V3_I3.dat	32,851	100.00	32,851	100.00	0.00
56	MVPRP_C20_P3_V3_I4.dat	17,400	100.00	17,400	100.00	0.00
57	MVPRP_C20_P6_V2_I1.dat	47,466	100.00	47,466	100.00	0.00
58	MVPRP_C20_P6_V2_I2.dat	315,846	100.00	315,846	100.00	0.00
59	MVPRP_C20_P6_V2_I3.dat	63,746	100.00	63,746	100.00	0.00
60	MVPRP_C20_P6_V2_I4.dat	33,488	100.00	33,488	100.00	0.00
61	MVPRP_C20_P6_V3_I1.dat	47,681	100.00	47,681	100.00	0.00
62	MVPRP_C20_P6_V3_I2.dat	316,061	100.00	316,061	100.00	0.00
63	MVPRP_C20_P6_V3_I3.dat	65,789	100.00	65,869	99.88	0.12
64	MVPRP_C20_P6_V3_I4.dat	33,859	100.00	33,859	100.00	0.00
65	MVPRP_C20_P9_V2_I1.dat	82,150	100.00	82,150	100.00	0.00
66	MVPRP_C20_P9_V2_I2.dat	596,230	100.00	596,317	99.99	0.01
67	MVPRP_C20_P9_V2_I3.dat	110,925	100.00	112,565	98.54	1.48

Table 4.3 continued from previous page

Instance	Name	Branch & cut		Matheuristic		
		Z^{BC}	LB (%)	Z^M	LB (%)	DEV (%)
68	MVPRP_C20_P9_V2_I4.dat	62,920	100.00	62,920	100.00	0.00
69	MVPRP_C20_P9_V3_I1.dat	82,685	100.00	82,741	99.93	0.07
70	MVPRP_C20_P9_V3_I2.dat	596,765	100.00	596,765	100.00	0.00
71	MVPRP_C20_P9_V3_I3.dat	115,499	98.33	117,771	96.43	1.97
72	MVPRP_C20_P9_V3_I4.dat	63,919	99.62	63,919	99.62	0.00
73	MVPRP_C25_P3_V2_I1.dat	26,055	100.00	26,055	100.00	0.00
74	MVPRP_C25_P3_V2_I2.dat	182,115	100.00	182,115	100.00	0.00
75	MVPRP_C25_P3_V2_I3.dat	35,939	100.00	35,939	100.00	0.00
76	MVPRP_C25_P3_V2_I4.dat	19,528	100.00	19,528	100.00	0.00
77	MVPRP_C25_P3_V3_I1.dat	26,269	100.00	26,269	100.00	0.00
78	MVPRP_C25_P3_V3_I2.dat	182,329	100.00	182,329	100.00	0.00
79	MVPRP_C25_P3_V3_I3.dat	37,754	100.00	37,754	100.00	0.00
80	MVPRP_C25_P3_V3_I4.dat	19,891	100.00	19,891	100.00	0.00
81	MVPRP_C25_P6_V2_I1.dat	56,869	100.00	56,869	100.00	0.00
82	MVPRP_C25_P6_V2_I2.dat	366,289	100.00	366,289	100.00	0.00
83	MVPRP_C25_P6_V2_I3.dat	73,339	100.00	73,339	100.00	0.00
84	MVPRP_C25_P6_V2_I4.dat	38,231	100.00	38,231	100.00	0.00
85	MVPRP_C25_P6_V3_I1.dat	57,077	100.00	57,077	100.00	0.00
86	MVPRP_C25_P6_V3_I2.dat	366,497	100.00	366,497	100.00	0.00
87	MVPRP_C25_P6_V3_I3.dat	76,112	100.00	76,112	100.00	0.00
88	MVPRP_C25_P6_V3_I4.dat	38,726	100.00	38,798	99.81	0.19
89	MVPRP_C25_P9_V2_I1.dat	99,868	100.00	99,879	99.99	0.01
90	MVPRP_C25_P9_V2_I2.dat	719,788	100.00	719,892	99.99	0.01
91	MVPRP_C25_P9_V2_I3.dat	133,290	99.16	136,388	96.91	2.32
92	MVPRP_C25_P9_V2_I4.dat	76,197	100.00	76,632	99.43	0.57
93	MVPRP_C25_P9_V3_I1.dat	100,690	99.85	101,371	99.18	0.68
94	MVPRP_C25_P9_V3_I2.dat	720,609	99.98	721,370	99.87	0.11
95	MVPRP_C25_P9_V3_I3.dat	139,695	95.32	145,528	91.50	4.18
96	MVPRP_C25_P9_V3_I4.dat	77,725	98.09	77,882	97.89	0.20
97	MVPRP_C30_P3_V3_I1.dat	28,872	100.00	28,872	100.00	0.00
98	MVPRP_C30_P3_V3_I2.dat	205,992	100.00	205,992	100.00	0.00
99	MVPRP_C30_P3_V3_I3.dat	41,164	100.00	41,164	100.00	0.00
100	MVPRP_C30_P3_V3_I4.dat	22,589	100.00	22,589	100.00	0.00
101	MVPRP_C30_P3_V4_I1.dat	29,157	100.00	29,157	100.00	0.00
102	MVPRP_C30_P3_V4_I2.dat	206,277	100.00	206,277	100.00	0.00
103	MVPRP_C30_P3_V4_I3.dat	42,543	100.00	42,543	100.00	0.00
104	MVPRP_C30_P3_V4_I4.dat	22,860	100.00	22,860	100.00	0.00
105	MVPRP_C30_P6_V3_I1.dat	61,287	100.00	61,350	99.90	0.10
106	MVPRP_C30_P6_V3_I2.dat	413,637	100.00	413,764	99.97	0.03
107	MVPRP_C30_P6_V3_I3.dat	82,249	100.00	82,897	99.22	0.79
108	MVPRP_C30_P6_V3_I4.dat	44,007	100.00	44,007	100.00	0.00
109	MVPRP_C30_P6_V4_I1.dat	61,741	100.00	61,784	99.93	0.07
110	MVPRP_C30_P6_V4_I2.dat	414,091	100.00	414,222	99.97	0.03
111	MVPRP_C30_P6_V4_I3.dat	85,895	97.03	85,931	96.99	0.04
112	MVPRP_C30_P6_V4_I4.dat	44,593	98.76	44,588	98.77	-0.01
113	MVPRP_C30_P9_V3_I1.dat	110,070	99.51	111,786	97.98	1.56
114	MVPRP_C30_P9_V3_I2.dat	800,629	99.93	802,413	99.71	0.22
115	MVPRP_C30_P9_V3_I3.dat	151,878	94.10	164,341	86.96	8.21
116	MVPRP_C30_P9_V3_I4.dat	86,292	97.49	86,138	97.66	-0.18
117	MVPRP_C30_P9_V4_I1.dat	111,263	98.60	116,151	94.45	4.39
118	MVPRP_C30_P9_V4_I2.dat	802,111	99.75	805,823	99.29	0.46
119	MVPRP_C30_P9_V4_I3.dat	158,605	90.52	164,033	87.52	3.42
120	MVPRP_C30_P9_V4_I4.dat	88,578	94.85	87,370	96.16	-1.36
121	MVPRP_C35_P3_V3_I1.dat	35,503	100.00	35,503	100.00	0.00
122	MVPRP_C35_P3_V3_I2.dat	256,903	100.00	256,916	99.99	0.01
123	MVPRP_C35_P3_V3_I3.dat	49,660	100.00	49,691	99.94	0.06
124	MVPRP_C35_P3_V3_I4.dat	27,774	100.00	27,774	100.00	0.00
125	MVPRP_C35_P3_V4_I1.dat	35,854	100.00	35,854	100.00	0.00
126	MVPRP_C35_P3_V4_I2.dat	257,254	100.00	257,254	100.00	0.00
127	MVPRP_C35_P3_V4_I3.dat	51,475	100.00	51,749	99.47	0.53
128	MVPRP_C35_P3_V4_I4.dat	28,160	100.00	28,160	100.00	0.00
129	MVPRP_C35_P6_V3_I1.dat	74,939	100.00	75,147	99.72	0.28
130	MVPRP_C35_P6_V3_I2.dat	515,039	100.00	515,334	99.94	0.06
131	MVPRP_C35_P6_V3_I3.dat	99,846	98.09	101,235	96.74	1.39
132	MVPRP_C35_P6_V3_I4.dat	54,410	99.18	54,483	99.05	0.13
133	MVPRP_C35_P6_V4_I1.dat	75,487	99.62	75,938	99.03	0.60
134	MVPRP_C35_P6_V4_I2.dat	515,594	99.95	516,115	99.85	0.10
135	MVPRP_C35_P6_V4_I3.dat	104,045	94.06	109,106	89.70	4.86
136	MVPRP_C35_P6_V4_I4.dat	55,439	97.36	55,094	97.97	-0.62

4. Experimental evaluation of using different mathematical formulations in a matheuristic for the production routing problem

Table 4.3 continued from previous page

Instance	Name	Branch & cut		Matheuristic		
		Z^{BC}	LB (%)	Z^M	LB (%)	DEV (%)
137	MVPRP_C40_P3_V3_I1.dat	44,422	100.00	44,422	100.00	0.00
138	MVPRP_C40_P3_V3_I2.dat	320,512	100.00	320,533	99.99	0.01
139	MVPRP_C40_P3_V3_I3.dat	61,530	100.00	61,705	99.72	0.28
140	MVPRP_C40_P3_V3_I4.dat	34,162	100.00	34,162	100.00	0.00
141	MVPRP_C40_P3_V4_I1.dat	44,461	100.00	44,468	99.98	0.02
142	MVPRP_C40_P3_V4_I2.dat	320,816	100.00	320,855	99.99	0.01
143	MVPRP_C40_P3_V4_I3.dat	63,823	96.34	63,611	96.66	-0.33
144	MVPRP_C40_P3_V4_I4.dat	34,688	99.09	34,728	98.98	0.12
145	MVPRP_C40_P6_V3_I1.dat	96,393	99.76	96,926	99.21	0.55
146	MVPRP_C40_P6_V3_I2.dat	646,929	99.98	647,463	99.90	0.08
147	MVPRP_C40_P6_V3_I3.dat	123,837	96.99	127,922	93.89	3.30
148	MVPRP_C40_P6_V3_I4.dat	67,180	98.58	67,140	98.64	-0.06
149	MVPRP_C40_P6_V4_I1.dat	97,104	98.94	98,855	97.19	1.80
150	MVPRP_C40_P6_V4_I2.dat	647,331	99.90	649,413	99.58	0.32
151	MVPRP_C40_P6_V4_I3.dat	129,933	92.43	135,637	88.54	4.39
152	MVPRP_C40_P6_V4_I4.dat	68,115	97.47	67,944	97.72	-0.25
153	MVPRP_C45_P3_V3_I1.dat	50,446	100.00	50,446	100.00	0.00
154	MVPRP_C45_P3_V3_I2.dat	376,125	100.00	376,166	99.99	0.01
155	MVPRP_C45_P3_V3_I3.dat	69,629	100.00	70,989	98.08	1.95
156	MVPRP_C45_P3_V3_I4.dat	39,929	100.00	39,959	99.92	0.08
157	MVPRP_C45_P3_V4_I1.dat	50,872	100.00	50,915	99.92	0.08
158	MVPRP_C45_P3_V4_I2.dat	376,654	99.86	376,604	99.87	-0.01
159	MVPRP_C45_P3_V4_I3.dat	73,658	93.94	72,570	95.35	-1.48
160	MVPRP_C45_P3_V4_I4.dat	40,862	97.76	40,500	98.63	-0.89
161	MVPRP_C50_P3_V3_I1.dat	46,726	100.00	46,757	99.93	0.07
162	MVPRP_C50_P3_V3_I2.dat	340,782	100.00	340,928	99.96	0.04
163	MVPRP_C50_P3_V3_I3.dat	65,260	100.00	65,449	99.71	0.29
164	MVPRP_C50_P3_V3_I4.dat	36,347	100.00	36,347	100.00	0.00
165	MVPRP_C50_P3_V4_I1.dat	47,138	100.00	47,149	99.98	0.02
166	MVPRP_C50_P3_V4_I2.dat	341,426	99.91	341,573	99.87	0.04
167	MVPRP_C50_P3_V4_I3.dat	68,125	96.45	69,352	94.74	1.80
168	MVPRP_C50_P3_V4_I4.dat	36,969	99.60	36,971	99.59	0.01
Average			99.45		99.15	0.32

Chapter 5

A Matheuristic for the Robust Integrated Airline Fleet Assignment, Aircraft Routing, and Crew Pairing Problem

Chapter 5

A Matheuristic for the Robust Integrated Airline Fleet Assignment, Aircraft Routing, and Crew Pairing Problem

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Mohamed Ben Ahmed Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway mohamed.ben.ahmed@himolde.no

Maryia Hryhoryeva Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway

Lars Magnus Hvattum Faculty of Logistics, Molde University College, PO Box 2110, NO-6402 Molde, Norway Lars.M.Hvattum@himolde.no

Mohamed Haouari Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, College of Engineering, Qatar University, P.O. Box 2713, Doha, Qatar mohamed.haouari@qu.edu.qa

Abstract

We address an integrated airline scheduling problem that combines three airline planning processes: fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing. For a given daily flight schedule, the problem requires simultaneously assigning aircraft and crews to each scheduled flight, taking into account aircraft maintenance restrictions and crew work rules. We propose to solve this complex problem of integrated flight planning while taking into account robustness considerations. In this regard, robustness is achieved by restricting tight connections in the schedule and increasing the number of connections where crews follow the aircraft. We formulate the problem using a very large-scale, yet compact, mixed-integer programming model, and we propose a matheuristic consisting of a decomposition approach and a proximity search algorithm. Computational experiments carried out on real instances from a major airline and having up to 14,014 itineraries, 646 flights, and 202 aircraft provide evidence of the proposed approach's efficacy. In particular, we find that the average deviation from a conservative bound is at most equal to 0.6%.

Keywords: Mixed-integer programming, Compact formulation, Robustness, Proximity search

5.1 Introduction

An airline schedule is a result of a comprehensive planning process known as airline schedule planning. It entails identifying profit-maximizing schedules for flights, aircraft, crews, and other operational resources. This is an intricate problem that involves organizational and operational restrictions, as well as marketing restrictions. The complexity of the problem grows with the size of the airline company (large airline companies operate thousands of flights with hundreds of crews and aircraft). By necessity, practitioners usually break down the airline scheduling problem into three manageable subproblems:

1. *The fleet assignment problem* matches aircraft types to flight legs in the airline's network to maximize the total expected profit. Restrictions on passenger demand, fleet composition, and aircraft seat capacities must be considered when solving this problem, although these considerations pose a tremendous computational challenge [37].
2. *The aircraft maintenance routing problem* generates feasible maintenance rotations for aircraft of each type while maintaining consistency with the fleet assignment output [1]. It should allow an aircraft to undergo a periodic maintenance check after accumulating a specified number of flying hours.

3. *The crew scheduling problem* determines a flight attendant's (cockpit and cabin) cost-minimizing assignment to scheduled flight legs. The solution is a schedule that specifies the sequence of flights to be executed by crew subject to several work-rule requirements established by the *Federal Aviation Administration* and union contracts [12].

Ordinarily, these problems are solved in sequence rather than in an integrated manner, chiefly due to computer technology and solution algorithms' limitations. However, such an implementation is unwanted. It might create infeasible solutions or generate higher-cost schedules. Instead, improved solutions can be produced by the judicious employment of integrated models and solutions techniques while at the same time being aware of the additional complexity that emerges.

Although these considerations alone pose a tremendous challenge for airline planners, they are often exacerbated by environmental uncertainties. Airline schedules are subject to unforeseeable disruptions impeding their implementation. Disruptions occur because of bad weather conditions, late-arriving passengers, or unplanned maintenance, and all weave their way through the airline network prompting more severe delays. Thereby, airlines employ operations controllers to repair their schedules by reassigning resources (i.e., aircraft, crews) and adjusting flight departures. The process undertaken by operations controllers to achieve this goal is called schedule recovery, albeit they can be running out of room for maneuvering when resources are scarce. However, it is more prudent to consider schedule perturbations during the airline planning process. Robust planning techniques create plans that are (i) easy to repair once disrupted, or (ii) less susceptible to disruptions [26].

The development of efficient airline schedules suggests considering simultaneously the subproblems' inter-dependencies and the impact of disruptive events. We want to formulate a problem that explicitly accommodates robustness considerations while integrating several stages of the airline schedule planning problem. Thus, we propose a nonlinear compact formulation for a robust airline scheduling problem that combines fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing problems. It embodies realistic functional restrictions such as itinerary-based demands, mandated aircraft maintenance requirements, and a wide variety of crew work rules. The formulation adopts a node-arc flow network representation which, in contrast to traditional set partitioning or set covering formulations, yields a polynomial number of variables and constraints. The model is initially non-linear, but the linearization relaxation technique of Sherali, Adams, and Driscoll [35] is used to derive an equivalent linear mode. The model incorporates two robustness policies: (i) crew to follow aircraft, and (ii) re-allocation of buffer times, which allow for better delay absorption. The objective function maximizes an aggregated sum of revenues minus operating costs and robustness penalties that discourage aircraft changes and short connections.

Although the proposed formulation is compact and can be solved using a general-purpose solver, excessive computation times are needed to derive proof of optimality. We design a matheuristic solution framework that hybridizes a decomposition approach and a proximity search [17]. The decomposition approach involves a two-phase optimization-based heuristic. The first phase is a mixed-integer programming (MIP) relaxation of the full problem. Motivated by the idea that pairing costs and robustness penalties do not need to be known precisely to find feasible fleeting decisions, integrality is relaxed except for the fleet assignment variables. Then, given the fleet assignment solutions, the reduced problem of aircraft routing and crew pairing is partitioned into a sub-problem sequence, one for each aircraft family, and solved while explicitly accommodating robustness considerations. Thereafter, the proximity search iteratively improves the initial solution by adjusting binary decisions (flipping their values from zero to one and vice-versa). In each iteration, a new solution is accepted, provided that it satisfies a cut-off constraint on the objective function. Upper and lower bounds are computed to assess solutions' quality.

Computational experiments on realistic data obtained from a major US airline carrier are performed. The solutions of the matheuristic are compared with the optimal solutions, whenever available, and with the upper bounds otherwise. We show that instances with up to 14,014 itineraries, 646 flights, and 202 aircraft can be solved in a relatively short time. Moreover, we compare solutions obtained by robust and non-robust models using several robustness measures, showing the benefits of using a robust approach over the classical non-robust one.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we review the literature on both robust and non-robust integrated airline scheduling models. In Section 3, we describe the robust integrated fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing problem. We present in Section 4 the compact mathematical formulation, first in its original nonlinear form, and then after being linearized. The matheuristic solution approach is described in Section 5. The results of computational tests are reported in Section 6, followed by concluding remarks in Section 7.

5.2 Literature review

In this section, we outline contributions to integrated airline scheduling models. We focus on the integration of three operational stages: fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing. We discuss some of the non-robust integrated models, starting from the earliest ones, then move to the robust ones. For an exhaustive survey, we refer to Eltoukhy, Chan, and Chung [16].

5.2.1 Non-robust integrated models

While numerous contributions have successfully integrated two stages of the airline scheduling problem, very few have proposed models that effectively integrate the three stages, i.e., fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing. Sandhu and Klabjan [32] presented a *time-space network* model that completely integrates the fleet assignment and crew pairing decisions, but not aircraft maintenance decisions. An aggregated plane-count constraint ensures the aircraft rotation feasibility, i.e., not using more aircraft than available. The authors proposed two solution methodologies based on using Lagrangian relaxation with column generation and using Benders decomposition. They are tested on four real-world data sets with up to four fleet families and 942 flight legs. Later, Papadakos [28] presented a set-partitioning formulation to model the integrated problem of minimizing the total cost of fleet assignment, aircraft maintenance routing, and crew pairings. The author considered a leg-based representation of passenger demand. The resulting model was solved using a Benders decomposition method and a column generation technique. Pareto-optimal cuts [24] were added in conjunction with the Benders subproblem to eliminate degenerate solutions, while pricing cuts were heuristically derived to accelerate the column generation process. The authors tested their model on realistic data instances, where the largest solved instance scheduled 700 legs and six fleet types. The integration of the three scheduling stages achieved a reduction in operational costs of 24 million US dollars compared to the sequential approach.

Salazar-González [31] investigated an integrated fleet assignment, aircraft routing, crew pairing problem, and crew rostering problem. An arc-based integer programming formulation of the vehicle routing problem with driver changes was adapted to solve the problem. In this representation, vehicles stand for aircraft, and drivers represent crews. Besides, maintenance tasks are assumed to occur overnight, thereby dropping their associated constraints in the formulation. The author first employed a heuristic algorithm to enumerate crew routes and later solved a reduced fleet assignment aircraft routing problem using mathematical programming. The rostering problem was solved a posteriori for each crew group. However, feasible crew schedules are not always guaranteed for the resulting solution.

Cacchiani and Salazar-González [8] proposed two mixed-integer linear programming formulations that integrate fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing. Aircraft maintenance requirements were also considered. The first formulation, called the *path-path* model, uses a set-partitioning representation to describe both aircraft routes and crew pairings. In the second formulation, called the *arc-path* model, a node-arc representation is used to model the aircraft routing part, while a set-partitioning representation describes the crew pairing part. In both models, the objective function minimizes a weighted sum of the number of aircraft routes, crew pairings, and the crew waiting times between consecutive flights. The conducted experiments showed that the *arc-path* formulation outperforms the *path-path* formulation. Cacchiani and Salazar-González [7] extended the work by introducing time windows to the legs' departure times. Such flexibility within the airline scheduling model may well generate even greater cost savings. As demonstrated by the computational experiments, retiming provides, on average, 11.87% of savings when juxtaposed with the baseline solution.

Finally, Shao, Sherali, and Haouari [34] proposed an integrated model that incorporates the fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing problems within a single framework. Their model conservatively includes operational considerations, such as itinerary-based demands and other mandated aircraft and crew requirements. A Benders decomposition approach, along with several acceleration strategies, was used to solve the resulting formulation.

5.2.2 Robust integrated models

Robust models in airline scheduling seek to attribute, at the planning stage, some features into the planned airline schedules that hedge against unforeseen events. We distinguish in this regard between two lines of studies from the literature. The first is concerned with *absorption robustness*. It aims to maintain feasible airline schedules in case of small-scale disruptions. The other is concerned with designing schedules and rotations that can easily fit recovery strategies in the event of a disruption. This discipline is often called *recovery robustness* [10].

We first consider absorption robustness. The work of Mercier and Soumis [27] revolves around schedule retiming in an integrated aircraft routing and crew scheduling framework. By adjusting flight departure times, the authors allowed longer transfer time on critical connections, thus reducing passengers' misconnections. Lee, Lee, and Tan [23] also incorporated robustness in aircraft rotations and crew pairings by schedule retiming. The problem is formulated as a multi-objective programming problem, where the aggregate objective function accounts for several robustness measures to be optimized. Ben Ahmed, Zeghal Mansour, and Haouari [2], Ben Ahmed et al. [3], and Ben Ahmed, Zeghal Mansour, and Haouari [4] and Cacchiani and Salazar-González [7] demonstrated that applying this strategy is highly effective.

Dück et al. [13] introduced a stochastic model for aircraft routing and crew scheduling to assign schedule slacks between flight connections that are most prone to delay propagation. The values of allocated slacks are calibrated by the delay scenarios used. Dunbar, Froyland, and Wu [14, 15] solved the integrated aircraft routing and crew scheduling problem to minimize delays that are transferred between late-running aircraft and crews, assuming deterministic and stochastic delay information, respectively. Cadarso and Marín [9] used slack reallocation to reduce the number of misconnected passengers when solving the schedule design and fleet assignment problem. Jamili [21] integrated schedule design, fleet assignment, and aircraft routing problems and designed a simulated annealing-based heuristic to solve them.

We finally consider recovery robustness. Burke et al. [6] created schedules and aircraft rotations that promote aircraft swap opportunities. A *swap point* is defined as a prolonged overlap between two grounded flights that enables a possible exchange of their aircraft. The authors demonstrated that maximizing these opportunities within a schedule could result in improved operational performance. Gao, Johnson, and Smith [18] proposed a model that integrates fleet assignment and crew pairing and imposes station purity. The concept of station purity can increase swap opportunities by limiting the number of fleet types and crew bases allowed to serve each airport. Rosenberger, Johnson, and Nemhauser [29] created fleet assignments and aircraft rotations with short cycles. The main goal is to allow airlines, given a disruption, to cancel a relatively small number of legs while maintaining a functioning schedule. Cordeau et al. [11] designed aircraft rotations and crew pairings where crews follow aircraft on short connections. The authors put forward that crews changing from one aircraft to another are more likely to be delayed. Computational experiments carried on realistic data instances showed that embedding this feature is both efficient and cost-effective. Recognizing this perspective, numerous contributions have also restricted the number of crews changing aircraft. Weide, Ryan, and Ehrgott [38], Ruther et al. [30], and Ben Ahmed, Zeghal Mansour, and Haouari [5] provide examples of restricting the number of crews changing aircraft.

5.3 Problem description

We introduce first some key definitions that shall be used throughout this paper.

- Aircraft type: a certain model of aircraft. All aircraft of the same type share the same cockpit configuration and number of seats in each compartment.
- Aircraft family: a set of aircraft types that share common cockpit configuration. For example, the Airbus A320 family includes variants of A318, A319, A320 and A321. A qualified cockpit crew can serve only one aircraft family.
- Maintenance checks: mandatory periodic inspections that have to be done on aircraft after accumulating a specific maximum flying time. These inspections can be carried out only in specific airports, called maintenance stations.
- Itinerary: a sequence of one or more flight legs traversed by a passenger from the passenger's origin to the passenger's destination.
- Base station: an airport at which the airline permanently bases aircraft and crew and from where it operates routes. Both aircraft and personnel return to the base at the end of the rotation.
- Duty: a single workday of a crew, composed of a sequence of flight legs with short rest periods, or sits, separating them.
- Pairing: a sequence of duty periods with overnight rests between consecutive periods. Each pairing begins and ends at the same station (the base station).

The robust integrated fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing problem assigns aircraft and crews to flights based on the following considerations:

- Each flight is covered exactly by one aircraft route and one crew pairing.
- Each aircraft route and each crew pairing should be periodic and thereby repeat themselves every day.
- Each aircraft route must be maintenance feasible. That is, the following restrictions hold: (1) the route must start and finish in the same maintenance station; (2) the route duration must exceed the time needed for performing a maintenance check; and (3) the total flying time does not exceed a specified time limit.
- The number of aircraft used does not exceed the number of aircraft available of each type.
- Each crew pairing, along with its duties, should satisfy all legal and structural restrictions. These restrictions are the following: (1) minimum and maximum sit-time between two consecutive flights; (2) maximum flying time between two consecutive rests; (3) maximum number of landings between two consecutive rests; (4) maximum time away from base for crews; and (5) maximum number of duties in a pairing.
- The total number of required crews should not exceed the available number of crews.
- The resulting schedule incorporates an in-built level of robustness.

5.4 Mathematical formulation

In contrast to the classical set-partitioning formulations, we propose to model the integrated problem using an arc flow formulation. Our model is based on two associated directed graphs: one for aircraft routes and one for crew pairings. These graphs are adapted from Haouari, Shao, and Sherali [19] and Haouari, Zeghal Mansour, and Sherali [20], respectively. Both graphs are described below.

5.4.1 Aircraft routing graph

We are given a set of *daily* flights L , a set of stations S , and a set of aircraft families F . A set K of aircraft types can be partitioned into subsets for each aircraft family $f \in F$, with K_f being the subset of aircraft types belonging to family f . For each aircraft type $k \in K$, we are given the turnaround time τ_k , the duration of a maintenance check M_k , the number of available aircraft N_k , and the associated set of maintenance stations, S_k . For each flight $j \in L$, we denote by t_j the corresponding flying time, T_j^D and T_j^A the departure and arrival times, respectively, and S_j^D and S_j^A the departure and arrival stations, respectively. Time parameters are expressed in minutes and are defined within the time interval $[0, 1440)$.

We define an associated digraph $G = (V, A)$ wherein each node $j \in V$ represents a flight leg. Furthermore, for each aircraft of type $k \in K$, we define a corresponding arc set A_k , where $A \equiv \cup_{k \in K} A_k$, and where each arc $(j, l) \in A_k$ represents a feasible aircraft connection, i.e., an arc $(j, l) \in A_k$ if and only if an aircraft of type $k \in K$ can consecutively serve the flights pertaining to the from-node and the to-node of this arc, respectively denoted as j and l . More specifically, the set of arcs A_k for each $k \in K$, is given by the union of four arc subsets $A_{1,k}$, $A_{2,k}$, $A_{3,k}$, and $A_{4,k}$ that are defined as follows:

- An arc $(j, l) \in A_{1,k}$ if and only if a maintenance check can be planned between the arrival of flight j and the departure of flight l , and both flights are required to be served consecutively on the same day. Hence, $(j, l) \in A_{1,k} \Leftrightarrow (i) S_j^A \equiv S_l^D$; $(ii) S_j^A \in S_k$; and $(iii) T_j^A + M_k \leq T_l^D$.
- An arc $(j, l) \in A_{2,k}$ if and only if a maintenance check can be planned between the arrival of flight j and the departure of flight l , and the same aircraft is required to serve flight leg l the day after serving flight leg j . Hence, $(j, l) \in A_{2,k} \Leftrightarrow (i) S_j^A \equiv S_l^D$; $(ii) S_j^A \in S_k$; and $T_l^D < T_j^A + M_k \leq T_l^D + 1,440$.
- An arc $(j, l) \in A_{3,k}$ if and only if a maintenance check cannot be planned between the arrival of flight j and the departure of flight l , and both flights are required to be served consecutively on the same day. Hence, $(j, l) \in A_{3,k} \Leftrightarrow (i) S_j^A \equiv S_l^D$; $(ii) S_j^A \notin S_k$ or $T_l^D < T_j^A + M_k$; and $(iii) T_j^A + \tau_k \leq T_l^D$.
- An arc $(j, l) \in A_{4,k}$ if and only if a maintenance check cannot be planned between the arrival of flight j and the departure of flight l , and the same aircraft is required to serve flight leg l the day

after serving flight leg j . Hence, $(j, l) \in A_{4,k} \Leftrightarrow (i) S_j^A \equiv S_l^D$; (ii) $S_j^A \notin S_k$ or $T_j^A + M_k > T_l^D$; and (iii) $T_l^D < T_j^A + \tau_k \leq T_l^D + 1, 440$.

We denote by $A_k^M \equiv A_{1,k} \cup A_{2,k}$ the set of maintenance arcs for each aircraft of type $k \in K$, and $A_k^{NM} \equiv A_k \setminus A_k^M$, the set of non-maintenance arcs. Arcs that belong to $A_{2,k} \cup A_{4,k}$ correspond to wraparound ground connections that link pairs of flights that are flown on two consecutive days. On the other hand, connections that belong to $A_{1,k} \cup A_{3,k}$ correspond to pairs of consecutive flights that depart on the same day. Let $n_k, k \in K$, denote the number of wraparound flights in L , that is, those flights whose arrival time occurs on the day after their departure day.

To incorporate itinerary-based flight demands, we use the following notation:

- Π : set of all itineraries.
- $\Pi_j \subset \Pi$: the subset of itineraries that include flight $j \in L$.
- H : set of all fare classes.
- C_{kh} : capacity of aircraft of type $k \in K$ to accommodate passengers for fare class $h \in H$.
- $\bar{\pi}_{ph}$: mean demand for fare class $h \in H$ within itinerary $p \in \Pi$.
- f_{ph} : estimated revenue for fare class $h \in H$ within itinerary $p \in \Pi$.

In addition, we adopt the same fleet assignment cost definition used by Mansour Zeghal et al. [25], which incorporates the fixed operating charges as well as the opportunity cost due to *spilled passengers*. Accordingly, we denote the cost associated with assigning an aircraft of type $k \in K$ to flight leg j as c_{jk} , which can be expressed as

$$c_{jk} = \bar{c}_{jk} + \sum_{h \in H} o_{jh} \left(\sum_{p \in \Pi_j} \bar{\pi}_{ph} - C_{kh} \right)^+, \quad (1.1)$$

where \bar{c}_{jk} denotes the fixed cost of assigning fleet type k to flight j , o_{jh} represents the opportunity cost per *spilled passenger* on flight j incurred where the expected demand for fare class h exceeds the capacity of the assigned aircraft, and $(\cdot)^+ \equiv \max\{0, \cdot\}$.

5.4.2 Crew pairing graph

Let $L^D \subset L$ denote the set of flights that depart from the base station, and $L^A \subset L$ the set of flights that arrive to the base station. Furthermore, we provide the following additional notation.

- s^{MIN}/s^{MAX} : Minimum/maximum sit-time between two consecutive flights within a duty.
- φ^{MAX} : Maximum flying time within a duty.
- λ^{MAX} : Maximum duty duration. We assume that the longest flight duration is shorter than the maximum duty duration (i.e., $t_j \leq \lambda^{MAX}, j \in V$).
- l^{MIN}/l^{MAX} : Minimum/maximum layover duration between two consecutive duties within a pairing (l^{MIN} is also the minimum rest time after a completing a pairing).
- η^{MIN}/η^{MAX} : Minimum/maximum duration of a pairing (i.e. time away from base).
- μ^{MAX} : Maximum number of landings within a duty.
- ν^{MAX} : Maximum number of duties within a pairing.

The crew pairing graph $G^{CP} = (\bar{V}, B)$ is defined as follows. The node set \bar{V} is derived by adding a dummy start node to V . That is, we have $\bar{V} \equiv V \cup \{0\}$, where the dummy node 0 represents both the start and the end of a pairing. We define for each aircraft family $f \in F$ a corresponding arc set B_f , where $B \equiv \cup_{f \in F} B_f$, and where each arc $(j, l) \in B_f$ represents a feasible connection, i.e., an arc $(j, l) \in B_f$ if and only if a crew that is eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$ can consecutively serve the flights pertaining to node j and node l . Hence, an arc $(j, l) \in B_f$ exists if and only if the following compatibility conditions hold: (i) The arrival station S_j^A of flight j coincides with the departure station S_l^D of flight l , (ii) the total connection time $(T_l^D - T_j^A)$ is greater than or equal to the minimum sit-time and smaller than the maximum layover duration, and (iii) the same crew that consecutively serves flights j and l is eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$. In addition, we define for each aircraft family $f \in F$ an arc $(0, j)$ for each flight node $j \in L^D$ that departs from the crew base, and an arc $(j, 0)$ for each flight node $j \in L^A$ that arrives to the crew base. The corresponding arc subsets are referred to as B_f^D and B_f^A , respectively.

The set of arcs B_f includes, for each $f \in F$, the subsets $B_{1,f}$ and $B_{2,f}$ that are defined as follows:

1. An arc $(j, l) \in B_{1,f}$ if and only if legs j and l can be served consecutively by a crew eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$ during the same duty period. That is, each arc $(j, l) \in B_{1,f}$ corresponds to a short rest period within a duty. Hence, $(j, l) \in B_{1,f} \Leftrightarrow$ (1) the sit-time s_{jlf} is bounded by aircraft turn-time and the maximum allowed sit-time (i.e., $s_{jlf} \in [\tau_f, s^{MAX}]$); (2) the maximum flying time with a duty is satisfied (i.e., $t_j + t_l \leq \varphi^{MAX}$), and (3) the maximum duty duration is satisfied (i.e., $t_j + t_l + s_{jlf} \leq \lambda^{MAX}$), where the sit-time s_{jlf} is computed as follows:

- $s_{jlf} = T_l^D - T_j^A$, if $T_l^D > T_j^A$, in this case the arrival of flight i and the departure of flight j occur on the same day.
- $s_{jlf} = T_l^D + 1,440 - T_j^A$, if $T_l^D < T_j^A$, in this case the arrival of flight j and the departure of flight l occur on two consecutive days.

2. An arc $(j, l) \in B_{2,f}$ connects two consecutive flights j and l that can be performed consecutively by a crew eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$ in two consecutive duty periods within the same pairing. Therefore, each arc $(j, l) \in B_{2,f}$ corresponds to a layover within a multi-day pairing, where the layover time l_{jlf} is computed as follows:

- $l_{jlf} = T_l^D - T_j^A$, if $T_j^A + l^{MIN} \leq T_l^D \leq T_j^A + l^{MAX}$, in this case the arrival of flight j and the departure of flight l occur on the same day.
- $l_{jlf} = T_l^D + 1,440 - T_j^A$, if $T_j^A + l^{MIN} \leq T_l^D + 1,440 \leq T_j^A + l^{MAX}$, in this case the arrival of flight j occurs one day before the departure of flight l .
- $l_{jlf} = T_l^D + 2,880 - T_j^A$, if $T_j^A + l^{MIN} \leq T_l^D + 2,880 \leq T_j^A + l^{MAX}$, in this case the arrival of flight j occurs two days before the departure of flight l .

Hence, $(j, l) \in B_{2,f} \Leftrightarrow$ (1) the layover duration is bounded by the minimum and the maximum layover time (i.e., $l_{jlf} \in [l^{MIN}, l^{MAX}]$), and (2) the maximum duration of a pairing is satisfied (i.e., $t_j + t_l + l_{jlf} \leq \eta^{MAX}$). Finally, we denote by nb_f^{crew} the number of crews eligible to serve an aircraft family $f \in F$.

5.4.3 Robustness policies

Airlines create their flight schedules assuming that every flight leg will depart and arrive as planned. However, schedules often turn out to be unstable because of delays and cancellations. As Lan, Clarke, and Barnhart [22] pointed out, even before constructing airline schedules, it is essential to apply robust optimization techniques to minimize the effects of potential delays.

We first introduce the concept of short and critical connections as introduced by Ben Ahmed, Zeghal Mansour, and Haouari [5]. If two flights are consecutively served by the same resource (i.e., crew or aircraft), the time between the ready time of the resource incurred after completing the inbound flight and the departure of the outbound flight is called *idle time*. For each aircraft connection $(j, l) \in A_k$, $k \in K$, we define the aircraft idle time I_{jlk} as the difference between the departure time of the outbound flight l and the aircraft ready time after performing the inbound flight j . That is,

$$I_{jlk} = \begin{cases} T_l^D - T_j^A - \tau_k, & \text{if } T_l^D \geq T_j^A + \tau_k \\ T_l^D + 1400 - T_j^A - \tau_k, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k. \quad (1.2)$$

Similarly, we define for each crew connection $(j, l) \in B_{1,f}, f \in F$ the crew idle time as the difference between the departure time of flight l and the crew ready time, given by,

$$I_{jlf} = \begin{cases} T_l^D - T_j^A - s^{MIN}, & \text{if } T_l^D \geq T_j^A \\ T_l^D + 1400 - T_j^A - s^{MIN}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad f \in F, \quad (j, l) \in B_{1,f}. \quad (1.3)$$

A crew connection $(j, l) \in B_{1,f}, f \in F$ is called short if $I_{jlf} < 0$. That is, the sit-time is shorter than the mandated minimum sit time. In this case, the connection is crew-feasible only if both flights are assigned to the same aircraft. We denote by B_f^S the sets containing all connections of this type. Given again a connection $(j, l) \in B_{1,f}, f \in F$, the connection is said critical if it is a feasible connection and its idle time is smaller than a given threshold \bar{T}_c that corresponds to a preferred cushion time. If a crew connection is critical, crew still can change aircraft. Similarly, a feasible aircraft connection $(j, l) \in A_k, k \in K$, is called critical if its idle time is smaller than a specific cushion time \bar{T}_a . While planning for short and critical connections allows a maximum utilization of resources, they are prone to delay propagation and must be avoided when unnecessary.

In our approach, we seek to maximize the robustness of airline schedules by implementing two policies: (1) penalizing shorter-than-threshold connections and, (2) promoting schedules where crews follow aircraft. Firstly, we impose a penalty term for each critical connection. We define artificial penalties γ_{jlk} and γ_{jlf} , associated to each aircraft connection, $(j, l) \in A_k$ and each crew connection $(j, l) \in B_{1,f}$, respectively. More precisely,

$$\gamma_{jlk} = \begin{cases} m(\bar{T}_a - I_{jlk}), & \text{if } I_{jlk} < \bar{T}_a \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad (1.4)$$

$$\gamma_{jlf} = \begin{cases} m(\bar{T}_c - I_{jlf}), & \text{if } 0 \leq I_{jlf} < \bar{T}_c \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad f \in F, \quad (j, l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (1.5)$$

where m is a multiplier that accounts for the degree of penalization.

The penalty functions increase linearly with decreasing idle times and are null for those above the preset threshold. By minimizing these penalties in the objective function, we build buffers into the schedule while maintaining the model feasibility.

Second, we restrict the number of connections where crews change aircraft during a duty period. The rule is strictly enforced for short connections, and it is described in the mathematical formulation in Section 4. However, it is relaxed for regular connections, and a fixed penalty term ρ is imposed whenever the crew changes aircraft. The rule applies for all types of connections, independently of their buffer times, thereby adding a second level of protection to the schedule.

5.4.4 Model description

Before presenting our integrated model, we introduce the following decisions variables:

w_{jk} : binary variable that equals 1 if flight leg $j \in L$ is assigned to an aircraft of type $k \in K$, and 0 otherwise.

x_{jlk} : binary variable that takes the value 1 if arc $(j, l) \in A_k, k \in K$ is selected, and 0 otherwise.

u_j : total accumulated flying hours for the aircraft serving flight leg $j \in L$ since its last maintenance check.

π_{ph} : number of passengers accepted for itinerary $p \in \Pi$ within fare class $h \in H$.

y_{jlf} : binary variable that equals 1 if arc $(j, l) \in B_f, f \in F$ is selected, and 0 otherwise.

z_{jlf} : binary variable that equals 1 if a crew follows an aircraft on arc $(j, l) \in B_f \cap A, f \in F$.

μ_{jff} : total number of landings after serving flight leg $j \in L$ with a crew eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$.

φ_{jff} : total accumulated duty flight duration after serving flight leg $j \in L$ with a crew eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$.

λ_{jff} : total accumulated duty duration after serving flight leg $j \in L$ with a crew eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$.

ν_{jff} : total accumulated number of duties after serving flight leg $j \in L$ with a crew eligible to aircraft

family $f \in F$.

η_{jf} : total accumulated time away from base after serving flight leg $j \in L$ with a crew eligible to aircraft family $f \in F$.

d_{jf} : integer variable that corresponds to the duration (in days) of the pairing that ends with flight $j \in L$, and whose crew is eligible to an aircraft family $f \in F$.

5.4.5 A nonlinear MIP formulation

Based on the above notation, we formulate the robust integrated fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing problem as follows:

Objective function The objective function (2.1) maximizes the overall profit given by the total revenue, minus the fleet assignment costs minus a sum of non-robustness penalties. The penalties are incurred by including (i) critical connections in aircraft routes, (ii) critical connections in crew pairings, and (iii) connections where crews do not follow aircraft.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max f(w, x, y, z) = & \sum_{p \in \Pi} \sum_{h \in H} f_{ph} \pi_{ph} - \sum_{j \in L} \sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} w_{jk} \\
 & - \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in (B_f \setminus B_f^S)} \rho(y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}) - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} \gamma_{ljk} x_{ljk} \\
 & - \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \gamma_{jlf} (y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}).
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

Aircraft routes feasibility Constraints (2.2) require each flight leg to be covered by exactly one fleet type. Constraints (2.3) and (2.4) ensure that each flight has exactly one predecessor and one successor, respectively, both of which are assigned to the same aircraft type. Hence, together with x being binary-valued, these restrictions induce the solution to be composed of cyclic rotations, where each aircraft periodically serves the same sequence of flights. The output schedule can thereby repeated an indefinite number of times. Note that since each rotation describes a cyclic use of a particular aircraft of some type, the traditional flow conservation constraints at stations are automatically satisfied. For each aircraft type, the nonlinear constraints (2.5)-(2.6) together with (2.7) enforce the total flying time restrictions. Constraint (2.8) requires that the total number of aircraft in service should not exceed the fleet size.

$$\sum_{k \in K} w_{jk} = 1, \quad j \in L, \tag{2.2}$$

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} = w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \tag{2.3}$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} x_{jlk} = w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \tag{2.4}$$

$$u_j x_{ljk} = t_j x_{ljk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (l,j) \in A_k^M, \tag{2.5}$$

$$u_j x_{ljk} = (u_l + t_j) x_{ljk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (l,j) \in A_k^{NM}, \tag{2.6}$$

$$t_j \leq u_j \leq t_k^{max}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \tag{2.7}$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in A_{2,k}^M \cup A_{4,k}^M} x_{jlk} \leq N_k - n_k, \quad k \in K. \tag{2.8}$$

Itineraries feasibility Constraints (2.9) ensure that the total number of passengers traveling on a flight is no more than the capacity available for the assigned aircraft. Constraint (2.10) guarantees that the total number of passengers accepted on any particular itinerary for each fare class does not exceed the total expected demand. Following Sherali, Bae, and Haouari [36], we write:

$$\sum_{h \in H} \sum_{p \in \Pi_j} \pi_{ph} \leq \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{k \in K_f} \tilde{C}_{jk} w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \tag{2.9}$$

where $\tilde{C}_{jk} \equiv \min\{C_k, \sum_{p \in \Pi_j} \bar{\pi}_{ph}\}$, $j \in L$, $k \in K$.

$$0 \leq \pi_{ph} \leq \bar{\pi} \equiv \min\{\bar{\pi}_{ph}, \max_{k \in K} C_k\}, \quad p \in \Pi, \quad h \in H. \quad (2.10)$$

Duties feasibility Constraints (2.11)-(2.12) require that each flight is covered by an eligible crew. Constraints (2.13) impose that the number of start arcs is equal to the number of end arcs. Hence together with (2.37), these three restrictions enforce building cyclic crew pairings. Constraints (2.14)-(2.15) and (2.20) guarantee the restriction on the maximum number of landings within a duty. Constraints (2.16)-(2.17) and (2.21) enforce the restriction on the maximum flying time within a duty. Constraints (2.18)-(2.19) and (2.22) impose the restriction on the maximum duty duration.

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in B_f} y_{ljf} = \sum_{k \in K_f} w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.11)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} y_{jlf} = \sum_{k \in K_f} w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.12)$$

$$\sum_{(0,j) \in B_f^D} y_{0,jf} - \sum_{(j,0) \in B_f^A} y_{j,0} = 0, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.13)$$

$$\mu_{jff} y_{ljf} = y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^D, \quad (2.14)$$

$$\mu_{jff} y_{ljf} = (\mu_{lf} + 1) y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.15)$$

$$\varphi_{jff} y_{ljf} = t_j y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^D, \quad (2.16)$$

$$\varphi_{jff} y_{ljf} = (\varphi_{lf} + t_j) y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.17)$$

$$\lambda_{jff} y_{ljf} = t_j y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^D, \quad (2.18)$$

$$\lambda_{jff} y_{ljf} = (\lambda_{lf} + s_{ljf} + t_j) y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.19)$$

$$1 \leq \mu_{jff} \leq \mu^{MAX}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.20)$$

$$t_j \leq \varphi_{jff} \leq \varphi^{MAX}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.21)$$

$$t_j \leq \lambda_{jff} \leq \lambda^{MAX}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F. \quad (2.22)$$

Pairings feasibility Constraints (2.23)-(2.25) and (2.29) ensure the restriction on the maximum number of duties within a pairing. Similarly, constraints (2.26)-(2.28) and (2.31) enforce the restriction on the maximum time away from base. Constraint (2.30) expresses the minimum duration of a pairing.

$$\nu_{jff} y_{0,jf} = y_{0,jf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (0,j,f) \in B_f^D, \quad (2.23)$$

$$\nu_{jff} y_{ljf} = \nu_{lf} y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.24)$$

$$\nu_{jff} y_{ljf} = (\nu_{lf} + 1) y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (2.25)$$

$$\eta_{jff} y_{ljf} = (\eta_{lf} + s_{ljf} + t_j) y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.26)$$

$$\eta_j y_{0,jf} = t_j y_{0,jf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (0,j,f) \in B_f^D, \quad (2.27)$$

$$\eta_{jff} y_{ljf} = (\eta_{lf} + l_{ljf} + t_j) y_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (l,j) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (2.28)$$

$$1 \leq \nu_{jff} \leq \nu^{MAX}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.29)$$

$$\eta_{jff} \geq \eta_f^{MIN} y_{j,0}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,0) \in B_f^A, \quad (2.30)$$

$$t_j \leq \eta_{jff} \leq \eta^{MAX}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F. \quad (2.31)$$

Number of available crews Constraints (2.32)-(2.33) require that the total number of crews in service should not exceed the available crew qualified for the considered aircraft family. The validity of these latter constraints follow from the fact that the if a pairing ends with flight j then the corresponding duration is $\eta_j y_{j0}$. After adding the post-pairing (mandatory) rest we get a total duration of $(\eta_j y_{j0} + l^{MIN})$ minutes which yields a total duration of $d_j = \left\lceil \frac{\eta_j y_{j0} + l^{MIN}}{D} \right\rceil$ days, where D is equal to 1,440. Since, the all flights are scheduled daily, then this pairing requires d_j crews.

$$\eta_{jff} y_{j0} + l^{MIN} \leq D d_{jf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,0) \in B_f^A, \quad (2.32)$$

$$\sum_{(j,0) \in B_f^A} d_{jf} \leq nb_f^{crew}, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.33)$$

Short and critical connections Constraints (2.34) enforce crew to follow aircraft on short connections. Finally, constraints (2.35)-(2.36) enforce that if $z_{jlf} = 1$ then a crew follows the aircraft on connection $(j, l) \in B \cap A$.

$$y_{jlf} \leq x_{jlk}, \quad f \in F, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j, l) \in B_f^S \cap A_k, \quad (2.34)$$

$$0 \leq z_{jlf} \leq x_{jlk}, \quad f \in F, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j, l) \in B \cap A_k, \quad (2.35)$$

$$0 \leq z_{jlf} \leq y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j, l) \in B \cap A_k. \quad (2.36)$$

Integrality and non-negativity constraints The integrality conditions of variables are given by constraints (2.37).

$$(x, y, z, w) \text{ binary.} \quad (2.37)$$

5.4.6 Model linearization

To derive an equivalent linear representation of our model, we apply the relaxation-linearization technique [35]. We define new variables that shall substitute to the nonlinear terms. These variables are:

$$\alpha_{jlk} = u_j x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad (2.38)$$

$$\beta_{jlf} = \mu_{jf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j, l) \in B_f, \quad (2.39)$$

$$\chi_{jlf} = \varphi_j y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j, l) \in B_f, \quad (2.40)$$

$$\zeta_{jlf} = \lambda_j y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j, l) \in B_f, \quad (2.41)$$

$$\sigma_{jlf} = \nu_j y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j, l) \in B_f, \quad (2.42)$$

$$\vartheta_{jlf} = \eta_j y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j, l) \in B_f. \quad (2.43)$$

For ease of exposition, the linearization process is described in Appendices A and B. Upon linearization, the equivalent linear model can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \max f(w, x, y, z) = & \sum_{p \in \Pi} \sum_{h \in H} f_{ph} \pi_{ph} - \sum_{j \in L} \sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} w_{jk} \\ & - \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in (B_f \setminus B_f^S)} \rho(y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}) - \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} \gamma_{lk} x_{ljk} \\ & - \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \gamma_{jlf} (y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.44)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{k \in K} w_{jk} = 1, \quad j \in L, \quad (2.45)$$

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} = w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \quad (2.46)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} x_{jlk} = w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \quad (2.47)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} \alpha_{jlk} = t_j \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} + \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k^{NM}} \alpha_{ljk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \quad (2.48)$$

$$t_j x_{jlk} \leq \alpha_{jlk} \leq b_{jl}^k x_{jlk}, \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad k \in K, \quad (2.49)$$

$$\sum_{j \in L} (1 - \sum_{(l,j) \in A_{1,k} \cup A_{3,k}} x_{ljk}) \leq N_k - n_k, \quad k \in K, \quad (2.50)$$

$$\sum_{h \in H} \sum_{p \in \Pi_j} \pi_{ph} \leq \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{k \in K_f} \tilde{C}_{jk} w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad (2.51)$$

$$0 \leq \pi_{ph} \leq \tilde{\pi}, \quad p \in \Pi, \quad h \in H, \quad (2.52)$$

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in B_f} y_{ljf} = \sum_{k \in K_f} w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.53)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} y_{jlf} = \sum_{k \in K_f} w_{jk}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.54)$$

$$\sum_{(0,j,f) \in B_f^D} y_{0,j,f} - \sum_{(j,0,f) \in B_f^A} y_{j,0,f} = 0, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.55)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \beta_{jlf} = 1 + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \beta_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.56)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \beta_{jlf} \leq (\mu^{MAX} - 1)y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.57)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \beta_{jlf} \leq \mu^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^D, \quad (2.58)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \chi_{jlf} = t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \chi_{ljf}, \quad f \in F, \quad j \in L, \quad (2.59)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \chi_{jlf} \leq (\varphi^{MAX} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.60)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \chi_{jlf} \leq \varphi^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^f, \quad (2.61)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \zeta_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} s_{ljf} y_{ljf} + t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \zeta_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.62)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \zeta_{jlf} \leq (\lambda^{MAX} - s_{jlf} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.63)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \zeta_{jlf} \leq \lambda^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^f, \quad (2.64)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \sigma_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_f^D \cup B_{2,f}} y_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_{2,f}} \sigma_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.65)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \sigma_{jlf} \leq (\nu^{MAX} - 1) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (2.66)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \sigma_{jlf} \leq \nu^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_f^f, \quad (2.67)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \vartheta_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} s_{ljf} y_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{2,f}} l_{ljf} y_{ljf} + t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_{2,f}} \vartheta_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.68)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \vartheta_{jlf} \leq (\eta^{MAX} - s_{jlf} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (2.69)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \vartheta_{jlf} \leq (\eta^{MAX} - l_{jlf} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (2.70)$$

$$\vartheta_{j,0,f} + l^{MIN} \leq Dd_{jf}, \quad j \in L^A, \quad f \in F, \quad (2.71)$$

$$y_{ijf} \leq x_{jlk}, \quad f \in F, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j,l) \in B_f^S \cap A_k, \quad (2.72)$$

$$0 \leq z_{jlf} \leq x_{jlk}, \quad f \in F, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j,l) \in B_f \cap A_k, \quad (2.73)$$

$$0 \leq z_{jlf} \leq y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j,l) \in B_f \cap A_k, \quad (2.74)$$

$$(x, y, z, w) \text{ binary.} \quad (2.75)$$

where we have written (2.49) in more compact way using

$$l_{jl}^{tk} = \begin{cases} t_k^{MAX} - t_l, & \text{if } k \in K \text{ and } (j,l) \in A_k^{NM}, \\ t_k^{MAX}, & \text{if } k \in K \text{ and } (j,l) \in A_k^M. \end{cases} \quad (2.76)$$

Remark 5.4.1. The non-robust counterpart of the robust integrated airline planning problem model can be obtained by dropping constraints (2.72)-(2.74) from Model (2.44)-(2.75). The objective problem function is to maximize the earned revenues minus aircraft assignment costs and crew pairing costs. Crew pairing costs are typically evaluated using a specific metric denoted by the flight-time credit [33]. The flight-time credit is the difference between the pairing's duration and the block time (flying time). In what follows, it is estimated as the sum of idle times (that is, a sum of sit-times and layovers). Hence, the non-robust

objective function is:

$$\max f_n(w, x, y) = \sum_{p \in \Pi} \sum_{h \in H} f_{ph} \pi_{ph} - \sum_{j \in L} \sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} w_{jk} - \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in B_{1,f}} s_{jlf} y_{jlf} - \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in B_{2,f}} l_{jlf} y_{jlf} \quad (2.77)$$

5.5 Solution methodology

Solving the robust integrated fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing model poses a formidable computational challenge. Consequently, we adopt the matheuristic solution method that is depicted in Figure 5.1. The basic idea is to decompose the problem into more manageable subproblems that are solved as independent MIPs, thereby obtaining a good feasible solution that is subsequently iteratively improved. Specifically, we initially generate a feasible solution for the full problem using a restricted master problem. In Step 1 of our approach in Figure 5.1, we construct a restricted master problem (*MP*) by dropping robustness variables and constraints from MIP model (2.44)-(2.75). We update the objective function to maximize the overall profit given by the total revenue, minus the fleet assignment costs, and it is given by:

$$\max f_1(w) = \sum_{p \in \Pi} \sum_{h \in H} f_{ph} \pi_{ph} - \sum_{j \in L} \sum_{k \in K} c_{jk} w_{jk}. \quad (3.1)$$

Figure 5.1: The matheuristic for the robust integrated fleet assignment, aircraft routing and crew pairing model.

In Step 2, we solve a relaxation of the master problem (*Rel-MP*), where only the integrality of the fleet decisions w is retained. Any feasible solution to the relaxation induces a feasible solution to the original problem, although it does not take heed of the robustness criteria. Indeed, retaining the routing and pairing requirements in a relaxed form ensures that there are compatible feasible aircraft routes and crew schedules with the w -variables. The optimal value of *Rel-MP* yields an upper bound on the original model's optimal value.

Knowing the fleet decision associated with each flight leg enables the restricted problem to be decomposed into a finite set of sub-problems according to aircraft families. Flight legs sharing the same aircraft family are grouped, and their optimal routes and pairings are built simultaneously. The solutions to the latter problems yield a feasible solution to the integrated problem. In Steps 3 and 4, aircraft routes and crew schedules are constructed to create a complete solution to the original problem. Hence, we build, for each aircraft family, a reduced aircraft routing and crew pairing problem. Each subproblem is a

robust integrated crew pairing and aircraft routing problem that inherits the same representation from the integrated model, although the fleet assignment considerations are omitted. The model formulation is detailed in Appendix C. The objective functions minimize all the penalties incurred by violating robustness policies. This will force the crew to follow aircraft as much as possible and concurrently allow for larger connection times. In other words, we solve the integrated aircraft routing and crew pairing problem using the following objective function:

$$\min f_2(x, y, z) = \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in (B_f \setminus B_f^S)} \rho(y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}) + \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} \gamma_{jlk} x_{jlk} + \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \gamma_{jlf} (y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}). \quad (3.2)$$

To derive an enhanced solution, we apply in Step 5, a proximity search algorithm. At each iteration of the algorithm, a derived mixed-integer programming model is used to move within the solution's neighborhood.

A proximity search algorithm. We present an iterative improvement algorithm that adapts the proximity search strategy proposed by Fischetti and Monaci [17]. The algorithm searches for an improved solution by modifying the original problem and solving it using a MIP black-box solver. We use the mathematical model (2.44)-(2.75) to guide the search while preserving the feasibility of aircraft routes and crew pairings.

The proximity search takes as an input the feasible solution generated earlier, henceforth referred to as (w^0, x^0, y^0, z^0) . At each iteration, $(\tilde{w}, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z})$ denotes the problem's current solution. The cut-off constraint given by (3.3) is appended to the original model, where θ is a strictly positive tolerance value that delimits the search space, and $f(w, x, y, z)$ is the problem's objective function.

$$f(w, x, y, z) \geq f(\tilde{w}, \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z}) + \theta. \quad (3.3)$$

The search for a new solution is driven by replacing the problem's objective function (2.44) with a new *proximity function* to be minimized.

$$\min \Delta(w, \tilde{w}) := \sum_{j \in L} \sum_{k \in K | \tilde{w}_{jk} = 0} w_{jk} + \sum_{j \in L} \sum_{k \in K | \tilde{w}_{jk} = 1} (1 - w_{jk}). \quad (3.4)$$

Algorithm 6: The proximity search algorithm

- 1 Let (w^0, x^0, y^0, z^0) be an initial feasible solution. Set $(\tilde{w}) := (w^0)$
 - 2 **repeat**
 - 3 add the cutoff constraint (3.3) to the MIP problem
 - 4 replace the objective function (2.44) by the Hamming distance function $\Delta(w, \tilde{w})$
 - 5 solve the modified problem
 - 6 **if** a new feasible solution (w, x, y, z) is found **then**
 - 7 recenter $\Delta(w, \tilde{w})$ by setting $\tilde{w} := w$
 - 8 **else**
 - 9 go to (12)
 - 10 **end**
 - 11 **until** until a termination criteria is reached;
 - 12 return(\tilde{w})
-

The modified objective function measures the Hamming distance between the binary w - variables and the given \tilde{w} of the current solution. Aircraft routing and crew pairing variables do not show in this definition. Given the problem's hierarchical structure, changing the fleet assignment variables induces distinct routing and pairing variables, but not necessarily the other way around. Accordingly, measuring the change in the fleet assignment variables is more important than the change in any other group of variables. At every iteration, the modified problem is solved by a MIP solver, the new solution is used to recenter the Hamming distance function, and the cut-off constraint is updated. If the modified problem does not have any feasible solutions, then the current solution (\tilde{w}) is within θ of the optimal value of the original problem. Algorithm 6 describes the steps of the proximity search.

5.6 Computational experiments

This section presents computational experiments that were carried out on a test-bed of real instances that were previously used by Shao, Sherali, and Haouari [34]. All runs were made on a desktop computer with an Intel Core i7-8700 3.2 GHz CPU with 16GB RAM and running a 64-bit Windows system. The mathematical model described in Section 5.4.4 and the solution framework described in Section 5.5 were implemented using AMPL and the MIP solver Gurobi 9.0.3 with default settings, except when solving the full model directly, in which case we enable in the solver’s parameters a moderate generation of mixed-integer-rounding (MIR) cuts and flow-cover cuts.

5.6.1 Data description

The instances correspond to several North American flight networks of United Airlines. These instances consider two types of networks, the hub-and-spoke, and the point-to-point, including major airports in the continental United States. In all cases, three aircraft families are presented, namely Airbus 320 series (including fleets of Airbus 319 and 320) and Boeing 757 (including fleets of Boeing 757–200 and 757–300), and a fleet of Boeing 777–200. The instances’ main characteristics are displayed in Table 5.1, where we provide for each instance the number of scheduled flights, the number of stations, the number of arcs, the fleet size for each family, and the number of passengers’ itineraries. The number of arcs shown in Table 5.1 indicates the number of binary variables for each designated fleet type.

Table 5.1: Characteristics of the test instances

Instance	Flights	Stations	Itineraries	Total aircraft arcs			Aircraft count		
				A320	B757	B777	A320	B757	B777
HS1	128	17	1,642	4,728	4,586	4,313	17	17	1
HS2	154	10	1,315	8,679	8,395	8,133	32	19	2
HS3	246	19	3,516	18,673	18,128	17,552	49	31	2
HS4	354	25	6,124	23,742	23,066	22,209	61	44	3
HS5	440	24	7,976	38,587	37,508	36,127	88	55	4
K1	205	11	2,319	10,596	10,327	10,094	42	26	2
K2	282	15	4,275	15,488	15,118	14,736	58	36	3
L1	522	23	9,075	44,435	43,629	41,645	104	64	5
L2	676	33	14,014	62,152	60,614	58,437	134	83	6

Data related to passengers, aircraft fleet, and crew pairing requirements are kept as in Shao, Sherali, and Haouari [34]. We considered the following values to define the penalty terms in the objective function: $m = 100$ and $\rho = 1000$. They were set after running empirical experiments to evaluate their effect on tractability and quality of the problem’s solutions. We set both cushion times \bar{T}_a and \bar{T}_c to 30 minutes.

We set a time limit of 10 hours for solving the full model of the integrated problem. A time limit of 5 hours was imposed on the decomposition procedure and for the proximity search, which yields an aggregated time limit of 10 hours. The proximity search tolerance θ is equal to 0.2% of the starting solution’s objective, and it remains invariable over all iterations.

5.6.2 Results for the exact solution of the integrated problem

We first solve the robust integrated fleet assignment aircraft routing and crew pairing problem and its non-robust counterpart directly using Gurobi. Table 5.2 reports the results for the exact solution of the problem’s robust variant, and Table 5.3 displays those related to the non-robust variant. The tables’ columns display the computing times (in seconds), the model objective function, the returned optimality gap, the fleet assignment for each aircraft family, the passengers’ revenue, and the aircraft assignments’ cost. We provide the robustness penalties for the robust model, respectively the flight-time credit for the non-robust model, both optimized in the objective function.

The integrated models produce mixed results from a numerical perspective, wherein the solver failed to find any feasible solutions for three of the instances within the time limit of 10 hours. The remaining instances were solved within computational times that scale up with the problem size. The average solution time is 4.14 hours for the robust model and 2.69 for the non-robust one. The added complexity resulting from robustness constraints could largely explain the difference in both models’ computational effort.

Table 5.2: Results for the exact solutions of the robust integrated problem

Inst.	CPU (in sec.)	Z^*	Opt. gap	Flights covered by			Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignments cost	Robustness penalties
				A320	B757	B777			
HS1	14,812	-220,016	0.00	71	55	2	1,422,086	1,606,752	35,350
HS2	4,161	1,160,847	0.00	130	24	0	3,004,042	1,840,545	2,650
HS3	36,000	8,756,426	0.03	150	92	4	12,811,104	4,038,865	15,813
HS4	12,951	7,924,474	0.00	222	122	10	14,582,957	6,624,283	34,200
HS5	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
K1	9,877	2,498,928	0.00	150	55	0	6,409,279	3,906,051	4,300
K2	11,572	566,048	0.00	210	71	3	5,690,872	5,117,624	7,200
L1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
L2	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

* The solver failed to provide an integer-feasible solution within 10h of computation.

Table 5.3: Results for the exact solutions of the non-robust integrated problem

Inst.	CPU (in sec.)	Z^*	Opt. gap	Flights covered by			Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignments cost	Crew pairing costs
				A320	B757	B777			
HS1	11,502	-215,105	0.00	71	55	2	1,422,704	1,604,473	33,336
HS2	3,892	1,154,234	0.00	140	14	0	3,004,042	1,829,291	20,517
HS3	18,318	8,734,820	0.00	148	94	0	12,816,447	4,038,478	43,149
HS4	10,332	7,886,226	0.00	219	125	10	14,585,170	6,619,731	79,213
HS5	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
K1	5,544	2,510,750	0.00	163	42	0	6,409,279	3,893,094	5,435
K2	8,571	582,792	0.00	226	55	3	5,689,569	5,098,625	8,152
L1	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
L2	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

* The solver failed to provide an integer-feasible solution within 10h of computation.

5.6.3 Results for the decomposition procedure

Next, we present computational results for the decomposition procedure of the proposed matheuristic, which involves solving a MIP relaxation of the master problem and then sequentially solving the reduced problem separately for each aircraft family based on the fleet assignments obtained before. Table 5.4 provides results obtained for the decomposition procedure when applied to the robust model, and Table 5.5 displays results obtained for the non-robust model. We report run times for the MIP relaxation, for the decomposition procedure, and the aggregated run time in each table. We provide the values of the objective functions obtained after relaxation and decomposition phases, denoted by Z^{MIP} and Z^D , respectively. The former value yields an upper bound on the optimal objective function value, while the latter represents a valid lower bound. We also compute the percentage gap (%Gap) between Z^D and the objective function value of the exact solution, Z^* . If the latter does not exist, we instead use Z^{MIP} .

Table 5.4: Results of the decomposition procedure solutions of the robust integrated problem

Inst.	MIP relaxation		Decomposition						
	CPU (in sec.)	Z^{MIP}	CPU (in secs.)	Z^D	%Gap	Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignments cost	Robustness penalties	CPU (tot.)
HS1	121	-179,253	1	-224,003	1.81	1,424,739	1,603,992	44,750	122
HS2	17	1,174,966	8	1,121,116	3.42	3,004,042	1,829,076	53,850	26
HS3	241	8,782,290	7	8,748,490	0.09	12,819,772	4,037,484	33,798	248
HS4	1,072	7,966,557	16	7,897,157	0.34	14,588,100	6,621,543	69,400	1,088
HS5	1,535	16,955,224	17	16,910,724	0.26	23,647,625	6,692,423	44,478	1,552
K1	781	2,516,255	10	2,462,105	1.47	6,409,279	3,893,121	54,053	791
K2	236	589,875	14	530,575	6.27	5,654,499	5,064,624	59,300	250
L1	5,931	9,215,280	24	9,149,730	0.71	17,896,032	8,680,752	65,550	5,955
L2	13,552	14,228,774	486	14,146,574	0.58	26,407,407	12,178,633	82,200	14,038

First, we see that solving the MIP relaxation of these instances is burdensome. The solution time required for the largest data instance is about four hours. Second, we observe that the decomposition procedure can produce integer solutions for all instances within short computation times. Third, we observe a small percentage gap (less than 1%) to the optimal solution, except in few cases. A closer

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Table 5.5: Results for the decomposition procedure solutions of the non-robust integrated problem

Inst.	MIP relaxation		Decomposition						
	CPU (in sec.)	Z^{MIP}	CPU (in secs.)	Z^D	%Gap	Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignments cost	Crew pairing costs	CPU (tot.)
HS1	193	-179,253	2	-225,904	5.02	1,424,739	1,603,992	46,651	195
HS2	16	1,174,966	3	1,152,751	0.13	3,004,042	1,829,076	22,215	19
HS3	286	8,782,288	4	8,733,304	0.02	12,819,772	4,037,484	48,984	290
HS4	1,052	7,966,557	3	7,885,863	0.00	14,588,100	6,621,543	80,695	1,055
HS5	1,927	16,955,224	8	16,846,104	0.64	23,647,625	6,692,423	109,098	1,935
K1	735	2,520,934	3	2,490,220	0.82	6,409,279	3,893,024	26,035	738
K2	256	589,875	7	580,361	0.42	5,654,499	5,064,624	9,514	263
L1	5,879	9,215,280	21	9,124,899	0.98	17,896,032	8,680,752	90,381	5,900
L2	13,992	14,228,774	118	14,124,987	0.73	26,407,407	12,178,633	103,787	14,110

examination of the results shows that passenger revenues and aircraft assignment costs contribute most to the objective function. By maintaining the integrality of their associated decision variables in the first stage, we obtain near-optimal solutions. These observations indicate the enormous advantage of the decomposition procedure for large instances of airline planning problems. The hierarchical structure of decisions making within this class of problems greatly simplifies their solution.

5.6.4 Results for the proximity search algorithm

We present in this section the results of the improvement phase, which invokes the proximity search. Table 5.6 and Table 5.7 summarize the results of the proximity search when applied to both variants of our problem. They also display the number of iterations required before the algorithm converges and the percentage of improvement between the starting and final solutions. We denote by Z^{PS} the value of the solution's objective function when the proximity search terminates.

Table 5.6: Results for the proximity search solutions of the robust integrated problem

Inst.	CPU(in secs.)	Z^{PS}	Number of iterations	% Improv.	% Gap	Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignments cost	Robustness penalties
HS1	5,536	-220,386	8	1.61	0.17	1,422,652	1,606,388	36,650
HS2	575	1,160,594	24	3.52	0.02	3,004,042	1,840,698	2,750
HS3	3,889	8,751,047	2	0.03	0.06	12,810,640	4,037,627	21,966
HS4	1,065	7,912,951	3	0.20	0.15	14,585,530	6,630,029	42,550
HS5	18,000	16,955,224	1	0.00	0.26	23,647,625	6,692,423	44,478
K1	3,948	2,497,074	12	1.42	0.07	6,409,279	3,907,303	4,902
K2	3,941	565,672	35	6.61	0.07	5,691,154	5,119,732	5,750
L1	18,000	9,215,280	1	0.00	0.71	17,896,032	8,680,752	65,550
L2	18,000	14,228,774	1	0.00	0.58	26,407,407	12,178,633	82,200

Table 5.7: Results for the proximity search solutions of the non-robust integrated problem

Inst.	CPU(in secs.)	Z^{PS}	Number of iterations	% Improv.	% Gap	Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignments cost	Flight-time credit
HS1	896	-215,314	15	4.69	0.10	1,422,703	1,604,681	33,336
HS2	59	1,153,948	3	0.10	0.02	3,004,042	1,829,583	20,511
HS3	1,274	8,733,313	2	0.00	0.02	12,819,763	4,037,484	48,966
HS4	342	7,885,870	2	0.00	0.00	14,588,093	6,621,543	80,679
HS5	2,798	16,862,934	3	0.10	0.54	23,647,972	6,692,766	92,273
K1	1,387	2,508,520	8	0.73	0.09	6,409,253	3,893,873	6,860
K2	9,120	582,696	5	0.40	0.02	5,689,569	5,098,623	8,250
L1	18,000	9,215,280	1	0.00	0.98	17,896,032	8,680,752	90,381
L2	18,000	14,228,774	1	0.00	0.73	26,407,407	12,178,633	103,787

Interestingly, we found that by slightly adjusting the fleeting decisions, the proximity search improves the starting robust solution in six out of nine instances, with an average improvement of 2.23%. In some cases, the percentage improvements are pretty substantial and exceed 6% of the objective of the starting solution. The proximity search did not improve the current solution in three instances. The maximum

optimality gap is 0.98%. However, since we use an upper bound to calculate the optimality gaps, this is a conservative estimate for the performance of the overall matheuristic. The improvements are minor for solutions of the non-robust problem with an average of 0.86%. Omitting robustness considerations in the first phase of the decomposition procedure produces less robust solutions, yielding considerable room for improvement. Indeed, penalties incurred from violating robustness policies decreased on average by over 60%. In the non-robust problem, robustness is not enforced, and the starting solutions are thus near-optimal.

We observe that the proximity search does not require, in most instances, a tremendous computational effort. First, the proximity objective function is helpful in speeding up the solution of the LP relaxations by driving the heuristics embedded in the MIP solvers. Also, the effect of the cut-off constraint on tightening the problem's LP relaxation might explain this observation. Our experiments also show that the algorithm tractability is sensitive to the tolerance parameter θ . If a higher tolerance θ is considered, the algorithm will converge within fewer iterations. However, each iteration can take extensive computational time to produce an integer solution.

5.6.5 Robustness analysis

We propose some robustness metrics to measure the performance of robust schedules generated by our approaches. We report the number of short crew connections, the number of critical crew connections, the number of short aircraft connections, the number of crews following aircraft, the flight-time credit, the cost of aircraft assignments, and the passenger revenue. Moreover, to examine the benefits of incorporating robustness policies in airline schedules, the robust problem's metrics (obtained by the most efficient approach) were contrasted with those obtained when solving the non-robust counterpart. Table 5.8 provides a summary of the comparison results. We also indicate in Table 5.8 the number of shared aircraft and crew connections, where a crew can potentially follow the aircraft. For any robustness metric, referred here by RM_i , we compute the percentage deviation $100 \times \frac{RM_i^r - RM_i^{nr}}{RM_i^{nr}}$ between their non-robust, and robust values. We display in Table 5.9 the minimum, maximum, and average percentage deviations.

Table 5.8: Robustness metrics and schedules' performance: with and without robustness policies

Inst.	Model	Short crew connections	Critical crew connections	Critical aircraft connections	Crews following aircraft	Shared connections	Flight-time credit	Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignments costs
HS1	Robust	0	2	25	66	100	47,405	1,422,086	1,606,752
	Non-robust	10	14	39	40	100	33,336	1,422,704	1,604,473
HS2	Robust	0	2	6	92	137	33,897	3,004,042	1,840,545
	Non-robust	16	38	74	52	137	20,517	3,004,042	1,829,291
HS3	Robust	0	1	21	135	202	66,010	12,811,104	4,038,865
	Non-robust	17	31	71	57	202	43,149	12,816,447	4,038,478
HS4	Robust	0	9	52	189	291	89,161	14,582,957	6,624,283
	Non-robust	21	36	105	68	291	79,213	14,585,170	6,619,731
HS5	Robust	14	22	86	120	315	162,375	23,647,625	6,692,423
	Non-robust	34	59	86	71	315	92,222	23,647,972	6,692,766
K1	Robust	0	0	18	99	143	11,169	6,409,279	3,906,051
	Non-robust	42	67	79	31	143	5,435	6,409,279	3,893,094
K2	Robust	0	2	16	141	195	15,746	5,690,872	5,117,624
	Non-robust	55	91	108	31	195	8,152	5,689,569	5,098,625
L1	Robust	21	43	172	167	425	141,407	17,896,032	8,680,752
	Non-robust	46	79	292	81	425	93,352	17,896,032	8,680,752
L2	Robust	17	38	210	154	537	225,665	26,407,407	12,178,633
	Non-robust	69	122	368	99	537	105,380	26,407,407	12,178,633

These results show that for all instances, the robust problem produces consistently more resilient schedules. The short crew connections, which exhibit a crew sit time shorter than the aircraft turn around time and thereby are highly sensitive to disruptions, are avoided as much as possible. The number of short crew connections were reduced on average by 87.6%. Similarly, the critical crew connections were decreased, on average, by 80% when penalized in the objective function. One can also notice a substantial reduction in the number of critical aircraft connections by 55% on average. The improvements were found to be of a smaller magnitude for instances whose optimal solutions are unknown. At the same time,

Table 5.9: Robustness metrics comparison

	Short crew connections	Critical crew connections	Critical aircraft connections	Crews following aircraft	Flight-time credit	Passenger revenue	Aircraft assignment cost
Minimum deviation (in %)	54.35	45.57	0.00	-354.84	-114.14	-0.02	-0.62
Maximum deviation (in %)	100.00	100.00	91.89	-55.56	-12.56	0.04	0.01
Average deviation (in %)	87.61	80.80	55.01	-140.18	-68.15	0.01	-0.17

restricting aircraft changes in the robust model promotes schedules where crew often follow aircraft. In robust solutions, the percentage of connections where crew follow aircraft ranges between 28.7% and 72.3%. In sharp contrast, the percentage varies between 15.9% and 38.8% for non-robust solutions. These slight schedule modifications can further protect the airline schedules against delays and thereby enhance its on-time performance, which will ultimately have a positive impact on its reputation and profitability. Of course, this level of protection comes at the price of increased operational costs. Table 5.8 shows that the aircraft assignment costs increased on average by 0.17% in the robust solutions, and the passenger revenue decreased by 0.01%; however, the potential gain from robustness might amply justify these deviations. The flight-time credit, which accounts for the crew idle time, increased on average by 68%. Since we are maximizing the schedules' protection, the generated solutions exhibit a maximum increase in pairing costs to their nominal values unless one is willing to accept a lower protection level. One could also implement a control parameter to ensure a trade-off between costs and protection.

5.7 Conclusion

In this paper, the robust integrated fleet assignment, aircraft routing, and crew pairing problem was investigated to gain insights into the benefits of fully integrated robust airline planning approaches. We first developed a mathematical formulation that adopts a node-arc flow network representation, thus yielding a polynomial number of variables and constraints. The proposed model accommodates several realistic considerations such as itinerary-based demands and various crew work rules. We induce robustness in the formulation by promoting schedules where crew follow aircraft and by judiciously reallocating the buffer times to minimize tight connections. Such a strategy maintains the tractability of the formulation as well as reduces the degree of conservatism.

A matheuristic solution framework, that combines a decomposition approach and a proximity search, was developed and implemented. The decomposition approach enables building a feasible solution to the problem, and the proximity search attempts to improve it iteratively. Both procedures require solving mathematical programming models in a heuristic framework which allows for easy implementation. Importantly, this solution method can be applied to general complex optimization problems where important decisions are optimized at the highest level.

We presented the results of computational experiments that were carried out on real-world instances having up to 14,014 itineraries, 646 flights, and 202 aircraft, which provide empirical evidence of the proposed approach's efficacy. We first emphasize that the proposed model can be solved using a commercial solver for small and medium-sized instances. Hence, as opposed to set partitioning formulations, our model does not require the implementation of sophisticated exact algorithms such as Benders decomposition or column generation. Furthermore, computational experiments show that the developed matheuristic provides high-quality solutions. When optimal solutions are available, the matheuristic finds solutions within 0.2% of the optimal value. When no optimal solution is known, the upper bound's average percentage gap is strictly below 1%.

Finally, we assessed the robustness of the delivered solutions by using several robustness metrics. We have observed that our robust model leads to significant advantages (much fewer tight connections and more crews following aircraft) at the expense of a negligible drop in revenue (-0.01%). This insignificant degradation is offset by the additional gain in robustness, which would ultimately improve the punctuality of the airline and, consequently, lead to better profitability.

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Appendix 5.A Aircraft routing linearization.

To enhance the solvability of the integrated model, we propose applying the special-structured Reformulation-Linearization Technique (RLT) of Sherali, Adams, and Driscoll [35] to derive a tight, equivalent linear model representation of this problem. Toward this end, first, consider constraints (2.5) and (2.6), we linearize these constraints using the substitutions:

$$\bar{\alpha}_{jlk} = u_j x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\alpha_{jlk} = u_{lk} x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Accordingly, constraints (2.5) and (2.6) become:

$$\bar{\alpha}_{jlk} = t_l^k x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k^M, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_{jlk} = \alpha_{jlk} x_{jlk} + t_l x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k^{NM}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

To ensure the product relationships (A.1) and (A.2) within the RLT process, consider the following set P_j^k , $j \in L, k \in K$, implied by (2.3)-(2.4), and (2.37):

$$P_j^k = \left\{ x : \begin{array}{l} \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} = \sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} x_{jlk} \\ \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} \leq 1 \\ x_{jlk} \geq 0, \quad (j, l) \in A_k \end{array} \right\} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Since P_j^k implies $\{0 \leq x_{jlk} \leq 1, (j, l) \in A_k\}$, $j \in L, k \in K$, it suffices to take interproducts of the constraints defining P_j^k within (2.7) for each $j \in L, k \in K$, to enforce (A.1)-(A.2) while deriving a tight linear programming representation (see Sherali, Adams, and Driscoll [35]). Hence, for each $j \in L, f \in F, k \in K_f$, multiplying constraint (2.7) by both x_{jlk} and x_{ljk} , $(j, l) \in A_k$, $(l, j) \in A_k$, we respectively obtain the following inequalities on linearization (where we have interchanged the indices l and j for the first case):

$$t_l x_{jlk} \leq \bar{\alpha}_{jlk} \leq t_k^{max} x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$t_j x_{jlk} \leq \alpha_{jlk} \leq t_k^{max} x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Next, multiplying the first constraint of (A.5) in P_j^k by simply u_j (noting that this is an equality restriction), we derive the following constraint on linearization using (A.1)-(A.2):

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} \bar{\alpha}_{ljk} = \sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} \alpha_{jlk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Finally, multiplying the second constraint of (A.5) in P_j^k with the two bound-factors in (2.7) lifts the latter (noting (A.6)) to the following restrictions on linearization using (A.1) and (A.2):

$$t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} (\bar{\alpha}_{ljk} - t_j x_{ljk}) \leq u_j \leq t_k^{MAX} - \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} (t_k^{MAX} x_{ljk} - \bar{\alpha}_{ljk}), \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Thus, by Sherali, Adams, and Driscoll [35], we can derive an equivalent lifted model by replacing (2.5), (2.6) and (2.7) in the problem with (A.3)-(A.9). However, observe that the variable u_j appears only in (A.9) within the resulting model. So this constraint can be eliminated and the u -variables can be determined a posteriori using (A.9) so long as

$$t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} (\bar{\alpha}_{ljk} - t_j x_{ljk}) \leq t_k^{MAX} - \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} (t_k^{MAX} x_{ljk} - \bar{\alpha}_{ljk}), \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \quad i.e., ,$$

$$t_j (1 - \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk}) \leq t_k^{MAX} (1 - \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk}), \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K.$$

which automatically holds because of $t_j \leq t_k^{MAX}$ and $\sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} \leq 1$ by (A.5). Thus, we can drop (A.9) and replace (2.4), (2.5) and (2.6) with (A.3)-(A.8).

By using (A.3) and (A.4) to further eliminate the $\bar{\alpha}$ -variables from (A.3)-(A.8), we readily establish the following proposition.

Proposition 5.A.1. *Constraints (A.3)-(A.8) can be replaced by the restrictions, which together with (2.2)-(2.4), yield an equivalent set of constraints, even in the sense of the continuous linear program (LP) relaxation*

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} \alpha_{jlk} = t_j \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} + \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k^{NM}} \alpha_{jlk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$t_j x_{jlk} \leq \alpha_{jlk} \leq b_{jl}^{t_k} x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K, \quad (j, l) \in A_k, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$\text{where } b_{jl}^{t_k} = \begin{cases} t_k^{MAX} - t_l, & (j, l) \in A_k^{NM}, \\ t_k^{MAX}, & (j, l) \in A_k^M. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Finally, we use (A.1) to equivalently rewrite (2.8). We obtain the following constraint:

$$\sum_{j \in L} \left(1 - \sum_{(j,l) \in A_{1,k} \cup A_{3,k}} x_{jlk} \right) \leq N_k - n_k, \quad k \in K. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Appendix 5.B Crew pairing linearization.

We linearize constraints (2.14)-(2.15) following Ben Ahmed, Zeghal Mansour, and Haouari [5] using the following substitutions:

$$\bar{\beta}_{jlf} = \mu_{jf} y_{jl}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\beta_{jlf} = \mu_{lf} y_{jl}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Thus, (2.14)-(2.15) get transformed to:

$$\bar{\beta}_{jlf} = y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^D, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\bar{\beta}_{jlf} = \beta_{jlf} + y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

To ensure the product relationships (B.1) and (B.2) within the RLT process, consider the following set $\bar{P}_j^f, j \in L, f \in F$, implied by (2.11), (2.12) and (2.37):

$$\bar{P}_j^f = \left\{ y : \begin{array}{l} \sum_{(l,j) \in B_f} y_{ljf} = \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} y_{jlf} \\ \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} y_{jlf} \leq 1 \\ y_{jlf} \geq 0, \quad (j,l) \in B_f \end{array} \right\} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Since \bar{P}_j^f implies $\{0 \leq y_{jlf} \leq 1, (j,l) \in B_f\}$, it suffices to take the interproducts of the constraints defining \bar{P}_j^f with (2.21) for each $j \in L, f \in F$, to enforce (B.1) and (B.2) while deriving a tight linear programming representation (see Sherali, Adams, and Driscoll [35]). hence for each $j \in L, f \in F$, multiplying constraints (2.21) by y_{jlf} , and by y_{ljf} , we respectively obtain the following inequalities on linearization (where we have interchanged the indices l and j for the second case):

$$y_{jlf} \leq \beta_{jlf} \leq \mu_f^{MAX}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f \setminus B_f^D, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \bar{\beta}_{jlf} \leq \mu_f^{MAX}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f \setminus B_f^A. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Next, multiplying the first constraint of (B.5) in \bar{P}_j^f by simply μ_{jf} , we derive the following constraint on linearization using (B.1) and (B.2):

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in B_f} \bar{\beta}_{ljf} = \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \beta_{jlf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F. \quad (\text{B.8})$$

This is equivalent to:

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \bar{\beta}_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{2,f}} \bar{\beta}_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_f^D} \bar{\beta}_{ljf} = \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \beta_{jlf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F.$$

We next eliminate the $\bar{\beta}$ -variables from these restrictions using the identities (B.3) and (B.4), which yields:

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} (\beta_{ljf} + y_{ljf}) + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{2,f}} y_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_f^D} y_{ljf} = \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \beta_{jlf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F. \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Using (2.2) we obtain:

$$1 + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \beta_{ljf} = \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \beta_{jlf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F. \quad (\text{B.10})$$

Proposition 5.B.1. *Constraints (B.1)-(B.10) can be replaced by the following restrictions, which together with (2.11) and (2.12), are equivalent to these constraints even in the continuous (LP relaxation) sense:*

$$1 + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \beta_{ljf} = \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \beta_{jlf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (\text{B.11})$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \beta_{jlf} \leq (\mu^{MAX} - 1)y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (\text{B.12})$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \beta_{jlf} \leq \mu^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^D. \quad (\text{B.13})$$

The nonlinear constraints (2.16)-(2.28) and (2.32) can be lifted and linearized following an identical derivation by defining the new set of RLT variables

$$\chi_{jlf} = \varphi_{jf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.14})$$

$$\bar{\chi}_{jl} = \varphi_{lf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.15})$$

$$\zeta_{jlf} = \lambda_{jf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.16})$$

$$\bar{\zeta}_{jlf} = \lambda_{lf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.17})$$

$$\sigma_{jlf} = \nu_{jf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.18})$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{jlf} = \nu_{lf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.19})$$

$$\vartheta_{jlf} = \eta_{jf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f, \quad (\text{B.20})$$

$$\bar{\vartheta}_{jlf} = \eta_{lf} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_f. \quad (\text{B.21})$$

In doing so, constraints (2.16)-(2.19), (2.23)-(2.28), and (2.32) can be written as follows:

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \chi_{jlf} = t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \chi_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (\text{B.22})$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \chi_{jlf} \leq (\varphi^{MAX} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (\text{B.23})$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \chi_{jlf} \leq \varphi^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_A^f, \quad (\text{B.24})$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \zeta_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} s_{ljf} y_{ljf} + t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \zeta_{jlf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (\text{B.25})$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \zeta_{jlf} \leq (\lambda^{MAX} - s_{jlf} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (\text{B.26})$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \zeta_{jlf} \leq \lambda^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_A^f, \quad (\text{B.27})$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \sigma_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_f^D \cup B_{2,f}} y_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_{2,f}} \sigma_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (\text{B.28})$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \sigma_{jlf} \leq (\nu^{MAX} - 1) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (\text{B.29})$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \sigma_{jlf} \leq \nu^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_A^f, \quad (\text{B.30})$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \vartheta_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} s_{ljf} y_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{2,f}} l_{ljf} y_{ljf} + t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_{2,f}} \vartheta_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad f \in F, \quad (\text{B.31})$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \vartheta_{jlf} \leq (\eta^{MAX} - s_{jlf} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (\text{B.32})$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \vartheta_{jlf} \leq (\eta^{MAX} - l_{jlf} - t_l) y_{jlf}, \quad f \in F, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (\text{B.33})$$

$$\vartheta_{j,0,f} + l^{MIN} \leq Dd_{jf}, \quad j \in L^A, \quad f \in F. \quad (\text{B.34})$$

Appendix 5.C Reduced aircraft routing and crew pairing problem.

The reduced aircraft routing and crew pairing model is written $\forall f \in F$:

$$\min \sum_{(j,l) \in (B_f \setminus B_f^S)} \rho(y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}) + \sum_{k \in K_f} \sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} \gamma_{jlk} x_{jlk} + \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \gamma_{jlf} (y_{jlf} - z_{jlf}), \quad (\text{C.1})$$

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} = 1, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (C.2)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} x_{jlk} = 1, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (C.3)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in A_k} \alpha_{jlk} = t_j \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k} x_{ljk} + \sum_{(l,j) \in A_k^{NM}} \alpha_{jlk}, \quad j \in L, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (C.4)$$

$$t_j x_{jlk} \leq \alpha_{jlk} \leq b_{jl}^{tk} x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j,l) \in A_k, \quad (C.5)$$

$$\sum_{j \in L} (1 - \sum_{(l,j) \in A_{1,k} \cup A_{3,k}} x_{ljk}) \leq N_k - n_k, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (C.6)$$

$$\sum_{(l,j) \in B_f} y_{ljf} = 1, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.7)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} y_{jlf} = 1, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.8)$$

$$\sum_{(0,j,f) \in B_f^D} y_{0,jf} - \sum_{(j,0,f) \in B_f^A} y_{j,0,f} = 0, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.9)$$

$$1 + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \beta_{ljf} = \sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \beta_{jlf}, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.10)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \beta_{jlf} \leq (\mu^{MAX} - 1)y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (C.11)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \beta_{jlf} \leq \mu^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_f^D, \quad (C.12)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \chi_{jlf} = t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \chi_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.13)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \chi_{jlf} \leq (\varphi^{MAX} - t_l)y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (C.14)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \chi_{jlf} \leq \varphi^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_A^f, \quad (C.15)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \zeta_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} s_{ljf} y_{ljf} + t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} \zeta_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.16)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \zeta_{jlf} \leq (\lambda^{MAX} - s_{jlf} - t_l)y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (C.17)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \zeta_{jlf} \leq \lambda^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f} \cup B_A^f, \quad (C.18)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \sigma_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_f^D \cup B_{2,f}} y_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_{2,f}} \sigma_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.19)$$

$$y_{jl} \leq \sigma_{jlf} \leq (\nu^{MAX} - 1)y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (C.20)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq \sigma_{jlf} \leq \nu^{MAX} y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_A^f, \quad (C.21)$$

$$\sum_{(j,l) \in B_f} \vartheta_{jlf} = \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f}} s_{ljf} y_{ljf} + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{2,f}} l_{ljf} y_{ljf} + t_j + \sum_{(l,j) \in B_{1,f} \cup B_{2,f}} \vartheta_{ljf}, \quad j \in L, \quad (C.22)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \vartheta_{jlf} \leq (\eta^{MAX} - s_{jlf} - t_l)y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{1,f}, \quad (C.23)$$

$$t_j y_{jlf} \leq \vartheta_{jlf} \leq (\eta^{MAX} - l_{jlf} - t_l)y_{jlf}, \quad (j,l) \in B_{2,f}, \quad (C.24)$$

$$\vartheta_{j,0,f} + l^{MIN} \leq Dd_{j,f}, \quad j \in L^A, \quad (C.25)$$

$$y_{jlf} \leq x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j,l) \in B_f^S \cap A_k, \quad (C.26)$$

$$0 \leq z_{jlf} \leq x_{jlk}, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j,l) \in B_f \cap A_k, \quad (C.27)$$

$$0 \leq z_{jlf} \leq y_{jlf}, \quad k \in K_f, \quad (j,l) \in B_f \cap A_k, \quad (C.28)$$

$$(x, y, z) \text{ binary.} \quad (C.29)$$